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The Influence of Online Studies and Information using Learning Analytics

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Abstract

This research will help people with inadequate knowledge to get a better understanding of online study or e-learning. Through this study, the social impact of online users or learners can be increased, and the users can have a clear idea of online study. In this research, the graphs will be presented according to country, gender, age, online resources, etc. showing the impact of online study and information on online users. The learners will get an understandable knowledge of the type of sources, what is their purpose, and resources people can use in online study. From this, the learners will get a guide or path that how easily they can learn online for study in a more flexible way. The outcomes are visualized using the R language and Tableau with pre-processed data.

Keywords: *Online studies, analysis, investigation, techniques, comparison, and visualization.*

1. Introduction

Learning Analytics (LA) is a multi-disciplinary area concerning online studies, synthetic intelligence, information retrieval, statistics, and visualization. LA is also an area where various related study areas of Technology Enhanced Learning (TEL) converge. These encompass academic analytics, action research, educational statistics mining, recommender systems, and personalized adaptive studying. LA is primarily based on four dimensions, particularly statistics and environments, i.e., information, stakeholders, targets, and techniques [1].

Nowadays, Learning Analytics (LA) is one of the main subsequences in the educational sector. The online study took a large portion of it. It has interested to work in online studies related to LA. Until now, there are many books, journals, and articles about LA. It is a new sector where

the readers can see online users in different sectors have been introduced.

The goal of this paper is to develop a new strategy for online study. This research shows the most used learning resources and the learning tools, such as traditional classroom-based systems or Massive Open Online Courses (Moocs) [2]. So, educational institutions can design the lectures online for their targeted students. So studying this research, anyone, specifically students, can be motivated by the online learning system. For example, in online learning, getting detailed information is easier. Online learning has an option to see the videos or tutorials, which is often very helpful & better for the project. Here, the percentages of online education of males or females can also be shown by visualizations. With the help of this research study, institutions such as universities, schools, and colleges can improve their study system. The teacher or professor can motivate students to change the study system to see other study purposes or gender-wise study purposes. The university also can design the lecture types for targeted students.

To achieve the objective of this research, the following process, such as monitoring, prediction, adaptation, personalization, awareness, and recommendations, has been fulfilled. Online studies help users more to come closer to practical studies.

Moreover, students get more engaged in their studies and help them achieve a good result. By reading this research, user or student will adapt to online study more frequently. Because they will inherit knowledge from this research that what type of resource people use so that they will get a

path. It will also improve future awareness of online studies. It will help learners how they can efficiently study online, and it is also used to recommend the learning source [3].

In this research, the participants' answers have been recorded face to face or via social media, web, and e-mail. Here, the target population is the user or student who uses the internet in their daily life. Alternatively, it can be said that people who have knowledge about online studies but prefer to study offline or with books. At the end of the survey, various graphs can be created by collecting all data, attributes, and scale ratings. These depend on the research requirements, the graphs that can be designed according to personal information or general information. Personal information includes age, education, profession, and others. General information includes nationality, gender, and duration of study in online studies, resources, sources, and types of studies.

2. Methodology and Implementation

2.1 Concept

In this research, an opportunity has been tried to provide for the general internet user why online studies are more flexible and secure. Moreover, it allows instructors to evaluate their teaching strategies. The development process was designed following the What-Why-How framework [4]. Here, in the paper, raw data will be collected from different sources based on studies and research. The system will visualize the following evaluation.

- Analysis of data from different sources
- Performance of users or stakeholders
- Country-wise data analysis [5].

The diagram of a simplified view of Learning Analytics (LA) is shown in figure-1,

Figure 1: General concept of LA (Modified) [3].

2.2 Learning Analytics Methods in Education

The supported open learning is a unique method of distance learning called "Supported Open Learning." Some key factors of the methodologies are as follows:

- Learning analytics analysis and process
- Data visualization tools and techniques
- Prediction
- Clustering
- Relationship mining
- Discovery with models
- Separation of data for use in the process of human judgment etc.

The implementation of the methods helps to meet the requirements of the online users as well as the teachers and the students. Such as,

- Flexible - students work where and when they want to study in order to meet their requirement, family, and other commitments.
- All-inclusive - students receive all the high-quality materials they need to learn
- Supportive - personal tutors provide academic expertise, guidance and feedback, and conduct group tutorials; and faculty advisors are available for other aspects of study
- Social - students meet through tutorials, online conferences, study networks, and course forums.

The paper's analysis provided a comprehensive overview of the analytic learning methods, benefits, and challenges of using Big Data in education. Examination of these aspects revealed positive contributions [5, 6].

In this research, the indicators used in the graphs are the age, country, gender, educational degree, starting year of online study, time duration, online study goals, online study purpose, online resources, online sources, and user remark. Considering the online survey, the appropriate visualization was identified based on different graphs. The raw data has been processed by programming R. The analyses utilizing the What-Why-How framework, represented by the so-called Identifier Description Cards (IDC), are shown in figure-2 and figure-3.

Figure 2: IDC of the Vis Idiom on the Starting Year of Web Surfing Among Online Users.

Figure 3: IDC of the Vis Idiom on Online Users in Different Countries by Gender.

Therefore, this research provides a detailed description, and the implementation, and development process of the application tool. The teachers can evaluate their teaching strategy by evaluating their exam styles; analyze enrollment patterns, average grades, and students' information. Teachers can do this through the process of learning analytics. Student can also evaluate their progress through this process. However, focused on the general user's online studies aspect, the teachers' and students aspect was not included in the initial design process. As mentioned already, mainly focused on the percentages of people who study online or who want to learn online. Then, it has focused on teachers and students. Here, the platform to provide an opportunity for teachers to evaluate their teaching strategies has extended. Students can also do their

research or contact the teachers for guidance through this process. This part of this survey is, therefore, only discussed in the result section of this paper. The research paper's core aim was to visualize online studies data country-wise in a useful way and through the online survey process. The development process consisted of three stages: Observation, Prototyping, or evaluation of the prototypes, and implementation.

Before entering the actual implementation segment, generated ideas, and layout concepts must be tested on the relevant target group. As the call to the next phase implies, prototypes must help generate comments, and ensure consumer acceptance. Besides, prototypes can be used to review exceptional concepts and designs and make good layout choices [7].

With the help of a tool named Moqups, distinct prototypes for rapid prototyping, distinct prototypes have been developed. All of which confirmed a unique color theme, included distinct attributes, one-of-a-kind indicators, and few changes in functionality, even as always consistent with the recognized center functionalities, are developed. It is because of the education, age differences of online users, and online users' chances in Asia compared to Europe, the US, or other countries.

2.2 Tools and Technologies

As we can see, data has been managed to distinguish between logic, views, and especially the styling in this research. Functions that need to be shared across multiple pages are exported to R programming files. The browser's local storage and query parameters were used for passing variables (e.g., filters, attributes, indicators, study online) between pages. The data is stored, and loaded from a CSV file, displaying only from the survey's collected data.

3. Survey Process and Analysis

Generally, the survey data are collected from the questions from person to person. The survey types have been chosen by the requirement of the research.

In every survey, there is a theory according to the research. In that case, the concept should be reliable, and transparent. The measure of the survey depends on the questionnaires and the population of the survey. The more the participant, the accurate result can be achieved. After that, the statistical result of the data has been obtained. Here, the content of the questionnaires, and the scope of the survey depend on the research. There can also be time boundaries. There are other terms, reliability, and validity of the data, which depend on the research, and the survey types [8].

Finally, the response of the end-user refers to the comments of the participants. The answer to this is the data that completes all other responses. They show that online education is more effective than traditional learning or not. After obtaining all the data, it has been analyzed and visualized by programming language R, and Tableau software.

3.1 What-Why-How Framework

Acquainting the most useful visualization language for a particular use case is a challenge. Some researchers argue that "The vast majority of possibilities within the design space will be ineffective for a unique context of use" and therefore proposes a three-part analysis named the What-Why-How framework, which represents answers to the corresponding data task idiom triplet [4].

Figure 4: What-Why-How Framework (Modified) [5].

Because of the research requirements resulting from the previous survey, suitable user goals were diagnosed to determine which suitable visualizations should be found. The analysis using the What-Why-How framework can be presented using the so-called Identifier Description Card (IDC) [6].

3.2 Research Questions Analysis

There are three key components that need further clarification for higher education stakeholders to help them effectively apply learning analytics in higher education. Educators must face the task of reviewing the literature to become familiar with LA methods, benefits, and challenges. To address the problem, the following questions guided this review:

1. What techniques are available to perform learning analytics in education?
2. What are the advantages of using learning analytics in education?
3. What are the limitations of using learning analytics in education?

Further identifying and describing LA methods, benefits, and challenges can easily help educators in higher education integrate LA to improve student learning [9].

The what-why-how analysis enabled the selection of the most commonly used visualization. To understand the Human-Centered Design (HCD) approach, the idea was presented to potential clients and the accompanying inquiries were conducted to identify goals and questions that a second degree might have regarding an emotionally supportive determination network [10]. At these points, several research questions arise and are discussed as follows:

1. What functionality would help to find specific information?
2. What are the essential attributes of online study?
3. What would be the desire for a survey useful to educational institutions?
4. What type of general information is the user looking for online?
5. Why are online surveys most popular in Europe and the USA and not in other Asian countries?
6. Why are young stars more interested in online studies than adults?
7. Why is online data more protected and secure than store massive amounts of data by documents?
8. Why is digital data easy to handle so that freelancers and clients alike can benefit from it?
9. What type of news or information are job holders or business people looking for online?
10. Why are online studies more convenient in every way these days?

The responses helped identify the core functionalities that should be given and the features of an online study that are likely to be of most interest to students, teachers, and researchers. Respondents considered the ability to compare data, a detailed overview of exciting topics among teachers and students, filtering by aspects such as exam-style, bonus points, exercises, and the ability to see data in each sector as most relevant or accessible. Online studies can reduce the problem of difficulty in finding data of any kind; the quality of data or real information can be determined very fluently as a result, and satisfaction with online studies has been identified as a key feature [11]. At the end of the discussion, further steps will show the plan to integrate

these identified core functionalities into the online studies or e-learning.

4. Visual Representation of the Findings

4.1 Results through Tableau Visualizations

In this paper, at first, the raw data has been taken from the survey, and then the raw data are analyzed. Data have been collected from indoor and outdoor surveys. Therefore the analysis part has been done with tableau software, and programming language R, and then trend data has been obtained. Thus, the graphical representation of this survey will be shown in such a way as given as follows;

Figure 5: Learning Goal or Learning Resource According to Age.

The above graph in Figure-5 is a Circle view. The chart is obtained by Tableau software by processing the data. This graph shows the relationship between learning goals and learning resource types. Learning resources and learning goals are shown on the x-axis. On the other h, it shows the range of age in the y-axis. Here, the survey data shows that among the age of 20 to 50 people do online surfing. For example, in this graph, students or users, at the age of 23, study for online tutorials. It also shows users most interested in online news, and blogs, online study materials, online articles, and tutorials that depend on age.

Figure 6: Online Users According to Gender, and Place of Studies.

In Figure-6, the graph is a Side by side bar chart. The Tableau software obtains the chart by processing the data like others. This graph shows the relationship between gender and place of online studies according to the highest number of records. Here, the place and gender are shown on the x-axis and the number of records is shown on the y-axis. According to this survey, the survey data shows that males mostly do online surfing more than females among the most top records. It also shows that in both cases, males and females preferred an online study place as a home.

Figure 7: Learning Resource Types by Gender.

The Pie charts are presented in Figure-7. It shows the rates of learning resource types according to males and female online users. Here it shows that both males and females are interested in videos and online study materials rather than other learning resources, but the percentage of females is a little bit more than males.

Figure 8: Learning Resources According to Different Year.

In figure-8, the graph is a Gantt chart. This graph shows the relationship between learning resources and different years of online studies among the participants according to the highest number of records. Here, learning resources are shown on the x-axis, and the years are shown on the y-axis. The survey data shows that most users believe that online studies are more effective in recent years than in the past.

4.2 Visualizations of R Functions

The different visualizations through R programming are as follows:

Figure 9: Starting Year of Web Surfing in Different Countries Online Users.

The above bar chart in Figure-9 has been obtained by processing the data in programming R. It mainly represents the internet surfing year of online users in the x-axis comparing with recent years shown in the y-axis. From the year 1990 to 1995, there are few online users, approximately two percent online users. Whereas in the year 2019, it is almost 49 percent among 50 percent. So, it can be said that from the past to recent more and more people are interested in surfing online.

Figure 10: Gender-Specific Review for the Learning Goals.

Figure-10 shows the percentages of gender review according to age shown in the x-axis for different learning objectives shown in the y-axis. Suppose the learning objective of females and males can be different according to age.

Figure 11: Daily Online Study Duration by Gender and Country.

The above Figure shows the time duration and gender in the x-axis, which shows online study hours per day according to different countries. Different countries are indicated on the y-axis. By this, anyone gets an idea of how often people study online. For example, in Bangladesh and Brazil, 40 percent of females surfing online on average daily two hours, whereas 80 percent of males daily surfing for approximately two hours.

Different visualizations have been made at the end of the survey, collecting all the data, attributes, and scale ratings. These depended on the research requirements, and charts have been prepared according to personal information or general information. Personal information includes age, education, profession, and general information, including nationality, gender, spending time in online studies, and types of research. Various online users' views have been visualized through the above graphs.

4.3 Limitations and Challenges

- Many websites require payment,
- Insufficient internet in rural areas,

- Sometimes correct or accurate information is not available in some sectors,
- In some cases, information is so massive that people are confused about what is correct or what to choose,
- Some people are not interested in web search, especially seniors.
- The review of the literature revealed the LA challenges about data tracking, collection, analysis, a connection with learning sciences and ethical concerns regarding legal and privacy issues.

Therefore, the problem is that the inclusion of LA in evaluating data in higher education diverts faculty attention from clearly identifying methods, benefits, and challenges of using LA in higher education. However, the literature review also revealed negative considerations for the use of learning analytics. For these reasons, a closer look at these aspects may lead to different findings.

5. Conclusions

The paper aimed to evolve online studies on the user-side. Theoretically, the approach was followed together with the What-Why-How analysis framework. This process has followed further work.

5.1 Outcome

The outcome of this research is a simple data survey in online studies. The usual use case would determine what information to choose as per requirements, research, or other studies.

At first, a minimalistic graph of online users will be shown. After that, the average percentages of each user group can be done by the visualization process. Other available categories are the necessity of previous knowledge, difficulty, pacing, and organization, satisfaction with the learned and overall quality.

5.2 Result Analysis

Initially, country-wise data collected through the survey were visualized. Different countries' online users' data has been obtained and visualized by various graphs. After that, it has been assumed that different data by different indicators can also be shown. Such as daily online study duration, age, country, gender, educational degree, online study goals, online study purpose, online resources, online sources, and user remark has been added for getting multipurpose readings.

Therefore, different strategies were investigated to support interactivity, and the raw data were processed by tableau and R programming. Moreover, starting a concept has been created. By this concept, a survey has been conducted to collect data. Then the raw data has been analyzed and achieved the expected graph through visualization.

In educational institutions, the professors and the teachers can overview online studies through these graph visualizations. So, that they can teach or guide their students properly. By reading this research paper, the general stakeholders or students can be influenced to study online and e-learning more. Moreover, the government of those countries where online studies are inadequate can influence and improve the online study service.

5.3 Further Work

In this research, most of the steps have been based on the online survey process, which was incorporated in the making plans and improvement techniques of these interactive web users. Nevertheless, because it is far from a theoretically primarily based research, the person degrees of the commonly iterative circle were only carried out once. Future steps would be sizable Testing by the target institution and implementing the resulting modifications of the application. Other ability modifications or debatable troubles situations are the facts and code base of the application.

However, due to resource restrictions, the individual stages of the data used in this paper are mainly bound to the online survey carried out. A continuation of the investigation could simply guarantee an extension of the dataset, but answer possibilities (e.g., agree, disagree, neutral) are firmly embedded in the code. This means that the type of data must follow a fixed structure for an extension of the application as it currently exists. However, since the survey was primarily based on the general online user evaluation forms, the integration of data generated from those forms should not require too much effort. Another data-related aspect is the effort involved in data adjustment. Although this survey allows the data to be exported to CSV, the exported dataset is not entirely in the desired CSV format to enable a smooth import using Programming R and tableau's CSV method. Also, special characters, commas, and different spellings of courses result in a fundamental revision of the exported dataset [12].

This research has shown that a web survey has many advantages instead of a paper-based evaluation bureaucracy. All users, along with students or teachers, are asked to complete the survey online, such as through an

online portal or email. This technique has a broader range of insurance than the distribution of the survey bureaucracy itself. Besides, the information should not be transferred from paper to digital. In the high-quality case, it enables direct integration into a current system. A more significant, variable, and easily expandable application would also be guaranteed using an established Internet framework. Due to the lack of individual experiences with a web framework, it was decided to use pure JavaScript and HTML. After a few tests run with unique frameworks at the beginning of the improvement phase, learning a new framework seemed to be an excessive time risk. Since the planned application seemed to be very manageable, the framework here would not be used here, which was considered the right decision. However, when reviewing the implementation and final code, it is definite that using a framework may have been a better choice. Of course, the code quality could have benefited from this. Besides, the extensibility of the application, in addition to its documentation, could be more accessible. The development of visualization without "programming guidelines" also made the collaboration very difficult. Loading times could also be extended by granting access to system-intensive variables. Given these types of problems, it can be said that future work should aim to advance the web survey as soon as possible.

5.4 Recommendations

In terms of future work, advanced interactions can be included in online education, such as people can survey in a massive way to get the exact percentages. A tool or software can be made through this process afterward in which the data of the whole world's online users' can be represented. By this, people and educational institutions will get a path to follow how they get more advantages in the online study that will be more influenced in online studies.

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SIMULATING ENSEMBLE LEARNING TECHNIQUE MODEL FOR DETECTING TEMPORAL ANOMALIES IN OLD PEOPLE'S HOME

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Abstract

The need to have a secure lifestyle for older persons at home is in demand more than ever. One of the major concerns for smart home systems is the capability of adapting to the user as personalizing the behavior of the home may provide improved comfort, control, and safety. The aim of this work is to (predict temporal anomalies among the aged living in older people home using ensemble learning algorithms) develop and simulate an ensemble learning algorithm for temporal anomaly detection of activities of daily living in old people's home. To achieve this goal, we applied two supervised learning algorithms which include the k-nearest neighbour (K-NN) and naïve Bayes (NB) algorithm. This two supervised learning algorithms were used to build the ensemble learning algorithm based on a 60day period secondary data collection, consisting of three of the four non-repetitive daily routine activities used for finding anomalies. The remaining data was used for testing the model. Rapidminer was used in model testing and the results showed that Ensemble learning model yielded better results than individual algorithms. This is because the two algorithms complemented each other as the strength of NB which is the stronger algorithm in the study; with capacity of handling missing value within a dataset, augmented the K-NN algorithm. The model's suitability was proven being that its average rate leads to increase in prediction accuracy. However, in this study NB algorithm was used in combination with K-NN as an ensemble learning technique, which improved k-nearest neighbour by increasing the ensemble learning model; producing a 95.0% level of accuracy as against the K-NN with an accuracy level of 71.67% singly. The result also revealed that NB algorithm is best when dealing with multivariate dataset and dataset with missing values as it individually outperformed the ensemble learning algorithm with an accuracy of 98.33% against 95.00% respectively. The ensemble learning algorithm has proven to have the capacity to handle missing values within data set, and so its average rate leads to better prediction accuracy.

Keywords: Temporal Anomalies, Aged people, Ensemble Learning Techniques, Simulation, Naïve Bayes, K- Nearest Neighbour, Supervised Learning,

1. Introduction

Anomalies are simply patterns or trends of older adults which are abnormal to their usual routine activities of daily living in a smart home whose data is collected via a wireless sensor network and stored in a central database for analysis. Areas of anomaly in these smart homes are: behavioural, spatial and temporal. However, not much has been done in the area of

temporal anomaly; hence, this paper presents simulating an ensemble model for detecting temporal anomaly in old people's home based on the duration of non-repetitive generalized activity for a period of 60 days.

Not long ago, data collection on human daily living meant carrying out surveys or using witnesses in the location of other humans to record observations on the behavioural habits. However, at the advent of microprocessor miniaturization, computing power has been implemented in mobile devices and gadgets and has almost invaded every sphere of life. This birthed the evolution of wireless, modest and affordable sensors for information collation in daily 'smart' surroundings.

This information so collected when studied using machine learning techniques, do not only give insight that can be inter-leavened in our lives but can also produce computerized domain specific support to daily living environments, for example a smart home. However, researchers have been more focused on the use of smart home automation to observe occupant's ability to carry out key Activities of Daily Living (ADL) as well as instrumented ADLs (iADLS) due to its importance in independent living for the aged and health care management [1]. Such activities include: cook_breakfast, eat_breakfast, sleeping, showering and taking medications.

Research on independent living is however not limited to dementia sufferers. Many published works have also addressed the issue of independent living in a broader sense [2], [3], [4] The smart environment can identify, model and evaluate the performance progression of dementia of the Alzheimers type in the execution of activities of daily living. The smart home can either monitor and collect the activities information of the user by means of sensors or communicate and control its environment. The former approach is widely used for monitoring, anomalous behaviour detection, behaviour diagnosis and prediction of activities in an Ambient Intelligence (AmI) environment [5], [6], [7], while the latter approach is used to intervene and interact with the user as a means of preventing accidents and reminding the user of daily routine activities at the precise time.

In this paper, a 60 day period of data from the Tulin CASAS Washington State University [8] of four non-repetitive generalized activities of daily living of an older adult was used to build and simulate an ensemble model based on naïve bayes algorithm and k-nearest neighbour algorithm for detecting anomalies in the old people's home.

2. Related work

Anomaly simply put is the deviation from the normal patterns of older adults in carrying out their daily healthy living in a context aware environment. This context aware environments could be smart homes, Ambient Intelligent (Aml) environment to support the older adult in living a less dependent life.

These Smart homes are intentionally designed living spaces that provide interactive technologies and support systems to enable people – for example elderly persons to enjoy a high level of independence, activity participation or well-being than otherwise afforded [9], [10]. Longevity of life is often associated with high rate of vulnerability to diseases and injury [11]. Chronic diseases such as cancer, diabetes, arthritis, heart disease and chronic obstructive pulmonary disease are very common in older adults. Falls and injuries are even more common in elderly people [12]. It has been predicted that by 2035 the number of people with dementia will double [13] and by 2050 the number of full time carriers will have tripled [14]. With these current trends in population demographics, it is becoming increasingly difficult for governments worldwide to fully maintain their health and social care systems [15]. Therefore, the use of smart technologies, including smart-homes could arguably relieve the pressure on aged care health and social support services [11].

Reddy proposed the use of Bayesian networks as suitable for anomaly detection [16]; While Smolyakov et al, developed and implemented an automatic anomaly detection algorithm for meteorological time-series [17]; and Giannoni et al, proposed four different approaches for detecting anomaly, namely: Running Average Low-High Pass Filter, Univariate Gaussian Predictor, Seasonal ESD (Extreme Studentized Deviate) Algorithm and Local Density Cluster-based Outlier Factor (LDCOF). He discovered that LDCOF which is based on k-means clustering is best for multiple features or a multivariate dataset. They proved that K-means Clustering machine learning technique is best for creating a solution implemented using multiple features or a multivariate dataset [18]. However, since this paper is limited to the application of supervised machine learning technique; naïve bayes, k-nearest neighbour which is the supervised variant of the unsupervised k-means clustering algorithm was used.

Research in anomaly detection has presented a lot of solutions to effectively detect anomaly which can be behavioural, spatial and temporal for both categorical and continuous datasets. It has also been proven by recent researches that implementing solutions with individual machine learning technique for dataset inhibits the expected results [19]. Hence, ensemble learning techniques which allow for the implementation of two or more machine learning technique per time in creating a solution [17] is highly encouraged and recommended. This is because the shortcomings of either technique can be complimented by the corresponding

technique. For example, in this paper the ensemble learning technique approach was used to build the model. This ensemble experts learning techniques used was Naïve Bayes algorithm and k-nearest neighbour algorithm which is the supervised variant of k-means clustering learning techniques.

3. Research Method

Data Collection

The data used in the study is secondary data collected from an online repository which consist data set of sensor events collated from the Washington State University, Centre for Advanced Studies in Adaptive Systems (WSU CASAS), Tulin smart apartment test bed from April to July of 2009 [8]. The apartment houses two married residents, though record of only one occupant is made public. The original data had ten generic activities of both repetitive and non-repetitive activity of daily living annotated by start time and end time of each routine activity occurrence having four attributes.

Data preparation and feature extraction

The data collected is contained in a text file and needed to be prepared by uploading it through the xlminer platform via the import text wizard. The xlminer converted the data from text file format into numeric and arranged in rows and columns. This resulted to 486,912 rows with 6 columns of data set. The dataset was then sorted and features were extracted into daily living activities with its corresponding start time, end time for each activity, the state, which is either the 'begin' or 'end' state per day. The duration (mins) of each activity was the focus of this study. This was derived as the difference between the start time of an activity and the end time of the activity.

The extraction of non-repetitive generic activity of daily living from the data set was carried out. This is made up of four (4) activities out of the ten the activities. The extracted activities also include the corresponding start time and end time of those activities. These activities include: cook_breakfast, cook_lunch, leave_home and enter_home. Five (5) attributes were used in this study. Two (2) of these attributes were derived from the initial data. the attributes include:

1. Approximate Duration: which was derived from the difference between the Start_Time and End_Time of the individual activity in Minutes?

2. State: derived from the approximate duration based on the following condition:
duration (minutes) < 1 = False, OR duration (minutes) > 1 = True

The other regular attributes include:

1. Days
2. Start time
3. Adl (activities of daily living)

Modeling and simulation

In building and simulating the ensemble model for detecting temporal anomaly, Rapidminer, a predictive analysis tool was used. In using this tool, the example set made up 180 examples i.e. the rows, which were gotten from a 60day period of three different activities with one special attribute called the label and four regular attributes. This data set was added to the rapidminer repository via an operator named 'Add data' in a process environment. The data built was carried out via operators in a process. The first operator was the 'retrieve' operator, which is responsible for calling out data sets already saved in the rapidminer repository. The 'retrieve' operator has an 'out' port, it uses to connect to other operators via their ports or the 'res' port in the process environment. In building the ensemble model for this paper, the 'out' port of the retrieve operator was connected to the 'tra' port of the vote operator which is an operator capable of implementing the more than one machine learning algorithm per time. The 'tra' port is simply what gives access to the data set for training while the 'mod' port on the right side of the vote operator, is the port responsible for the output of the model implementation. The 'mod' port is then connected to the 'res' port of the process environment. After this connection is set and ready, the run button is clicked on and the model is built. It is important to note that the vote operator is a sub process, and its at the sub process level naïve bayes algorithm and k-nearest algorithm are implemented via their operator calls as shown in the figure 1 below.

Figure 1: Design View of the Simulated Ensemble Model

4. Implementation

In implementing the model simulation, the operator called model simulator is called via its operator. This is done by dragging and dropping the operator in the process window. The model operator as shown in figure 2, has five ports; with three on the left side called 'mod', 'tra' and 'tes' respectively. The 'mod' port is connected to the 'mod' port of the vote operator; while the 'tra' port known as training is connected to the retrieve operator to feed in the training data already stored in the repository while the 'tes' port known for testing is being connected to the another retrieve operator for feeding in the test data also stored.

The model simulator has two ports on its right side namely: 'sim' i.e. simulation and 'mod' i.e. model ports. However, since we are more concerned about the simulation at

this point, only the 'sim' port is connected to the 'res' port of the process environment as shown below.

Figure 2: Process View of the Ensemble Model Simulator

5. Result and Performance Evaluation

The result of the model built from figure 1 and simulated in figure 2 as shown above is shown in figure 3 below' shows that the model's prediction is true with the confidence for this decision at 50% with the duration (mins) as the main attribute for this conclusion. However, 95% of predictions done by this model are correct and when the model says true, it covers 100% of the cases and its correct with 83.33% of all predictions for class true.

Figure 3: Result of the Ensemble Model Simulator

Performance evaluation was carried out on certain criteria, after building the model. This was to determine the level of efficiency of the models created and if they reflect the aim of the study. The results of these performance findings are shown in Table 1.

Table 1 Performance Evaluation between Naïve Bayes, K-Nearest Neighbour and Ensemble Learning Technique

S.NO.	Performance Criteria	Naïve Bayes Algorithm	K-Nearest Neighbour Algorithm	Ensemble Learning Algorithm
1.	Accuracy	98.33%	71.67%	95.00%
2.	Classification Error	1.67%	28.33%	5.00%
3.	Root_Mean_Squared_Error (RMSE)	0.129 +/- 0.000	0.515 +/- 0.000	0.274 +/- 0.000
4.	Squared Error	0.017 +/- 0.128	0.266 +/- 0.428	0.075 +/- 0.115

The results from the comparison table above have shown that the accuracy performance criteria for the models was 98.33%, 71.6% and 95% for Naïve Bayes Algorithm, K-Nearest Neighbour Algorithm and Ensemble Algorithm respectively. It can be observed that, the accuracy for ensemble learning appears lower than that of Naïve Bayes

Algorithm, this is because the `root_mean_squared_error` (RMSE) which is the standard deviation of the predicted errors was recorded at 0.274 ± 0.000 for ensemble technique and 0.129 ± 0.000 for Naïve Bayes with squared error, which is the average of the squares of the errors; at 0.075 ± 0.115 for ensemble technique and 0.017 ± 0.128 for Naïve Bayes as shown in figure 4, 5 and 6 respectively. These errors which are inversely proportional to the rate of accuracy are the reason why the ensemble techniques accuracy is subtly lower than that of Naïve Bayes Algorithm.

Figure 4 Description of Naïve Bayes Model Performance Evaluation

Figure 5 Description of the K-Nearest Neighbour Model Performance Evaluation

Figure 6 Description of the Ensemble Model Performance Evaluation

It also principally shows that ensemble learning is of a higher advantage to individual learning algorithm as k-nearest neighbour with an accuracy of 71.6% when ensembled with naïve Bayes had its accuracy rise to 95.00%.

6. Conclusions

In conclusion, the results shown by Ensemble learning technique is advantageous over individual algorithms as the strength of the stronger algorithm augments the weakness of the other. For example, the strength of naïve bayes which is the stronger algorithm in the study with capacity of handling missing value within a dataset is seen and agrees with Reddy [16] where Bayesian networks model was used for anomaly detection and proved the model's suitability being that its average rate leads to increase in prediction accuracy, however, in this work Bayesian was used in combination with k-nearest neighbour as an ensemble learning technique, which improved k-nearest neighbour by increasing the model accuracy from 71.67% singly to a 95.00% as an ensemble learner.

The study result also agreed with Analytics Vidya,[20] that Naïve Bayes algorithm is best when dealing with multivariate dataset and dataset with missing values as it individually outperformed the ensemble learner with an accuracy of 98.33% against 95.00%. This result differed with smolyakov [17] conclusion of ensemble learning technique outperforming individual techniques, however, the reason for the variance may be as a result of disparity in the type of data used, as real time nominal data which consist of missing values, was used in this study while artificially generated continuous data which is usually complete was used by Smolyakov [17]. The study simply confirmed the possibility of exceptions with ensemble learning techniques underperforming than individual algorithm in the use case of nominal values with missing dataset.

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GRAPH-BASED VISUALIZED MODEL: AN IDEAL ALTERNATIVE FOR TEMPORAL ANOMALY DETECTION IN OLD PEOPLE'S HOME

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Abstract

The need to have a secure lifestyle for older persons at home is in demand more than ever. One of the major concerns for smart home systems is the capability of adapting to the user as personalizing the behaviour of the home may provide improved comfort, control, and safety. The main aim of this work is to simulate a graph-based visualized model for temporal anomaly detection in smart homes which can be applicable in building occupant specific smart homes. To achieve this goal, dataset of activities of daily living from a smart environment covering a period of 60 days was used. The data covered in this 60day period consist of three non-repetitive daily routine activities, with specifics to the *start_time* and duration was used for building the trend / pattern of which a deviation from this trend implies an anomaly. The result of the study revealed that line plot and scatter plot graph can be used to create a graph-based models for temporal anomaly detection in old people's home. This is a visualized system with the advantages of flexibility, speed and lack of need for label attribute.

Keywords: Graph-based visualized model, temporal anomaly detection, Old people's home, smart environments, Smart home system

1. Introduction

The need for graph-based model has become important in different areas of detecting patterns and anomalies. However, no much work has been in this area [1]. Studying and mimicking human behaviour is a great asset for computer systems. It provides knowledge of human behaviour and the impact on their overall wellbeing. Hence, computerized systems focusing on human behaviour require adequate information from humans. The need for the development of computerized systems like smart homes, health monitoring and energy efficiency is dependent on the cost of health services, sustainability and age of the population [2].

This birthed the evolution of wireless, modest and affordable sensors for information collation in daily 'smart' surroundings. This information so collected when studied using machine learning techniques, do not only give discernment that can be inter-leavened in our

lives but can also produce computerized domain specific support to daily living environments, for example a smart home [3].

In reality, embedded sensors in the smart home produces data as occupant's carryout everyday routines. The data is usually gathered via a computer network which acts as a bridge and is housed in a database that the informant uses to produce insight-like trends and make prediction which is conveyed via the network to physical devices that executes a trigger, for a corresponding action or human intervention [4].

In addition to the identification of normal activities that make up for the majority of sensor events produced, occupants of smart homes are also interested in anomalies which may reflect a crisis associated with health challenges, security monitoring where suspicious activities are flagged. Hence, anomaly detection is most assured when based on behaviours that are predictable and regular [5].

Smart Technologies and Homes can be taken a step further by analyzing the daily routine activities of its occupants and comparing such over time. A behavioural pattern can thus be established and deviations from this established pattern(s) considered an abnormal behaviour [6].

This paper aims at simulating a graph-based model for temporal anomaly detection in smart homes which can be applicable in building occupant specific smart homes. To achieve this goal, dataset of activities of daily living from a smart environment covering a period of 60 days was used. The data covered in this 60day period consist of three non-repetitive daily routine activities, with specifics to the start_time and duration was used for building the trend / pattern of which a deviation from this trend implies an anomaly precisely the first part of the occupant's day before leaving home. This trend / pattern created is based on the start_time and duration of each of this activity and collectively becomes the model/template for normalcy of which a deviation from this trend implies an anomaly.

2. Related work

Steiger et al, proposed a visualization system for interactive pattern analysis in univariate sensor networks particularly anomaly detection with focus on the analysis of similar patterns over different temporal scales. The methods used were best practices in the information visualization domain which cover the daily, weekly and seasonal patterns of data with the daily collections being analyzed in a clustering-based view [7].

Paudel, proposed that a graph-based approach can successfully discover patterns and anomalies in resident activities. Activity graphs were constructed from smart home daily activities to detect normative patterns as well as spatial and behavioural anomalies [8].

Eberle and Holder proposed a graph-based approach in uncovering anomalies in domains where anomalies consist of unexpected entity/relationship deviations that resemble non-anomalous behaviour using synthetic and real-world data [1].

Reveiro and Falkman, also agreed that visualization can contribute to the data mining process by its ability to represent results of complex computational algorithms, ability to depict the process and discover complex patterns which cannot be automatically detected, however, using the powerful human visual system, it can be detected [9].

Research in anomaly detection has proposed lots of solutions to effectively detect anomaly which can be behavioural, spatial and temporal for both categorical and continuous datasets. In this paper the trends / patterns model, I derived was used as basis for anomaly detection.

3. Methodology

The data used in this project [10], was gotten from the online repository which consist sensor events data collated from the Washington State University, Centre for Advanced Studies in Adaptive Systems (WSU CASAS) Tulin smart apartment test bed from April to July of 2009. The apartment houses two married residents, though record of only one occupant is made public in this release. The original data had ten generic activities of both repetitive and non-repetitive activity of daily living, annotated by *start_time* and *end_time* of each routine activity occurrence having four attributes.

Figure 1 Phases in the Data Handling Work Flow

The data collected from the WSU CASAS online repository, was a text file and needed to be prepared by uploading it through the xlminer platform via the import text wizard. This action have passed through the phases of data handling as shown in figure 1, that is its collection, preparation, representation was done by converting the data from text file format into rows and columns. It resulted to 486,912 rows with 6 columns. This resulting dataset in the xlminer format allowed for sorting and feature extraction and visualization for activities of daily living with its corresponding *start time*, *end time*, its state that is '*begin*' or '*end*' per day. The duration(mins) which is the core of this study, was derived by invoking the function *MINUTE*(), to convert the result of the difference between the *start* and *end* time.

4. Implementation

In the implementation that is the visualization phase, which is the last phase in the data handling work flow shown in figure 1, xlminer, the tool was used for creating the graph-based visualized model. XLMiner is a wide range tool offering various methods in investigating data with an all-inclusive machine-learning and statistical techniques for classification, prediction, affinity analysis, data exploration and reduction [11]. XLMiner is part of the Analytic integrated software for predictive and prescriptive analytics like

forecasting, data mining, optimization and simulation. This gives Excel the capacity to solve both small and big data problems and every business analyst uses Excel because it often plays a role in many analytical projects [11].

XLMiner’s data mining algorithms, now written in C++, were based on studies of the latest published papers, doctoral theses and conference proceedings in machine learning and data mining. All directed to take utmost advantage of multi-core processors and modern vector instruction sets. This resulted in a dramatic upgrade in performance (often 100 times faster or more) and capability to manage large, composite datasets. A performance benchmark of the XLMiner against software packages such as SAS JMP, IBM SPSS and Minitab was carried out to ensure that XLMiner could handle datasets as large as these well-known statistical packages, with similar or better performance.

As shown in figure 2 and figure 3, the times series and scatter plot graph were both used to implement the graph-based model. These models created, reveals the trend of the occupant’s daily first three non-repetitive routine activities of daily living for a 60 day period.

Figure 2: Simulated Time Series Model

Figure 3: Simulated Bubble Chart Model

Figure 4, 5 and 6 on the other hand gives a more detailed singular view of the normal pattern for the cook_breakfast individual activity of daily living at a weekly level. This pattern or trend shows that the normal time duration for the cook_breakfast activity as a minimum of 5 minutes and maximum of 35 minutes.

Figure 4: Simulated ADL_Cook_Breakfast Model Week 1

Figure 5: Simulated ADL_Cook_Breakfast Model Week 2

Figure 6: Simulated ADL_Cook_Breakfast Model Week 3

However, Figure 7 and 8 reveals the anomaly based on the condition of 5 minutes minimum and 35 minutes maximum for this particular activity. This is seen in days 25, 29 and 30. Day 25 has a duration less than lower limit of 5 minutes while Day 29 and 30 has duration higher than the higher limit.

Figure 7: Simulated ADL_Cook_Breakfast Model Week 4

Figure 8: Simulated ADL_Cook_Breakfast Model Week 5

5. Result

The result of the model built in figure 2 as shown in figure 3, reveals that both line plot and scatter plot graphs can be used to create graph-based models for temporal anomaly detection in old people’s home, which is a visualized system and has the advantages of flexibility, speed and lack of need for label attribute/value. This discovery is in agreement with Paudel et al, Eberle and Holder, that a graph-based approach can successfully discover patterns and anomalies in resident activities and Steiger et al, on the use of a visualization system for interactive pattern analysis.

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Upshot of Percentage Consistency and the Sum-of-Pairs Score Factor on the Algorithmic Structures of some DNA Analysis Tools

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ABSTRACT

One of the most popular quantitative measurements for multiple sequence alignment (MSA) is the Sum-of-Pair score, or simply sum-of-pair (SP). Sum-of-pairs scoring of multiple alignments is a potentially biased scoring measure. If the input sequences are not independent but instead over-sample some groups compared to others, the higher number of pairwise alignments to an over-sampled group can dominate the alignment score. This greater contribution of an over-sampled group to the score will tend to drive the multiple alignments toward improving the pairwise alignments to such groups at the price of worsening the pairwise alignments to under-sampled groups, thus degrading the overall quality of the alignment.

Keywords:

Sum-of-pairs score, Percentage Consistency, Algorithmic approaches, DNA sequencing tools, Jalveiw, Sequencing methods,

1.1 Introduction

Biologist-friendly software tools are crucial in this age of burgeoning sequence databases. These tools not only make it possible to use computational and statistical methods, but also allow scientists to select methods and algorithms best suited to understand the function, structure, evolution, and adaptation of genes and species, (Butler, 2012), . The flood of data acquired from the increasing number of publicly available databases has led to new demands for bio-informatics software. With the growing amount of information resulting from high throughput experiments, new questions arise that often focus on the comparison of genes, genomes, and their expression profiles. Inferring new knowledge by combining different kinds of post-genomics data obviously necessitates the development of new approaches that allow the integration of variable data sources into a flexible framework, (Catherine et al., 2011).

In the context of an explosion of new data management challenges, the field of bio-informatics is rapidly becoming the most critical step in realizing the full potential of genomics and proteomics. Population geneticists, ecologists, epidemiologists, and clinical researchers, have routinely used statistical and computational models to evaluate information they have collected. However, new breeds of life scientists are applying new analytical techniques to new types of data, (Clamp *et al.*, 2004).

Many data mining, annotation, and visualization systems have been developed over the last couple of years, each with their advantages and limitations. Additionally,

several stand-alone tools have been introduced, which rely on object-oriented programming languages, e.g. Strainer: Software for analysis of population variation in community genomic datasets or MetaLook: 3D visualization software for marine ecological genomics. They have been designed to facilitate the exploration and analysis of highly specific datasets. Moreover, they are user-friendly and offer simple installation procedures. A shift from process to object oriented programming languages is a current trend in biologist-centric software development. The rise of bioinformatics to its current prominence has paralleled the growth of the Human Genome Project, thereby paving ways for more DNA sequence software with diversity in content.

1.2 Statement of the problem

The genome sequencing revolution is approaching a landmark figure of 1500 completely sequenced genomes. Coupled with fast-declining, per-base sequencing costs, this influx of DNA sequence data has encouraged laboratory scientists to engage large data sets in comparative sequence analyses for making evolutionary, functional and transitional inferences. Sum-of-pairs scoring of multiple alignments is a potentially biased scoring measure. If the input sequences are not independent but instead over-sample some groups compared to others, the higher number of pairwise alignments to an over-sampled group can dominate the alignment score. This greater contribution of an over-sampled group to the score will tend to drive the multiple alignments toward improving the pairwise alignments to such groups at the price of worsening the pairwise alignments to under-sampled groups, thus degrading the overall quality of the alignment. Again, creating a direct perturbation to the percentage consistency of the entire process. Therefore, there is need to x-ray the effect of sum-of-pairs scoring on the percentage consistency and the alignment result.

1.3 Aim and objectives of the study

This is aim at analyzing the diversity in content and algorithm structure of DNA sequence data software(s), and recommends a more standardized set of modules and algorithm for different quest with respect to accuracy, time of execution and robustness of the system.

To achieve this aim, the following objectives were set for use.

1. To establish the possible upshot of the Percentage consistency and the Sum-of-pair factors on the alignment tools.

1.4 Motivation and Significance of the studying

The application of analytical software in live science, specifically in DNA and protein sequences data analytical has expose users and researches to a dilemma of extensive review of such software in order to ascertain and consider which of the software that is most suitable for the application and why. The reasons for the particular interest in molecular biology are, first, that it is a growing and important area of scientific study, and second, the lengths of biological sequences are such that the need for efficient methods of sequence analysis is becoming acute

2.0 Review of related works

2.1 Genetic analysis software

The Molecular Evolutionary Genetics Analysis (MEGA)

The Molecular Evolutionary Genetics Analysis (MEGA) software is a desktop application designed for comparative analysis of homologous gene sequences either from multi-gene families or from different species with a special emphasis on inferring evolutionary relationships and patterns of DNA and protein evolution. In addition to the tools for statistical analysis of data, MEGA provides many convenient facilities for the assembly of sequence data sets from files or web-based repositories, and it includes tools for visual presentation of the results obtained in the form of interactive phylogenetic trees and evolutionary distance matrices, (Davulur and Zhang, 2003).

The MEGA software project grew out of the need for employing statistical methods in the phylogenetic analysis of DNA and protein sequences in the early 1990s. At this time, most computer programs available did not allow us to explore their primary data visually and lacked a user-friendly interface. There were two primary general-purpose computer programs for inferring phylogenetic trees. One was PAUP for constructing parsimony trees, and the other was PHYLIP for inferring phylogenetic trees using various character and statistical methods such as maximum likelihood, parsimony, and distance methods, (Kriventseva, 2001).

GenAIEx (Genetic Analysis in Excel)

GenAIEx was originally developed as a teaching tool to facilitate teaching population genetic analysis at the graduate level (Markowitz et al, 2007). GenAIEx operates within Microsoft Excel and widely used spread sheet software that forms part of the cross platform Microsoft Office suite. Packaging genetic analysis within a familiar and flexible environment resulted in quick understanding and effective performance of population genetic analyses. Taking advantage of the rich graphical options available within Excel, GenAIEx offers a wide range of graphical outputs that aid genetic data analysis and interpretation. GenAIEx is now widely used by university teachers at both undergraduate and graduate levels around the world. Moreover, the software has also attracted a large number of researchers who utilize its unique features.

GenAIEx offers population genetic analysis of diploid dominant, haploid, haplotypic and binary genetic data from animals, plants and microorganisms. It accommodates a wide range of genetic markers, including microsatellites SQL server reporting servers (SSRs), single-nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs), amplified fragment length polymorphisms and DNA sequences. Both allele frequency-based and distance based analysis options are provided. The former includes estimates of heterozygosity and genetic diversity, F-statistics, Nei's genetic distance, population assignment and relatedness. The latter includes Analysis of Molecular Variance (ANOVA), Principal Coordinates Analysis (PCoA), Mantel tests, TwoGener, multivariate and 2D spatial autocorrelation, (Panchenko and Bryant, 2002).

GenAIEx maintains backward compatibility, but it provides access to the expanded spread sheet of Excel 2007 onward. Thus, the maximum numbers of loci and samples are vastly expanded and only constrained by memory. More than 30 different Excel graphs summarize the outcomes of genetic analyses. Graphics can be further

manipulated with Excel options and easily converted to pdf or other publication quality formats.

2.2 DNA sequencing methods

Dynamic programming method

Dynamic programming is a method that determines optimal alignment by matching two sequences for all possible pairs of characters between the two sequences. It is fundamentally similar to the dot matrix method in that it also creates a two-dimensional alignment grid. However, it finds alignment in a more quantitative way by converting a dot matrix into a scoring matrix to account for matches and mismatches between sequences. By searching for the set of highest scores in this matrix, the best alignment can be accurately obtained.

Dynamic programming works by first constructing a two-dimensional matrix whose axes are the two sequences to be compared. The residue matching is according to a particular scoring matrix. The scores are calculated one row at a time. This starts with the first row of one sequence, which is used to scan through the entire length of the other sequence, followed by scanning of the second row. The matching scores are calculated. The scanning of the second row takes into account the scores already obtained in the first round. The best score is put into the bottom right corner of an intermediate matrix, dynamic programming for local alignment. In regular sequence alignment, the divergence level between the two sequences to be aligned is not easily known. The sequence lengths of the two sequences may also be unequal. In such cases, identification of regional sequence similarity may be of greater significance than finding a match that includes all residues. The first application of dynamic programming in local alignment is the Smith–Waterman algorithm. In this algorithm, positive scores are assigned for matching residues and zeros for mismatches. No negative scores are used. A similar tracing-back procedure is used in dynamic programming. However, the alignment path may begin and end internally along the main diagonal. It starts with the highest scoring position and proceeds diagonally up to the left until reaching a cell with a zero.

Maximum Likelihood (ML)

Another character-based approach is ML, which uses probabilistic models to choose a best tree that has the highest probability or likelihood of reproducing the observed data. It finds a tree that most likely reflects the actual evolutionary process. ML is an exhaustive method that searches every possible tree topology and considers every position in an alignment, not just informative sites. (Ogban et al 2019) By employing a particular substitution model that has probability values of residue substitutions, ML calculates the total likelihood of ancestral sequences evolving to internal nodes and eventually to existing sequences. It sometimes also incorporates parameters that account for rate variations across sites.

ML works by calculating the probability of a given evolutionary path for a particular extant sequence. The probability values are determined by a substitution model (either for nucleotides or amino acids), (Thompson, 2006).

For other substitution models, the formulas are much more complex and are not described here. For a particular site, the probability of a tree path is the product of the probability from the root to all the tips, including every intermediate branch in the tree topology. Because multiplication often results in very small values, it is

computationally more convenient to express all probability values as natural log likelihood values, which also converts multiplication into summation.

Neighbor-joining (NJ)

The Unweight Pair Group Method (UPGMA) method uses unweight distances and assume that all taxa have constant evolutionary rates. Since this molecular clock assumption is often not met in biological sequences, to build a more accurate phylogenetic trees, the neighbor joining (NJ) method can be used, which is somewhat similar to UPGMA in that it builds a tree by using stepwise reduced distance matrices. However, the NJ method does not assume the taxa to be equidistant from the root. It corrects for unequal evolutionary rates between sequences by using a conversion step, (Waterhouse *et al.*, 2009).

Maximum parsimony

The parsimony method chooses a tree that has the fewest evolutionary changes or shortest overall branch lengths. It is based on a principle related to a medieval philosophy called Occam's razor. The theory was formulated by William of Occam in the thirteenth century and states that the simplest explanation is probably the correct one. This is because the simplest explanation requires the fewest assumptions and the fewest leaps of logic. In dealing with problems that may have an infinite number of possible solutions, choosing the simplest model may help to "shave off" those variables that are not really necessary to explain the phenomenon. By doing this, model development may become easier, and there may be less chance of introducing inconsistencies, ambiguities, and redundancies, hence, the name Occam's razor. For phylogenetic analysis, parsimony seems a good assumption. By this principle, a tree with the least number of substitutions is probably the best to explain the differences among the taxa under study. This view is justified by the fact that evolutionary changes are relatively rare within a reasonably short time frame. This implies that a tree with minimal changes is likely to be a good estimate of the true tree. By minimizing the changes, the method minimizes the phylogenetic noise owing to homoplasy and independent evolution, (Zhang *et al.*, 2002).

3.1 Methodology

The DNA sequence analysis application reference was built using the agile software development method. The agile software development methodology is focused around a short iterative software release cycle. This design is geared toward heavily involving the stakeholders and constantly showing them demonstrations of the current state of the software. This allows for the stakeholders to make recommendations and suggest changes while the software is being actively developed so that the software can track what the customers actually desire. Agile also helps software projects improve the expectations of when software will be completed, determine what items can feasibly go into a release cycle, and provide the ability to easily track overall project progress.

Netbeans Integrated Development Environment (IDE) was used for the implementation of the software. Netbeans IDE (version is 3.6) is an open source Java development tool (current Java version is 1.4.2). The System Analysis and Alignment (SAAS) application was designed and developed to run on all windows operating system. Since the application (which includes graphical display and sequence analysis algorithms implementation) is written using Java programming language (version

1.4.2), it can be run on any computer platforms which has a Java Virtual Machine (JVM) installed.

The system architecture of the application has a link to the GeneBank database to get all the possible DNA sample data; figure 1. Again, a set of DNA sequence analysis algorithms, and a Java GUI based DNA analysis tool for results display and sequences manipulation facilities.

Figure 1: SAAS Architecture

However, due to the confidentiality and sensitivity nature of the data (i.e. involving human DNA), a high security clearance from the relevant authorities is required in order to have access to the real data, which makes it difficult to acquire real data for the system. Therefore, in this work test data, a combination of self-generation data supplemented by data obtained from the Internet Genome Databases will be used.

Materials and methods

Materials

Eleven (11) multiple sequence alignment tools were installed on a HP EliteBook Folio9470m computer running with windows 10 operating system and each program was tested using default parameters. The choice of the 11 multiple sequence alignment tools were dependent on the sequence to be aligned. In the research work, a comparative study of the 11 most used MSA tools based on it algorithmic approach, namely: ClustalW, MEGA , T-Coffee, Muscle, Mafft, ProbCons, Kalign, MSAProbs, GLProbs, Clustal Omega and MSProbs was done.

Methods

First, sequences with different class labels will be combined to generate each benchmark dataset. Then, the alignment analyses will be performed using 11 multiple sequence alignment (MSA) and 1(one) Pair-wise Sequence Alignment (PSA) methods

and the aligned sequence matrices with gaps inserted will be generated as outputs. Based on this, evaluation calculation was performed by cluster validity calculation using Sum-of Pairs (SW) and Silhouette Width (RS scores), based on distances calculation results. Significance analyses will be performed on biological and statistical levels to determine whether the performance differences between algorithms produces essential discriminations on application scope and then after result will be discussion. Finally application development will follow.

Online Data Linking

We choose the globin genes of 11 species, which are widely used for evaluating the performance of sequence similarity analysis methods. This data was obtained from genebank (Table 1).

For each dataset, we combined DNA sequences of different protein families into one file. All the protein families and sequences were included in the analyses except for the sequences that belonged to more than one protein families since they would cause the confusion of the following steps. Each protein sequence was considered as a sample and the family it belonged to was considered as the sample's class label. The original family labels of the sequences are considered as the ground truth of the clustering results.

Table 1: Globin genes of 11 species *Source: Genebank*

S/N	SPECIES	ACCESSION NUMBER	LOCATION	LENGTH(nt)
1	Bovine	[GenBank:X00376]	278-1741	1464
2	Chimpanzee	[GenBank:X02345]	4189-5532	1344
3	Gallus	[GenBank:V00409]	465-1810	1346
4	Goat	[GenBank:M15387]	279-1749	1471
5	Gorilla	[GenBank:X61109]	4538-5881	1344
6	Human	[GenBank:U01317]	62187-63610	1424
7	Lemur	[GenBank:M15734]	154-1595	1442
8	Mouse	[GenBank:V00722]	275-1462	1188
9	Opossum	[GenBank:J03643]	467-2488	2022
10	Rabbit	[GenBank:V00882]	277-1419	1143
11	Rat	[GenBank:X06701]	310-1505	1196

MSA methods evaluated and Benchmarks

To evaluate different alignment tools effectively, there is need to have some benchmark sequences and “gold standard” reference alignments of those sequences. For assessing the performance of different automated alignment tools, it is required to find a quantitative accuracy relative to gold standard reference alignments. Popular benchmark databases of hand-curated reference alignments include BALiBASE and HOMSTRAD. A number of modern alignment databases rely on automated structural alignment protocols, including SABmark PREFAB, OxBench , and BALiBASE version 3. Among them, the most widely applied database is BALiBASE that contains a C-language application, called bali-score, which measure the *SP* (Sum of Pairs) and the *TC* (Total Column) score of test alignment in comparison to the reference alignment will be used in this research work

The 11 MSA tools were selected based on two parameters: (1) the underlying algorithms and (2) their popularity. Table 2 describes the MSA tools with their versions, main algorithms, and URL for download. All these MSA methods were run using default parameters.

TABLE 2: Multiple sequence alignment program use comparatively in this research

S/N	MSA METHOD	VERSION	MAIN ALGORITHM	AVAILABILITY
1	T-Coffee	3.27	Consistency (multi-core usage capable)	http://www.tcoffee.org/
2	ProbCons	1.1	Consistency	http://probcons.stanford.edu/download.html
3	Kalign	1.04	Progressive (Wu-Manber)	http://msa.sbc.su.se/cgi-bin/msa.cgi
4	MEGA 7.0	7.0	Consistency	
5	GLprobs	1.2	Progressive	https://sourceforge.net/projects/glprobs/files/latest/download
6	MSAprobs	1.4	Progressive	http://MSAprobs.cbrc.jp/alignment/software/
7	Clustal W	1.8	Hidden Markov Model	http://www.clustal.org/omega/
8	MUSCLE	3.6	Iterative	http://www.drive5.com/MUSCLE/downloads.htm
9	MAFFT	5.732	Iterative	http://mafft.cbrc.jp/alignment/software/
10	Clustal Omega	1.2.2	Progressive	Source code .tar.gz (1.2.4)
11	MSprobs	2.4	Progressive	http://MSprobs.cbrc.jp/alignment/software/

4.0 System Implementation and Results

The programming language use in implementing a system is typically chosen based on the features offered by the language that makes it suitable to solve the problem at hand. The important factor to consider during the chosen of a programming language include the target operating environment in which the system will be deployed and used and the ease of maintaining the system development afforded by the language. The implementation of this tool was done using the PHP ((hypertext processor) programming language.

TABLE 3: MSA Result Comparison Analysis Table.

S/N	MSA TOOLS	% consistency	sum of pairs scores	column scores(no gaps)	column scores(with gaps)	min #seq for cs
1	T-Coffee	64.55	0.9	0.567	0.567	6
2	ProbCons	46.55	0.912	0.423	0.423	6
3	Kalign	45.55	0.917	0.422	0.422	6
4	MEGA 7.0	45.55	0.942	0.573	0.573	6
5	GLprobs	56.706	0.938	0.562	0.554	6
6	MSAprobs	56.706	0.934	0.565	0.545	6
7	Clustal W	43.805	0.915	0.409	0.409	6
8	MUSCLE	45.675	0.916	0.42	0.419	6
9	MAFFT	44.118	0.914	0.407	0.406	6
10	ClustalOmega	43.63	0.915	0.409	0.409	6
11	MSprobs	56.706	0.934	0.565	0.545	6

Sum of pair’s scores

One of the most popular quantitative measurement for multiple sequence alignment (MSA) is the Sum-of-Pair score, or simply sum-of-pair (SP), figure 2. Sum-of-pairs scoring of multiple alignments is a potentially biased scoring measure. If the input sequences are not independent but instead over-sample some groups compared to others, the higher number of pairwise alignments to an over-sampled group can dominate the alignment score.

Figure 2: Chart showing the enlarged Percentage Consistency compared to the other factors.

This greater contribution of an over-sampled group to the score will tend to drive the multiple alignments toward improving the pairwise alignments to such groups at the price of worsening the pairwise alignments to under-sampled groups, Figure 3 thus degrading the overall quality of the alignment. Mega and Clustal W outperform other multiple sequence alignment tools.

FIG. 3: Bar Chart showing the sum of pair scores compare to other multiple sequence alignment tools.

5.1 Summary

Choosing the most suitable program to a dataset alignment is difficult. SAAS will help young and inexperienced bioinformatics to choose the right tools for sequence alignment analysis. However, with regards to the available tools, Mega outperformed others in the control and use of Sum-of-Pairs scoring.

5.2 Conclusion

Running MSA programs with default parameters are usually preferred when no information regarding the sequences to be aligned are available and/or for users without previous knowledge in this particular field of sequence analysis. With that in mind, we chose to benchmark a selection of programs mostly with their default options. Although results presented herein are compatible with current low-cost hardware and timelines of most research projects, they must be used only as guidelines, and we encourage users to carefully study each program’s parameters in order to obtain the best possible output. The BALiBASE suite is a reliable benchmarking dataset, but still might be considered small to meet certain MSA projects. Thus, understanding each programs own limitations are imperative in order to generate reliable results.

5.3 Recommendation

It is clear that future work to improve alignment programs should concentrate on the problems of large insertions, extensions and sequence fragments. The alignment of sequences of similar length is relatively successful, even if there is only weak identity between the sequences. Another important area of interest which is becoming more and more frequent is the alignment of families of sequences. Increasing the number of sequences in an alignment set often significantly improves the alignment quality of divergent sequences.

The results of this program comparison may be used to indicate the most suitable program for a particular alignment problem. It should now be possible to predetermine the nature of a set of sequences, in particular the re-partition of sequence identities and the presence of unequal length sequences. An alignment server would then be able to automatically select the program which is likely to give the most accurate results.

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**Flood Magnitude Prediction Model using Autoregressive and Integrated Moving Average
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ABSTRACT

Disaster is imminent and humans have to learn to manage it. Flood is one of the most common natural disasters in Nigeria with adequate negative impact on people, properties and farmlands. Flooding tends to occur during heavy down pour (rainfall) when water absorption is low. The extent of flood is proportional to the negative impact that is experienced by the victims. The adverse effects of flood cannot be overemphasized. It causes loss of life, properties and economic degradation to mention but a few. These effects can be mitigated via Flood Prediction Models (FPMs). Several successful Flood Prediction Models have been developed, but there are still limitations in the prediction of the magnitude of the flood when it occurs. Flood magnitude is the degree (extent) of the flood. The aim of this study is to build an efficient time series model in forecasting flood magnitude as a natural phenomenon that occurs frequently in nature. In this study, secondary data was collected and used for model training and testing. An autoregressive integrated moving average (ARIMA) Time Series was used to develop a flood magnitude prediction model. The ARIMA model is a combination of autoregressive (AR) and Moving average (MA) models. The implementation was done using Python Spider IDE in ANACONDA for the model simulation. The model was trained, successfully tested and evaluated via coefficient of determination and standard error diagnostic tools. The ARIMA model prediction results indicate that in the year 2024 the flood magnitude will be low level, while that of 2025 will be normal. The result also shows that the year 2026 will have high levels of flood. The results show that the coefficient of AR technique produced a score of 0.0554 indicating a higher and better performance than the MA model with a score value of -0.9077. The higher the coefficient of determination value, the better and more successful the models' performance.

Keywords: Disaster, Flood, Flood Magnitude, Machine Learning, Autoregressive, Moving Average, Time Series.

1. INTRODUCTION

One essential task towards reducing the negative impact of disaster is to adequately and accurately analyze the potential risk and ascertain measures to prevent, mitigate or prepare for emergencies. Information and Communication Technology can play a vital role in highlighting risk areas, vulnerabilities and the likely populations that will be affected by producing geographically referenced analysis such as the use of geographic information system (GIS). Accurate analysis and timely information are keys in mitigating negative impacts of disaster such as flood. In Nigeria several cases of flood were reported by individuals and agencies of government in several towns and communities in 2019 and 2020. Cases of submerged communities and farmlands with negative impacts were common. The negative impact of flood on people and properties can be reduced significantly by improving the flood forecasting system and accurately predicting the extent or magnitude of the flood.

Several Flood Prediction Models (FPM) have been developed and used for this purpose. Different approaches have been applied in developing models to predict flood. These include approaches based on physical parameters (deterministic hydrological models), statistical approaches (statistical models) such as Markov method [1], Machine learning approaches such as Artificial Neural Network[2], Fussy Logic, Time Series and Support Vector Machines [3]. This study is an attempt to apply autoregressive integrated moving average (ARIMA) Time Series algorithm with Machine Learning in the prediction of flood and its magnitude.

The time series is a little bit statistical in nature but its forecasting methods are evaluated using machine learning-like type of techniques [4]. It uses test and training principles of collecting past and present data to describe and prescribe the behavior of future or unseen data with respect to time. This study's objective is to build an efficient time series model in forecasting flood magnitude as a natural phenomenon that occurs frequently in nature. The study employed the combination of autoregressive (AR) and moving average (MA) technique called the ARIMA's model in time series to predict the occurrence of flood with respect to time. The implementation was done using Python in ANACONDA for simulation.

Little or no work has been done in the area of exploring auto-regressive (AR) and moving average (MA) techniques in time series to forecast flood magnitude.

The performance of time series model depends mainly on the order of the data. There are three major classifications of data in time series namely: cross sectional, time series data and the combination of both. A full blown time series data usually contain the time component as well as

series of variables at a given instance of time. We are considering only the time series component. The time series data are multivariate data collected across a given period in a sequential manner and equally spaced time of interval. Time series is the collection of observations at a regular time interval for certain variables over a given period of time. This can be adopted to predict and forecast flood magnitude, sales data, rain fall, stock market analysis, work load projection, census analysis, process and quality control systems etc. There are three major components identified in time series; namely: trend, seasonal and irregular component by [5]. The trend is a long-term upward or down ward movement, seasonal deals with the inter year fluctuations repeatable over the entire length of time and irregular depicts the random movement of data patterns. The objective of time series is to extract information from historical data and is used to predict future behavior of the same data based on previous pattern. There are two major approaches adopted in time series forecasting namely; decomposition which extracts individual components of time series and regression which uses the concept of regression on past data.

1.2 Statement of the problem

Several countries around the globe are experiencing heavy down pour (rainfall) and over flowing river banks leading to an unexpected flood disaster. This can negatively affect some part or entire localities in our living areas and frequently occurs as a natural disaster resulting into loss of life, destruction of properties and the environment at large. It exposes a number of people to be at risk of becoming more vulnerable to flood disaster. Little or no work has been done in the area of exploring auto-regressive (AR) and moving average (MA) techniques in time series to forecast flood magnitude. The aim is to build an efficient time series model in forecasting flood magnitude as a natural phenomenon that occurs frequently in nature. We are employing the combination of autoregressive (AR) and moving average (MA) technique called the ARIMA's model in time series to predict the occurrence of flood and its magnitude with respect to time.

II REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Several flood prediction schemes have been presented in the literature. Research has also shown that due to advancement in technology, flood prediction methods have moved on from solely mathematical modeling or physical parameter based flood forecasting schemes, to methodologies focused around algorithmic approaches. Flood Prediction Models (FPM) predicts flood relying on several factors such as amount of rainfall, temperature, river water level, degree of soil permeability, degree of ground saturation etc. The variables often used in these studies are

rainfall data, river water run-offs, temperature, precipitation etc. The tools used in predicting the flood level or magnitude ranges from rainfall, temperature run-off models, hydraulic models, data driven hydrological models [6].

Reference [7] developed a model that attempted forecasting the magnitude of flood in Afikpo North East of Nigeria using Artificial Neural Network and a modified runoff equation. Temperature and rainfall data were the main variables they used; their model produced 84.7% and 95.5% level of performance in rainfall and temperature respectively. However, the result cannot be relied on owing to the size of the dataset used. The dataset used in training the model was very small; temperature and rainfall data, 2012 to 2018. Also, the temperature should have been recorded at various time intervals of each day to allow for a better performance of the model which is a time-dependent event. Reference [8] identified the presence of tangible differences in the course of estimating flood magnitude of a region. They used Annual Maximum Flood (AMF) time series to determine the trend at local and regional scale using time-dependent conditions while ensuring that the factors that lead to variations in flood in an area or region remain constant for a specified period. Monte Carlo experiments were used to evaluate the performance of the model. However, the factors that were considered in their study that brought non-stationarity may change from one country to another. Reference [9] considered a situation where the physical characteristics of drainage basins could be applied in flood frequency analysis in Scotland. They used the Normal Mixtures (NORMIX) multivariate clustering algorithm. Their method was applied to about 168 basins in Scotland and five regions were identified and produced a homogeneous result of flood frequency that corresponded to the basin types. But this method, no matter how encouraging the results are, would have lapses when implemented in a third-world country like Nigeria due to topography and other development indices.

Reference [10] looked at the prediction of rainfall-based river flood forecasting in Malaysia using Nonlinear Autoregressive Exogenous model (NARX). The use of Bayesian regularisation for training of algorithm put up a better performance when compared with Levenberg-Marquardt back propagation training technique. NARX in rainfall based flood prediction showed a 99% performance. However, this was just a prediction of 24 hours in advance. In the flood magnitude prediction system proposed in this article, the prediction is targeted at months and even years ahead.

Reference [11] developed a five-hour flooding model for Kuala Lumpur applying Neural System Autoregressive Model with Exogenous feedback (NNARX). The model was implemented using

Matlab Neural Network Toolbox. The training was done with 131 samples, validation with 84 samples, and testing vector was done with 170 sample size. The training was done with gradient descent algorithm. The model was fitted at 89.2% performance level. But, the data used was small to be used to predict flood on monthly or even on yearly basis, as such the likely reason for the poor performance seen.

Reference [12] sought to use NARX to do a five-hour in advance flood prediction model for Terengganu River. 641 data sample was used for training; another 641 data sample was used for validation while 1351 was used for testing the model. The Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) value was 0.220, and the performance level of the model recorded above 80% as the model predicted the flood occurrence in advance of five hours. But the non-linearity of the data appeared to have affected the performance of the model. Again, data scaling and the number of data samples used affected the performance.

Reference [13] used NARX NN for the prediction of the dynamic characteristics of water flood level. Same study used Extended Kalman Filter (EKF) algorithm in comparison with NARX NN. NARX outperformed EKF algorithm with RMSE of 0.06m compared with 0.67m respectively. Reference [14] sought to use NARX to do a 10-hour in advance prediction of flood with the Kelang River as a case study. Results showed that NARX design was able to do the prediction 10.833 hours before time. The performance level was quite impressive with RMSE of 0.0806m. But, as stated hitherto, this case is specific to a particular river; not a region. Again, the variables like temperature, runoffs, etc. were not put into the mix.

Reference [15] used Support Vector Machine (SVM) technique to investigate a two-year knowledge based on 2005 and 2006. A total of 7 lake floods in downtown of Chiang Mai, Thailand were used as data. The study revealed that SVM performed better than Multilayer Perceptron Models (MLP) models, and that SVM can be effective in forecasting of flooding. Also the model can be used in real-world flood prediction systems with real life available data. Reference [16] also used SVM to forecast flooding event. Bird Creek,U.S.A catchment area data was used for training; and the unseen data for testing and model implementation. Rainfall and river flow data were collected from 12 rain gauges kept in the catchment area. A comparison with other prediction algorithm was made after implementation. SVM did better than all the other algorithms in the time data series. The result showed that linear and nonlinear kernel characteristics could provide significant activities against each other for various conditions in the same catchment. Reference [17] aimed at determining better attribute selection, and discharge

level estimation using Rawal Lake, Islamabad as case study. SVM, RBF (Radial-Basis-Function), ANN (Artificial Neural Network) and ARIMA were used to predict the discharge time. The major pitfall of their model is prediction over small duration.

III. MATERIALS AND METHODS

In this paper, we are focusing on the use of autoregressive integrated moving average (ARIMA), autoregressive (AR) and moving average (MA) processes. The ARIMA's model or mixed process takes into account past and present data and decomposes it through an autoregressive (AR) process that stabilizes or makes the data stationary. The moving average (MA) processes can easily carryout forecasting with or without previous error terms [18].

Dataset: The dataset used was obtained from the kaggle online repository site [19,] containing one hundred and one (101) items with attributes of date, level and target. The proposed system dataset is divided into 80% training and 20% testing set in detecting flood levels.

Table 1: Flood dataset

	YEAR	FLOOD_LEVEL	TARGET
0	1920-12-01	3	High
1	1921-12-01	1	Low
2	1922-12-01	2	Normal
3	1923-12=01	3	High
4	1924-12-01	1	Low
---	---	---	---
96	2016-12-01	2	Normal
97	2017-12-01	2	Normal
98	2018-12-01	1	Low
99	2019-12-01	2	Normal
100	2020-12-01	8	High

The autoregressive integrated moving average model (ARIMA): The ARIMA model is a more complex technique made up of the autoregressive represented with AR (p) and moving-average with MA (q). The ARIMA (p,q) model is the linear combination of the actual past values and errors terms [5]. Where q is the order of moving average and p is the order of the autoregressive component and the general form is given as:

$$Y_i = \mu + \alpha_1 Y_{t-1} + \alpha_2 Y_{t-2} + \dots + \alpha_p Y_{t-p} + e_i - \theta_1 e_{i-1} - \dots - \theta_q e_{i-q} \tag{1}$$

$$Y_i = \sum_{k=1}^p \alpha_k Y_{t-k} - \sum_{k=1}^q \theta_k e_{t-k} + \mu + e_t \tag{2}$$

The ARIMA model has an autocorrelation that decreases as the residual distance increases

The general form of the Autoregressive integrated Moving Average (ARIMA) is given as

$$Z_t = \sum_{k=1}^p \alpha_k Z_{t-k} - \sum_{k=1}^q \theta_k Z_{t-k} + \mu + e_t \tag{3}$$

These models were simulated using the Python Spider IDE. In this environment, the “statsmodels” library was invoked and used in training the ARIMA model and created the model outcome using the steps stated below.

The AR model: The autoregressive(AR) techniques is one of the most popular known method used in time series analysis where the dependent variables depend upon values of the response variable measured in the past [20]. It represents a linear regression on itself in the context of time series analysis [21].

$$Y_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 * Y_{t-1} + Error_t \tag{4}$$

The AR model of the first order is represented with AR (1) model and the time lag is taken to be yearly. The Y_{t-1} is used to represent the value of Y of the previous flood year while $Error_t$ as the standard error term.

Moving Average (MA): Is a time series model that the target or output depends linearly on past and current data with respect to a time lag. The MA is represented with MA(q) where q is the the order and \mathcal{E} is the standard error.

$$X_t = \mu + \mathcal{E}_t + \theta_1 \mathcal{E}_{t-1} + \dots + \theta_q \mathcal{E}_{t-1} \tag{5}$$

Where μ is the mean. $\theta_1, \theta_2, + \dots + \theta_q$ are the parameters of the MA model and $\mathcal{E}_t, \mathcal{E}_{t-1}, + \dots \mathcal{E}_{t-q}$ are the error terms. The equation 5 above can be rewritten as follows:

$$X_t = \mu + (1 + \theta_1 B + \dots + \theta_q B^q) \mathcal{E}_t \tag{6}$$

Where the error value is computed using:

$$Error_t = Expected - Predicted \tag{7}$$

Algorithm 1: Moving Average(MA) Time Series Model

Step	Processes involved
1	Start
2	Invoke necessary libraries
3	Define and call the MA model
5	Pass in p and d parameters as the order of moving average and auto-regression
6	Call the fit() function to train model using the training dataset
7	Make predictions using the predict() function using testing dataset

8 Stop

Algorithm 2: Autoregressive(AR) Time Series Model

Step	Processes involved
1	Start
2	Invoke necessary libraries
3	Check for stationary
5	Determine order of AR model
6	Train model using training dataset
7	Make the predictions and evaluate predictions using testing data
8	Stop

Performance evaluation

The performance evaluation step serves as the final step used to effectively measure the success rate of MA and AR models using the rolling means and standard deviation. This study employed the coefficient of determination and standard error diagnostic tools to compare the performance of both techniques. The results are presented and discussed next.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

We discussed about the results of MA and AR models obtained from the proposed system dataset in time series. The implementation was done with some fine-tuned hyper-parameter values for better performance. The fine tuning was achieved through the seasonal graph plot and by obtaining the rolling mean and standard deviation of the input data. The essence of fine tuning the dataset is set standardize it, thus giving rise to a stable model.

Figure1: Time series plot of flood magnitude

Figure 1 shows the up and down movement or trend of flood level that changes with previous dataset. The graph is non stationary which changes with respect to time. The graph represents the datasets (inputs) used for the prediction, that is, the data fed into the model. The time series plot of flood magnitude was implemented via the code snippet below.

```

24 dataset = pd.read_excel(file2, "Sheet3")
25 dataset['YEAR']=pd.to_datetime(dataset['YEAR'], infer_datetime_1
26 print(dataset)
27 dataset = dataset.drop('TARGET',axis=1)
28 indexeddataset=dataset.set_index(['YEAR'])
29
30 print(indexeddataset)
31
32 #plot graph
33 plt.xlabel('YEAR')
34 plt.ylabel('Low Normal High')
35 plt.title('Flood Magnitude with training dataset')
36 plt.plot(indexeddataset, lw=3, marker='o', ms=10, markerfacecol
37 plt.show()
38
39 y=indexeddataset['FLOOD']
40 y.plot(figsize=(15, 6))
41 plt.show()

```


Figure 2: The rolling mean and standard deviation of flood level

Figure 2 is the rolling mean and standard deviation of flood level; it changes along with time because it's non stationary. Also; the rolling mean and the standard deviation are starting from a different year (1925) at the Year-axis because they don't have the values for the first 5 years as rolling terms (mean and standard deviation). Some data patterns appear to be seasonal, some in upward (ever increasing) and some in downward (ever decreasing) pattern; the rolling mean and standard deviation were introduced to standardize the data pattern so as to stabilize the model.

Figure 3: the seasonal decomposition graph

Figure 3 is the seasonal decomposition graph containing the original, trend and seasonal data or graph. The seasonal decomposition graph is used as a tool to make our dataset stationary. This separates the seasonal part from the trending part which then gave the last kind of graph (called residual) within the range of dataset. At the topmost part of the graph is pattern of the original data obtained, the second and third parts of the graph represents the data in its trend pattern (that is, the up and down pattern) and its seasonal (fluctuation) pattern. The last part of the graph (residual) contains the pattern of the original data after the fine tuning (separation of both seasonal and trend patterns) was completed.

Figure 4a: Histogram plus estimated density

The curve in figure 4a shows the estimated density plot of the ARIMA's model which is essentially a smooth version of the histogram. The histogram shows a wider bandwidth which resulted in more smoothing of distributed data and even though the data was limited to fall within -3 to 3 inclusively, the density plot extended it beyond these limits. The model learns from the

data distribution and the fine-tuning or change in kernel hyper parameter value changes the distribution data drawn at each data point in forming a more smoothing curve that falls within the normal distribution curve showing the relationship. The intercepts on the curve depicts a close relationship between the independent variables and the target.

Figure 4b: The Normal quantile-quantile (Q-Q) plot

Figure 4b presents the normal quantile-quantile (Q-Q) plot. The plot is a graphical plot used to compare the probability distribution of two variables by plotting sample quantiles against theoretical quantiles. There are four outliers evident at the bottom left and three at the top right of the Normal Q-Q plot. It shows that the data points are normally and linearly distributed, thus implying that the model has good precision, less error margin and good performance.

Figure 4c: The correlation graph

The correlogram in figure 4c shows the density plot which is essentially a smoothing version of the histogram and even though we limited our data plot to -2 to 3; the density plot extends beyond the limits. It is used to interpret a set of autocorrelation coefficients in which

autocorrelation function (ACF) is plotted against the time lag. We are expected to have one significant value under pure randomness in every ten lag. There are distinct spikes at lag 2 and 3; very high and equal to ACF but other values are relatively smaller in the correlogram. This also means that the model performance is within an acceptable range.

Figure 5: The prediction graph of flood level

Figure 5 is the graph showing the past and present data in predicting the future behavior of flood level (magnitude) with respect to time. The model was fed with previous data patterns to predict from the year 2022 to 2045 as shown in figure 5. The model predicted flood level of year 2022 as normal, year 2023-high, 2024-low, 2025-normal, 2026-high etc. The code snippet below was used for the actual prediction.

```

81  pred_uc = results.get_forecast(steps=30)
82  pred_ci = pred_uc.conf_int()
83  ax = y.plot(label='observed', figsize=(14, 7), lw=3)
84  pred_uc.predicted_mean.plot(ax=ax, label='Forecast', lw=4)
85  ax.fill_between(pred_ci.index,
86                 pred_ci.iloc[:, 0],
87                 pred_ci.iloc[:, 1], color='k', alpha=.25)
88
89  ax.set_xlabel('YEAR', fontsize=17)
90  ax.set_ylabel('Flood Magnitude Prediction', fontsize=17)
91  plt.legend()
92  plt.show()
93

```

Model Evaluation

Table I: Diagnostic Summary of the Proposed Model

coef	Std err	Z	P> Z	[0.025	0.975]
------	---------	---	------	--------	--------

ar.L1	0.0554	0.170	0.325	0.745	-0.279	0.389
ma.L1	-0.9077	0.065	-14.039	0.00	-1.034	-.0781

Table I shows the attributes of dependent and predictor variables (ar.L1, and ma.L1) with their error margin. The model Coefficient of determination is the value used in predicting the target from the independent variable. The coefficient of AR technique produced 0.0554 which is higher and performed better than the MA model that gave value as -0.9077. The higher the coefficient of determination value the better and more successful the models' performance. The standard error value of MA model gave 0.065 and AR produced 0.170 which was used to determine the significance of different parameters at lag one (L1) within the interval of 0.025 and 0.975. The MA model produced lesser error value in prediction compared to the AR model.

IV. CONCLUSION

Flood magnitude prediction model can drastically reduce the adverse effects associated with flood disaster. This will help the concerned organizations to make decisions and plan ahead as a mitigation measure. The residents within flood prone areas can be alerted on time so as to evacuate their properties on time.

ARIMA time series method of flood magnitude prediction has not been fully utilized. The developed model can serve as benchmark to other researchers since the model is scalable; little modifications can be made to predict other natural disasters such as drought by varying the determinant parameter(s). The result depicts that the model performed well, has small error margin and high degree of precision.

The use of Python in the simulation made the task less tedious. This is because Python have inbuilt libraries, functions and tools that we utilized both for simulation, prediction and diagnostic summary of the model performance. All these were achieved with few lines of codes, thus code optimization was utilized at its best.

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Issues in Machine Translation of Indian Languages for Information Retrieval

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Abstract— Natural languages differ from one geographical location to the other. In India, there are 22 official languages [1]. Many documents have been digitized as a result of the advancement of information technology. Machine Translation Systems (MTS), as well as information retrieval systems, are required in order to retrieve any information from an existing digital document in any natural language. This paper describes some of the most important domains in information retrieval where Machine Translation (MT) is essential, such as Cross-Lingual Information Retrieval (CLIR) and Multi-Lingual Information Retrieval (MLIR).

Keywords-Machine Translation; CLIR; MLIR; MTS

I. INTRODUCTION

The automatic translation of text from one language to another is referred to as Machine Translation [3]. Machine Translation System (MTS) is an application of artificial intelligence in Natural Language Processing (NLP). The language of the input text is referred to as the source language, while the language of the output text is referred to as the target language. These days MTS is an arising area of study for scientists in India. India is multilingual country. Indian government utilizes Hindi or English language as a correspondence medium while different states of India utilize their local language as a correspondence medium [4]. There is a major interest for record transformation starting with one language into the other language. The English language is generally utilized in all fields. So MTSs are required for interpretation of local language to English language or vice-versa.

The act of storing, finding, and retrieving information from a database that fits a user's request is known as Information Retrieval (IR) [5]. Since non English material (Hindi, Gujarati, etc.) is rapidly expanding, the digital world is no longer monolingual. The capacity to obtain information in different languages is becoming important in an increasingly globalized economy. In the digital age, the multiplicity of languages is becoming a barrier to understanding and familiarity. As a result, IR has become a critical field of study in recent years. It has been discovered that when users receive

services in their native language, they are more likely to accept and use them.

One of the most significant challenges in CLIR and MLIR is identifying relevant material for a query issued in the user's native language. As the World Wide Web expands, so does the amount of material available in languages other than English on the internet. In recent years, there has been a tremendous rise in the availability of non-English content on the internet. All important government institutions, newspapers, and publishing firms created websites in Hindi or Gujarati or any native language [6]. National boundaries are becoming less important in terms of commerce and information sharing as a result of globalization. Hindi is the world's third most commonly spoken language. Gujarati is also the most frequently spoken language in Gujarat. India is diverse in terms of languages, and just 12% of the population is familiar with the English language [7]. IR in languages such as Hindi, Gujarati, English etc. is gaining popularity. Google now supports transliteration in 14 languages namely Arabic, Bengali, Farsi (Persian), Greek, Gujarati, Hindi, Kannada, Malayalam, Marathi, Nepali, Punjabi, Tamil, Telugu and Urdu [8]. Society gains the benefit of allowing users to access information in their native language and retrieve information in the same language without knowing which language the information is stored in the database through the MLIR process, making it a very effective research area. The IR system may help people in various areas, including agriculture, rural health, education, national resource planning, crisis management, information kiosks, and others.

In terms of IR development a lot of work is being done. Other relevant fields of research are also being pursued, such as NLP, MT, and so on. For IR, scholars have considered a variety of regional languages. Government organizations such as TDIL (Technology Development for Indian Languages) have also made major contributions to the standardization of Indian languages on the web [9].

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Extra information is available online in the form of text, audio, video, and other media. This source will provide users with important information. IR is the act of obtaining essential documents or information from the content of a data

collection such as the World Wide Web [10]. A web search engine is an IR system that searches the World Wide Web for information. IR involves a number of components such as:

Crawl: Download and save documents from the Internet.

Index: Searched documents are indexed.

Query: It is the user's input.

Rank: The system creates a list of documents that are rated based on their relevance to the query.

The availability of information on the internet is expanding in a variety of formats and languages. Though English used to dominate the web, it currently accounts for fewer than half of all documents on the internet. Because of the popularity and the availability of online information sources, there will be a greater demand for CLIR systems. CLIR is the search for documents written in a language other than the language used to clearly explain a query. This allows users to browse a collection of documents in a variety of languages to obtain valuable information in a usable format, even when the target language has little or no linguistic ability. CLIR is critical in countries like India, where a substantial proportion of the population does not speak English and so does not have access to the huge store of knowledge available on the Internet.

There are various areas where MT systems can be coupled with IR systems:

A. Books:

The books can be identified in order to accommodate to the representation of various domains. The key goal in picking a book is to select from a wide range of domains so that the corpus may cover a substantial portion of the vocabulary and not lose out on domain-specific words.

B. Magazines:

Magazine corpus often comprises a variety of texts such as cuisine, health, movies, fiction, current news, and so on.

C. Newspaper:

The newspaper corpus is made out of current text. Political news, editorials, sports news, and so on may be included in the text. The news articles include a wide range of topics, including religious views, scientific principles, and other concepts that must be communicated to the general public. As a result, it is assumed that the authors would have captured these domains in a clear and understandable manner. Such articles make good use of terminology, have a clear linguistic structure, and use effective phraseology. To entice readers, newspaper stories may employ colloquial, non-standard words or jargons. The words chosen must be descriptive and reflect the author's feelings and attitude toward the occurrences.

Following are the categorization of the contents that a common man may be interested in:

A. Science and Technology:

The science and technology domain comprises text extracts from numerous scientific publications, magazine articles, journal articles, and so on. These are also known as knowledge texts. The linguistic structure and word use differ from everyday language. The subject of the text is generally worldwide, therefore terminology of this domain will include the most borrowed terms.

B. Social Sciences:

Since language is a tool for the development and preservation of human society, language in the social sciences category correlates the linguistic aspects of the dynamic society. Human development and reformation are occurring in many community contexts, therefore all social knowledge and reality may be portrayed in this literature genre.

C. Official Document

The language used in official documents is highly standardized, clear, straightforward, and structurally changed. Official documents are designed to communicate about some activity, inquiry, or proceedings of some assembly.

Following are the subdomains recognized under Official Document, see Figure 1.

Figure 1: Subcategories of Official Documents

D. Aesthetics:

This category includes subdomains from Literature and Fine Arts. The text samples are taken from literary works. It is used to record literary phrases. Aesthetics content is compiled from several works. The text is most likely a typical description text of some kind. It exemplifies the linguistic style of the time period from which the work is drawn. It is a snippet from a piece of creative writing. It consists of fictional stories, essays on various themes, and so on. These articles are primarily the writer's personal expressions. It captures the writer's flow of words in the literary work.

The subdomains recognized under Aesthetics are given in Figure 2

Figure 2: Subcategories of Aesthetics

E. Commerce:

The commerce is an important component of society. It exists and functions in collaboration with a variety of societal groups, including customers, suppliers, rivals, banks and financial institutions, government agencies, and labor unions.

The subdomains recognized under Commerce are shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Subcategories of Commerce

F. Mass Media

For many individuals all around the globe, media is an essential part of their daily lives, both at work and at home. The text of this domain is a current character. Political news, editorials, or sports news may be included in the text. The newspaper is the primary source of the Mass Media text category. It contains terms that are often used in everyday life. Exposition, argument, description, and narrative are all

structural elements of mass media language. It comprises many forms of writings. It consists of structures with various patterns, vocabulary, and styles. Everything is written in a language that everyone can connect to and comprehend. Some of the media prints take the shape of a dialogue or a series of questions and replies. This data often include an interviewer and an interviewee. They are generally conversations. The interviewee might be a celebrity or a well-known figure from the world of films, politics, or other fields. The words used in this type of literature are typically more personal and straightforward.

The subdomains recognized under Mass Media are depicted in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Subcategories of Mass Media

III. CHALLENGES IN DEVELOPING CROSS-LINGUAL INFORMATION RETRIEVAL

Following are the challenges in developing a CLIR system:

1. Conflict in translation: More than one translation may be available when translating from source to target language. It is difficult to choose a suitable translation. For example, the word હાર (haar) has two connotations; defeat and necklace.
2. Phrase recognition and translation: It is difficult to recognize phrases in a limited context and translate them as a whole unit rather than as separate words.
3. Transliterate/translate a word: There are several confusing names that must be transliterated rather than translated. For example, મૌલિક (Maulik) in Gujarati refers to a person's name as well as Original. It is difficult to detect these situations solely on the given context.

4. Transliteration errors:

Errors in transliteration may result in the erroneous term being returned in the target language.

5. Dictionary coverage

When translating with a bi-lingual dictionary, dictionary completeness is an important criterion for measuring system performance.

6. Font:

Many web documents do not use the Unicode character set. Before they can be processed and stored, these documents must be converted to Unicode format.

7. An analysis of morphology (differs for each language)

8. Words that are not in the vocabulary

New terms are added into the language that the system may or may not recognize.

IV. CONCLUSION

Many domains where MT may be utilized for IR are described in this paper. Cross-lingual and multi-lingual IR introduce new paradigms for finding texts in many languages throughout the world, and this may serve as the foundation for searching not just between two languages but also across several languages. For many years, MT has been a thriving research sector in artificial intelligence and IR systems. Since natural languages are very complex, MT is a difficult task. As languages are evolutionary in nature, it is impossible to assume that one technique would be sufficient to handle the translation process. A few of the difficulties encountered in CLIR have also been highlighted.

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PSCCTEM Ontology to overcome pesticide paradox in Model Based Testing

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Abstract—This research proposed ontologies to retain information and knowledge for overcoming pesticide paradox in model based testing. Domain ontology was constructed, which described the vocabularies related to a software engineering domain. The ontology retained the structure of a Polymorphism State Collaboration Class Test Model (PSCCTEM) by defining the test model's structural elements and the relationships between them. In this research, the rules for transforming UML PSCCTEM test model into behavioral model ontology, proposed based on the Ontology Definition Metamodel (ODM). The proposed solution argued that developing a new testing phase that help the user to regenerate the test steps easily according to system modifications that will overcome pesticide paradox.

Keywords

Ontologies; pesticide paradox; software engineering; Ontology Definition Metamodel (ODM).

i. Introduction

Software testing is an attempt to execute a program with well-designed input data to discover failures. In other words, "Testing is the process of drying out a program with the intent of uncovering errors". Testing identifies faults, whose removal enhancing the software quality by increasing the software's reliability [1]. Basically, the testing procedure consists of three phases: (i) Test Case Creation, (ii) Test Case Execution and (iii) Test Case Evaluation. Test case creation process represents a vital phase among the three phases [2]. Singh (2013) stated seven principles of testing which must be regarded while testing a product. The last principle is the pesticide paradox states that, if similar set of test cases are used repeatedly then chances of forecasting defects can be reduced. Therefore, users have to update and check their test cases on continual basis [3]. In model-based testing, test cases are derived from a model representing software behavior. In this approach, the System under Test (SUT) is converted into System Test Graph (STG); the graph is traversed to generate test cases automatically based on coverage criteria and a fault model [4]. The literature review shows that (1) the existing approaches on model-based testing using UML Diagrams tend to rely on intermediate formats and formalisms for model verification and test generation. (2) A multitude of graph-based coverage criteria, and use graph search algorithms employed. (3) Most approaches target very restricted application domains, and (4) there is currently a clear lack of holistic approaches for model-based testing using UML diagrams. Most of the well-known model based testing techniques for test case generation encounter pesticide paradox. To overcome such limitations, new approaches and solutions need to be proposed. This research presents the testing procedure that can be enhanced by

developing a new ontology testing phase to retain software testing model. This may help the user to regenerate the steps easily to improve the reusability and modifiability of testing methods, and suite to overcome pesticide paradox. The rest of this paper organized as follows: Section 2 provides a brief background on the model based testing and also highlights related work. Section 3 presents the proposed test model that capture complete picture of the system. Section 4 presents the transformation rules used to build the ontology. Section 5 presents case study. Finally, Section 6 concludes the paper and outlines future work.

ii. BACKGROUND AND RELATED WORK

A considerable amount of work targets the generation of test inputs, the selection of test scenarios, and the generation of test oracles from formal models and specification. Arvinder Kaur et al (2018) presented an approach to generate test cases automatically from collaboration diagrams and validation of results using mutation testing. The approach proposed an algorithm for generation of graphs from collaboration diagrams ensuring full path coverage. The results generated after traversal of graph covered all the valid, invalid and terminated paths but still restricts the path selection to minimal and avoid duplicate or unbounded path selection [5]. WeifengXu et al (2016) Proposed an integration testing approach based on the core concept of contracts (i.e., preconditions and postconditions of components calls in first-order logic) to exercise component interactions. They converted the test model into operational model for correctness analysis and generation of coverage-based tests (including state coverage, transition or component coverage, and reachability coverage) of a contract-based test model. They executed their approach in framework that generates the test cases for large collection of programming languages. To measure the effectiveness of their approach, they executed experiments to check the performance and fault detection capabilities of tests [6]. In [7], Yi Sun et al (2017) proposed an approach for integration test cases generation based on collaboration diagram and logic contracts to automatically generate integration test cases. The researchers tried to overcome the shortcoming exist in [6] by extracting control flow information from collaboration diagram and combining with contracts as component specification. An intermediate model called execution tree of components is established, and then test cases are automatically generated through contract solving technology. Muhammad Nouman Zafar et al (2021) proposed GraphWalker model based test framework to generate test scripts for embedded software controlling. The GraphWalker

defines mapping rules for converting abstract test cases to executable test cases [8]. Qiu Zhipeng et al (2021) proposed formal requirement model (VRM) to generate test cases by exploring the input and output structure of the model [9].

Few researches have studied in the direction of developing ontologies to improve software testing phase. Josip Bozic et al (2021) proposed ontologies based web testing approach that combines knowledge about common attacks and the system under test. The proposed approach depends on transforms ontologies into input models and using a combinatorial testing algorithm for deducing the test cases [11]. Anjalika and et al (2017) introduced test case extraction based on ontology reasoning. For this goal, requirement ontology is first constructed to store requirement knowledge; test cases are derived from requirement based on action, object and actor. Actions related to objects and actors that are responsible for actions are traversed to extract data properties [12]. Likewise, Valeh H. Nasser and et al (2010) proposed an approach for unit test case generation from knowledge base artifact in the form of ontologies. The test oracle considered is a UML state machine, also called a state-chart, which is a design-level abstraction of a unit's behavior. The proposed approach enables generation of required test cases based on the pre-defined coverage criteria [13]. Although, the new exist testing methods are applicable to generate test cases from a formal model and specification, the literature review shows that research is lacking in overcoming pesticide paradox. No specific study focused on developing dynamic test case generation approach based on ontology to capture complete picture of the system.

iii. The proposed Framework of Test Model

The proposed test model uses usecase diagram, collaboration diagram, class diagram, and statechart diagrams to test classes' interactions for a specific use case of all possible object states. Figure (1) shows the framework of the general procedure to create the test model. Before the test model construction, it is assumed that all UML diagrams are consistent. In previous work, the augmentation of collaboration diagram with objects states to develop the SCCTEM (State Collaboration Class Test Model) was already done that can be used to uncover state-dependent interaction faults, e.g., inconsistent states of classes involved in a collaboration diagram, wrong calling state of a class in a collaboration diagram, and wrong initial state of a class in a collaboration diagram [14]. After the SCCTEM has been generated, this research proposes calling of class diagram of the system to capture inheritance relations and polymorphic methods for complete and coherent description of the system. Polymorphic classes are extracted from class diagram according to the objects involved in collaboration graph. The extracted polymorphic information is added into SCCTEM to create the UML based Polymorphism State Collaboration Class Test Model (PSCCTEM).

iv. Transformation of UML PSCCTEM Test Model into Behavioral Model Ontology

A domain ontology will be constructed, which Describes the vocabulary related to an applied domain (for example, information systems or medicine), by means of the specialization of the introduced concepts of high-level ontologies [15]. The ontology retains the structure of a PSCCTEM test model by defining the test model's constructs and the relationships between them. Behavioral model ontology for PSCCTEM test model is built and saved in RDF/XML file format to extract test cases according to defined coverage criteria. The conceptual modeling of the UML test model is likely to reflect the complete picture of the system. Thus, the ontology structure (concepts and properties) can be defined and

Fig .1. Framework for Proposed Test Model Generation.

Contrariwise, the ontology instantiation will vary depending on requirement descriptions. In this section, the rules for transforming UML PSCCTEM test model into behavioral model ontology proposed based on the Ontology Definition Metamodel (ODM), adopted by the OMG [16]. The notion for mapping between UML and OWL must be formalized. The proposed notation shown as follows:

- In the UML, the class is represented as $U(C)$, the attribute is represented as $U(A)$, and the relation is represented as $U(R)$.
- In OWL the class is represented as $O(C)$, data type property is represented as $O(A)$, and object property between classes is represented as $O(E1OE2)$.

In the following section, the proposed conversion rules are introduced in details.

a. Transformation of Root Component

Root component in the PSCCTEM test model is null node for starting the interaction. The concept of class exists in both UML and OWL2. In UML, The class structures the same properties, methods, and relationships for a set of objects. Class properties set the structure of the class and methods of the class determine the behavior of the instances of the class. In OWL2, Class in is an empty structure or has multiple individuals and do not manipulate operations on those individuals [16]. So, the transformation rule for Root component in UML to Root component in OWL ontology as follows:

PSCCTEM Rule 1: the Root component in PSCCTEM test model is null vertex for starting the interaction. In Behavioral Model Ontology (BMO), it is transformed into empty Root class respectively for starting the interaction.

b. Transformation of Class Component

PSCCTEM Rule 2: each PSCCTEM class $U(C)$ is transformed into class $O(C)$ respectively in Behavioral Model Ontology based on OWL2, set Disjoint Classes properties for each class if they are not generalization.

c. Transformation of Abstract Class Component

The abstract Class component represents the class which has the inheritance relationship and polymorphic methods. for example, the "Payment" class is a parent class of the "Credit Card" and "PayPal" classes, so that the "Credit Card" and "PayPal" classes inherit "check Out()" methods from the "Payment" class. In UML, this is known as generalization relationship between the base class "Payment" and the sub classes "Credit Card" and "PayPal". The

generalization indicates to the existence of the child classes that inherit from the base class. In UML and OWL, generalization and specialization concepts are defined. In OWL, The existence of inheritance leads to the transforming of a base class into associated with child class component with corresponding constraint. The base generalization transformation rule from UML into OWL as follow:

PSCCTEM Rule 3: In PSCCTEM test model, the generalization and association between the U(C) and the subclass U(C_i), do the following: Add the abstract class O(A_C) and class O(C_i) which is child class of class O(C).

d. Transformation of the Class Attributes

In UML, The Properties of the class must be unparalleled in the context of the class. Attributes are defined to capture real world, and to be accessible from other classes. In the PSCCTEM test model, the attributes are used to describe the content of each class within the test path. The class- name identifies the name of the class. The message attributes show the message name and number. The state shows every state within the class. The State _Transition shows every state transition which is triggered by the received message. In OWL, the retrieval access does not supported in the data type properties. So, the transformation rule of attributes in UML into Behavioral Model ontology depends on the type of the attribute. The attribute of primitive data type is transformed into a data type property in the OWL ontology. The attribute of the type class is transformed into an object property

o *Transformation of the Message Details*

The attributes of the interaction between classes as the number, operation (iteration or condition), and name of the message need to be stored as a simple attributes in the message association class that enables to retrieve them for building test paths. In the following, the transformation rule for mapping message attributes from UML based test model to model behavior Ontology:-

PSCCTEM Rule 4.1: In PSCCTEM test model that Considering the Message details as simple attributes, for each simple Attribute in test model class, Transformation of attribute U(att M)of class U(C)that the data type is primitive data type , create a data type property by respectively associating with its domain and range the URI of the class corresponding to the attribute and the XSD type corresponding to the type of the attribute in the UML test model diagram.

o *Transformation of the State and State Transition Attributes*

Each test path may go through the modal class, the non- modal class or the abstract class. Each state transition path of the modal class is from a source state to a destination state of state transition when it receives a particular message. The captured states and state transitions of the model classes in PSCCTEM test model will need transformation rules for mapping them into OWL Ontology. This research proposes to treat states and state transitions of each model class as separate classes and connect them with the base model class through "Object Property" axiom. The research did this assumption because each model class may have one or more state and not all classes are model classes. Also, these states are not the attributes of the classes (methods of model classes). So, they will be stored in separate classes and access them through associations. The transformation rule for the states and state transitions of the model class in PSCCTEM test model show in the following:

PSCCTEM Rule 4.2: In PSCCTEM test model ontology that considering the state and state transition of the model class as class and make Association between model class and state, state transition class through object property with domain is O (M_C), range is O (State).

e. Transformation of the Relation Between Classes

The test case starts with dummy node and builds by the ascending order of the entire messages in the UML PSCCTEM model. The total number of test paths is decided by the number of state

transition paths of the modal class and the number of Childs classes of abstract classes. In this section, the transformation rules for mapping interactions among objects in the PSCCTEM test model into behavior ontology model is described. In previous sections, the message details are transformed in OWL Ontology as attributes of the message Association class using data type property. But, the sender and receiver of the message must be retained in the ontology to be able to retrieve the message expression for building test paths. Message links in PSCCTEM test model is type of class association relation. In UML, the association can be one-directional or uni-directional. In OWL, association between classes can be transformed into an object property. For uni-directional association, each direction is converted into object property. Then, the transformation rule for mapping class association links from UML based test model to OWL Ontology as follow:-

PSCCTEM Rule 5: In PSCCTEM test model that Considering the Message link as association class with attributes, the transformation rules for association class M₀ between classes O₁ and O₂ is formally transformed to:

- An OWL class (named message association class) with message association class instance for each message, and two pairs of inverse object properties for every class connected to the association class.
- Chains of Object properties between classes connected to the message association class, the semantics of the classes and properties of this ontology are described in Table 1 and Table 2.

Table I.Semantics of PSCCTEM Ontology Classes.

Class	Description
Root Class	A PSCCTEM class to initialize the interaction.
Sender Class	Base class contains classes that send messages
Receiver Class	Base class contains classes that receive messages
Model Class	A model class is class that has states
Non model class	Non model class is a class that don't have states
Abstract class	The Abstract Class represents the class which has the inheritance relationship and polymorphic methods.
State class	State class represents states of the model class.
Transition class	A Transition class represents state transitions of the model class.

Table II.Semantics of properties of PSCCTEM ontology

Property	Domain	Range	Description
Send Message	Sender Class	Message Association Class	It is a collection that contains the sent messages of the PSCCTEM.
Receive Message	Message Association Class	Receiver Class	It is a collection that contains the received messages of the PSCCTEM.
Has States	Model class	State class of model class	It is a collection that contains the states of the model class.
Has Transitions	Model class	Transition class of	It is a collection that contains the transitions of the

		model class	model class.
From	Transition	State	It is a state, which is the source of the transition.
To	Transition	State	It is a state, which is the destination of the transition.

o PSCCTEM Test Model Generation

As shown in figure (3), PSCCTEM Test model for medical online shopping portal is generated based on system scenario. A medical online shopping portal allows their customers to register to their portal. The customer uses the system to find medical equipment (ex. a defibrillators, Anesthesia Machines, Patient Monitors, Sterilizers, Surgical Tables or Blanket and Fluid Warmers). He can login to the system anytime to search for the items. The customer can edit the final cart then submit the final cart for check out and make a payment. The site's administrator can update different items in the system; manage the registration of new customer. After payment a receipt will be sent to customer in hard or soft copy. The shipment data will be entered to deliver the order. The SCCTEM of the Medical Online Shopping Portal is generated from collaboration graph and statechart diagrams. Then, inheritance information of the corresponding classes in the SCCTEM model is extracted from class diagram to be used in creating PSCCTEM test model. In this step the SCCTEM is augmented with inheritance and polymorphic information captured from class diagram. The rectangle of the compound dotted line represents the polymorphic relationship in the class diagram.

v. Case Study

It is not accurate to apply the approach to one system to validate it. So, two case studies are implemented for approach validation. In this section evaluation of the approach is demonstrated as follow: - First : Is building test model for the system.

Second: Is building behavioral model ontology for the system.

a. PSCCTEM Ontology Generation for Medical Online Shopping Portal

Fig .3. PSCCTEM Diagram for medical Online shopping Portal.

o Behavioral Model Ontology for Medical Online Shopping Portal

Ontology is developed using web interface of Protégé. Medical PSCCTEM Ontology can be defined as classes, subclasses; Relationship between classes implemented using data and object properties as depicted in Figure (4).

Fig.4. Object Properties, Data Properties.

To validate the semantic consistency of the generated ontology, graphical representation of the medical portal ontology obtained using the plugin OntoGraf protégé to show the hierarchy of the test model. As shown in figure(4), there is object property called send message, the domain of the property is sender class, and the range of the property is message association class. Another object property is receive message, the domain of the property is message association class and the range is receiver class. Also, there is object property with name has state between receiver class and state class, the domain of the property is receiver class, and the range is state class. Finally, there are two object properties with name from and to between state class and state transition class to represent the source and destination states of state transition. Also, in the figure there is individual of message association class called update product message with two object properties; send message and receive message. The domain of the send message object property is the instance of the portal'sAdmin class as sender class and the range of the receive message is the

Based on a set of transformation rules for mapping between UML test model and OWL ontology, Behavioral model ontology for PSCOTEM test model is generated and saved in RDF/XML file format. According to PSCCTEM ontology for library management system graphical representation of the ontology is extracted, as depicted in Figure (7).

Fig .5. Graphical Representation of Medical Online Shopping Portal Ontology.

Fig .7. Graphical Representation of Library Management System Ontology.

Based on the graphical representation of the ontologies, the generated ontologies completely represent the constructs of PSCCTEM test model, without any error. Therefore, it is dependable to generate test cases to overcome pesticide paradox. A dynamic approach can be developed to generate test cases to overcome pesticide paradox.

vi. CONCLUSION

In this research, a new approach to overcome pesticide paradox in model based testing is presented. This study focused on developing dynamic test case generation based on ontology building. The PSCCTEM ontology is developed using Web Ontology Language (OWL) to map system specifications into OWL specification. The conceptual modeling of the UML test model is likely to reflect the complete picture of the system. Thus, the ontology structure (concepts and properties) can be defined and fixed by human study of the domain knowledge of UML models. Contrariwise, the ontology instantiation will vary depending on requirement descriptions. A limitation of mapping approach is that it does not implement algorithm to manipulate RDF/XML file to generate test cases. The future research will be focused on developing tool that captures the constructs of PSCCTEM test model and generate a set of algorithms to generate test suite.

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b. PSCCTEM Ontology Generation for Library Management System

o PSCCTEM Test Model Generation

Library management project maintains all tasks of library system such as add books stock, issue book data, return book data, student registration and also maintain data of penalty for not returned books in time. PSCCTEM Test model for library management system is generated, as shown in figure (6).

Fig .6. PSCCTEM Diagram for Library Management System.

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A Comparative Study of Various Simulation Tools for Cognitive Radio Networks

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Abstract

In the recent years with the wireless world facing a scarcity of radio spectrum, Cognitive Radio Networks (CRNs) have emerged as a very fascinating technology. The requirement for bandwidth and speed is increasing very fast with developing technology day by day. So, this problem has to be overcome in a more intelligent way whereby using the unused spectrum of the licensed users by the unlicensed users. A CRN can be simulated using various tools such as MATLAB, ns2, ns3, GNU Radio etc. In this paper we presented a comprehensive study of the above mentioned tools in CRN.

Keywords: CRN, primary user, secondary user, ns2, ns3, GNU Radio, MATLAB.

I. Introduction

The Cognitive Radio (CR) learns from its environment and changes its operating parameters accordingly. The radio spectrum is categorized into three categories namely White, Grey and Black spaces. Black spaces are part of the licensed spectrum which is used by the primary users or high power signals. Grey spaces are temporarily occupied by low power signals. White spaces are purely unutilized part of the licensed radio spectrum [1].

Cognitive Radio has the potential to utilize these Grey and White available spectrum spaces and utilize the unused or inefficiently used spectrum in a more intelligent way thus reducing the problem of spectrum shortage. The sensing, sharing, management and mobility of spectrum are the different parts of a cognitive radio network [2]. Here, the secondary users which are the unlicensed spectrum users try to occupy the spectrum left unused by the primary users which are

the licensed users. In *Spectrum Sensing*, CR searches for the spectrum holes or white spaces. The selection of the best available frequency band or channel is termed as *Spectrum Management*. When the secondary user shares the unused spectrum either utilizing any of the methods i.e. underlay, overlay and interweave, it is known as *Spectrum Sharing*. *Spectrum Mobility* is defined as the property of the cognitive radio to leave the occupied radio spectrum whenever any primary user tries to reschedule its activity. The figure 1 shows a simple model of Cognitive Radio Network.

Figure 1 A simple model of CRN

A CRN has three main system models on which primary and secondary user activity depends upon. These are: Underlay, Overlay and Interweave models.

Underlay system: In this secondary and primary user transmits simultaneously by maintaining interference at primary receiver by secondary users below certain threshold level [3] [4]. Here, the interference problem can be solved by using multiple antennas by which

secondary user transmission could be guided away from primary receiver. Also, we can use wide bandwidth on which secondary transmitter could be spread while dispreading signals at secondary receiver.

Overlay system: In these systems interference is reduced and sometimes completely cancelled as the primary users assist the secondary user for simultaneous transmission by using portion of their transmitting power.

Interweaver system: This system works on the primary idea of CR. They sense the unused spectrum opportunistically, utilize it for communication and leave the spectrum when primary user is detected. Thus avoids the considerable interference.

The secondary user does not affect the transmission of primary user, it may use either of the models of acquiring the primary channel i.e., underlay model, overlay model or interweaver model. For this the secondary user first recognizes the spectrum availability on the spatial, temporal or frequency domains, which means the absence of primary user. For this some of the communication-based regulations are also to be followed by the secondary user.

Today, computer-based simulation tools are more widespread in place of real platform based experimental analysis as these simulation tools are more cost effective and available as open-source software that can be easily installed on our computers. These Tools are updated with wireless communication libraries from time to time by different working groups as technology evolves. These simulators can be modeled for large scale simulations (scalable) where this is a major disadvantage when working on experiment based platforms. Results can be obtained with varying various parameters according to the need and radio environment. The paper provides an overview of the currently available CRN simulators.

Section II explains the cognitive radio transceiver architecture. Section III comprises of various simulation tools and their comparative analysis.

II. Cognitive Radio Architecture

The figure 2 shows the architecture of a cognitive radio where the complete system comprises of a front end radio (Transmit and Receive unit with the Analog to Digital conversion), baseband processing, and data processing unit (Interface between the front end and the user).

Figure 2 Architecture of a CRN

The cognitive radio network architecture is of three types mainly Infrastructure based, Ad-Hoc architecture and Mesh architecture. The transmission activities of the primary and secondary users is controlled and coordinated by the cognitive radio base stations in an infrastructure based networks. In Ad-Hoc networks the communication is one by adopting point to point connections using different communication protocols. The third one is heterogeneous network making a combination of the other two types. Therefore, a CR transceiver with the above defined architecture and network model should be able to sense and select the best available channel allocation strategy for communication between the secondary and primary users so that the interference levels are minimum.

III. Simulation Tools

There are a large variety of open source/licensed network simulators available e.g., ns2, ns3, MATLAB, GNU Radio etc. The network simulator used must be efficient in terms of total memory that is occupied by them during the simulation of any network, the time which is utilized for computing the required parameters

of the defined network time and how much the processor is utilized during the complete simulation.

When it comes to selection of any of the simulation software tools for research we must see that it is easy to use. It should be flexible for model development, modification and validation. It should be easier to install and configure the simulation software. Signal processing and data analysis should be done easily. Classification of network simulator is done according to the complexity of design, GUI support, scalability, analysis of traffic between various network nodes, network parameters such as throughput, delay, channel utilization etc [5].

Network Simulator 2 (ns2)

It is designed as an open-source simulator. Ns2 is used as a discrete event network simulator. ns2 is designed using C++ and it provides the simulation interface through OTcl which is the object-oriented language of Tcl. Network topology is described by writing OTcl scripts. The ns2 program code simulates that topology with some specified parameters. Network Animator (NAM) is a GUI for graphical view of network [6]. The basic functionalities of ns2 include the design of routing protocols, performance analysis of different networks, study of network traffic and designing of physical as well as network layer architectures.

While using ns2 these days, other specific packages for CRN have also been developed, such as Cognitive Radio Cognitive Networks (CRCN), CogNS and CRAHNs. All these packages have to be integrated with the ns2 protocol stack.

But overall, we can say that ns2 is a complex system containing large number of functional modules, which need recompilation each time if there is an update or addition in the system structure. As it is designed with languages C++ and Tcl, it becomes difficult to understand. Lastly, it has an overhead of large execution time.

Network Simulator 3 (ns3)

It is a new development and is again an open source discrete event network simulator. Its core language is C++ and Python. ns2 is not extended to ns3 but basically ns3 is a replacement of ns2. ns3 does not have an OTcl API [7] [8]. Its latest version supports parallel

simulation. Simulation as well as Emulation both can be performed in ns3 using sockets, where emulation mode integration with real networks is allowed. Some tools like Wireshark may be used to read the trace files and analyze network traffic. It has realistic environment and its source code is also well organized. ns2 and ns3 have many similarities in terms of framework, protocol stack, simulation support and application library. But it can be more advantageous than ns2 due to its more scalable and modular nature.

Table 1 shows the basic comparison between ns2 and ns3 on the basis of some features.

Table 1 Comparison between ns2 and ns3 Simulators

Features	ns2	ns3
Performance	Simulation time is more to make a link between C++ & OTcl	Less due to removal of overheads
Packet Representation	Complex	Simple
Memory Management	Memory required to store packets is not freed until the simulation is terminated	Better in ns3 as the system doesn't store the unneeded parameters and the packets do not contain the unused reserved header space
GUI	NAM the Animation system provides the visual representation of the network	PyViz is Python based real time visualization package
Robustness	Two language system makes debugging more complex	Single language system makes it more robust in long term
Contribution	Large amount of contributed code by users and design groups	Limited number of contributed codes

GNU Radio

It is a free and open source software development toolkit that provides signal processing blocks to implement software radio e.g. modulators, filters, amplifiers etc. GNU Radio applications are written using Python

programming language [9]. The signal processing part is implemented in C++. Simplified Wrapper and Interface Generator (SWIG) is used as the interface compiler which allows the integration between C++ and Python language. GNU Radio is modular and flexible. GNU Radio applications are built using Flowgraphs and Blocks. Blocks are the nodes of the Flowgraph [10] [11] [12]. The data flows through the edges. The signal processing part of the Flowgraph is done within the blocks. GRC (GNU Radio Companion) is the graphical user interface of GNU Radio. It allows us to build the Flowgraphs.

The signal processing blocks of GNU Radio are linked together for simulating some radio configurations. Universal Software Radio Peripheral (USRP) is the link between the radio and the real environment [13]. USRP consists of Analog-Digital Converter and Digital-Analog Converter, to convert some parameters from analog to digital domain and vice-versa.

GNU Radio is a user-friendly tool for the beginners. Here, by modifying the top level design or developing and implementing new functional blocks, and customizing the connections various research operations can be performed. This increases its flexibility and makes it more comprehensive to use for cognitive radio networks. GNU Radio has an ever growing popularity due to its good community support and real time environment support through the use of Software Defined Radio (SDR) and USRP [14]. A generic GNU Radio loop like as given in figure 3.

Figure 3 GNU Radio Components

MATLAB/-Simulink

This tool has the most widespread use in academics and research due to its powerful mathematical toolboxes. Matrix Laboratory known as MATLAB has the inbuilt blocks for signal processing. MATLAB is software that can be used to perform analysis and solve variety of mathematical and engineering problems. Programming in MATLAB is easy and very user friendly as it has extensively developed function library. Also, the graphics part is very well developed.

Simulink is an integrated part of MATLAB. System models are developed in the form of block diagrams and can be simulated and analyzed.

We can compare both the tools on basis of different features [17] [18] [19] [20] as given in Table 2:

Table 2 Comparison of MATLAB & GNU Radio

Features	MATLAB	GNU Radio
Real-time vs. Off-line	Generally, Matlab code is simulated for offline analysis, may be used with Universal Software Radio Peripheral	Often used for real-time analysis
Graphical vs. Non-Graphical flow graph	Need Simulink for graphical mode to work. In Simulink flow graphs all links are in black color.	(GRC) is the native graphical tool for GNU Radio. In GRC flowgraphs various data types are represented with different color.
Native language vs. Compiled language	Real-time analysis of MATLAB code is first translated into C-code and then compiled, with the help of tools like MATLAB Coder or Simulink Coder.	Python coding is used to build the flow graphs, which does not want compilation before execution for real-time analysis. All GNU Radio features are fully supported.
USRP support	Doesn't support legacy USRP	Driver support better on USRP

MATLAB has a wide range of Toolboxes. We can build a software defined and cognitive radio in MATLAB/-Simulink to analyze or study the different spectrum sensing, management and sharing techniques [15] [16].

IV. Conclusion

GNU Radio with GRC as a tool is a good option if we have an USRP support and good skills in Python, C++ and signal processing applications. Also if we are working in Spectrum sensing from physical layer point of view GNU Radio is a good option. As it already has an implemented example for Spectrum Sensing. Otherwise MATLAB is good for communication environment. ns2 and ns3 are open-source simulators but have installation issues and require patches and updating from the repositories.

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Intrusion Detection System based on Machine Learning : A Review

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Abstract—Internet of Things (IoT) is a new model for integrating physical and virtual objects to connect in concept as anything anywhere and anytime to transmit information via a global network. It is interoperability and heterogenous of many devices that lead to the vulnerability of the IoT network that allows attackers to attack and disrupt the network. Therefore, additional security tools on IoT network in this paper we proposed a common survey the Intrusion Detection System concept and analyzed Intrusion Detection System (IDS) based on Machine Learning could fulfill this purpose.

Keywords—Intrusion Detection System, Machine Learning, Internet of Things, Literature Review

I. INTRODUCTION

Currently, Internet of Things (IoT) is a new paradigm that is applied in many applications domain on smart concept such as smart manufacturing/industrial, smart transportation /mobility, smart grid/energy, smart retail, smart agriculture, and smart building/home. They are provided the facility of daily living of people led to the number of devices that connected the internet are being more and the vulnerability for attack on cyber is also increasing. The number of devices that are expected to be connected to internet from the Gartner by 2025 is 75.44 billion [1] and the size of the internet of thing (IoT) security market worldwide from 2016 to 2025, 7.28 to 30.9 billion U.S. dollars[2]. So, the security issues are concerned in the IoT system. The basic security requirements have 6 keys important consist of confidentiality, availability, integrity, non-repudiation, authentication, and privacy [3-8].

The attack is a big problem in the IoT system which two types include passive attacks and active attacks [9-10]. The attack method on the network layer consist of denial of service[11], hello flooding [12], eavesdropping/sniffing[12], man-in-the-middle[13], routing[14], selective forwarding [14], sinkhole[12], spoofing [12], sybil[13], malicious code [8], and traffic analysis[11]. Some of the attack dimension divided to 4 categories consists of denials of service (DoS), probing, remote to local (R2L) and user to root (U2R)

However, currently has a various methods for detecting and preventing the network from the attacker. One of the popular method for detecting and preventing the network from the attacker which addition the high level security is intrusion detection system (IDS) method. But now the IDS must be

improved for a new context of the internet such as Internet of Things (IoT) which is surveyed and analyzed in this paper.

This paper is going to survey the up-to-date intrusion detection system concept and also analyze the intrusion detection system based on machine learning.

II. INTRUSION DETECTION SYSTEM CONCEPT

Intrusion detection system: a security service that monitors and analyzes system events for the purpose of finding, and providing real-time or near real-time warning of, attempt to access system resources in an unauthorized manner[15]. IDS are often classified by many researchers and different viewpoint such as classified base on position base composed of Host-based IDS, network-based IDS, and Hybrid IDS[15-18]. And classified based on detection-based consists of signature base IDS, and anomaly based IDS.

A. Position based IDS

The position based IDS divided to 3 types:

- 1) *Host-based IDS (HIDS)*: monitors the characteristics of a single host and the events occurring within that host, such as process identifiers and the system calls they make, for evidence of suspicious activity[15].
- 2) *Network-based IDS (NIDS)*: monitors network traffic for particular network segments of devices and analyzes network, transport, and application protocols to identify suspicious activity[15].
- 3) *Hybrid-based IDS*: Both host-based and network-based IDS, can be used at the same time[20].

B. Detection based IDS

The detection based IDS divided to 2 types:

- 1) *Signature based or misuse IDS* : uses a set of known malicious data patterns (signature) or attack rules that are compared with current behavior to decide if it is that of an intruder. it is also known as misuse detection. this approach can only identify known attacks for which it has pattern or rules [15].
- 2) *Anomaly based IDS*: Anomaly detection is the process of finding outliers in a given dataset. Outliers are the data objects that stand out amongst other objects in the dataset and do not conform to the normal behavior in a dataset[19].

III. MACHINE LEARNING TECHNIQUE FOR INTRUSION DETECTION SYSTEM

Machine Learning Techniques for IoT IDS consists of supervised learning: naïve baye (NB), K-Nearest Neighbor (KNN), decision tree (DT), support vector machine (SVM), random forest (RF), ensemble learning (EL), and unsupervised learning: k-mean, principal component analysis (PCA). See Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. A taxonomy of ML Techniques for IoT-based IDSs [40].

They are most popular techniques used for detection intrusion system that monitored and detected the network and report that status normal/anormal. For Example, these technique are applied as brief below:

1) *Naïve Baye (NB)*: NB is a machine learning classification technique base on Baye's Theorem with an assumption of indepedence among predictors. The classifier algorithm was used to model the normal and abnormal network activity[22]. NB is usually used in IoT to detect intrusion detection in the network layer, and anomaly detection. NB has some advantages, such as simple to understand, requiring less data for classification, easy to implement, applicable for multi-stage[10].

2) *K-Nearest Neighbor (KNN)*: KNN technique does not require any parameter in supervised learning which usually uses Euclidian distance. Euclidian distance in KNN determines the average value of unknown node which is k nearest neighbors. KNN method is used in intrusion detection, malware detections, and anomaly detection in IoT. KNN algorithm is simple, cheap, and easy to apply. In contrast, it is a time-consuming process to identify the missing nodes which are challenging in terms of accuracy [10].

3) *Decision Tree (DT)*: DT is mainly categorized as classification and regression. DT has advantages over other ML techniques like simple construction, easy to implement that handling large data samples. DT are widely used as classifier in security applications like DoS and intrusion detection [10].

4) *Support Vector Machine (SVM)*: The algorithm is used to analyze data that use regression and classification analysis. SVM possesses a high accuracy level which makes it suitable for security application in IoT like intrusion detection, malware detection, etc. [10]. SVM are ideal for anomaly detection where classification between normal and abnormal class is required [21].

5) *Random Forest (RF)*: The method that combines the decision trees and ensemble learning. The prediction is decided by majority voting. This mechanism can be applied for improved the performance of IDS [23]. Used in DDoS attack detection, anomaly detection, an unauthorized IoT devices identification in network layer etc.

6) *Ensemble Learning (EL)*: Used for anomaly detection, malware detection, and intrusion detection. EL use difference classification techniques to get an acceptable outcome by increasing its performance [10].

7) *K-Mean*: The clustering method base on unsupervised learning. Which is usually used in anomaly detection and Sybil attack detection on IoT system [10].

8) *Principal Component Analysis (PCA)*: Which is also know as a feature reduction technique converts a large data set into smaller ones. It decrease the complexity of a system. This method used for selecting a feature to detect real-time intrusion attacks in an IoT system. The combination of PCA and some other ML methods can be applied to provide a strong security protocol [10].

IV. ANALYZED THE EXISTING IDS WITH MACHINE LEARNING

This section analyzed the existing intrusion detection system with machine learning from 17 research papers. These can be classified to 7 aspects as follow and show some details in Table I.

1) Techniques and type composed of a single algorithm [33-39] and combine algorithm or multiple method [10, 24-32]

2) Dataset, The most of the dataset that use are KDDcup99 and NSL_KDD

3) Attack categories consists of Denials of Service (DoS), Probing, Remote to Local (R2L) and User to Root (U2R)

4) Performance consists of accuracy, precision, recall, f-measure, detection rate, computation time, and false positive.

5) Detection base for all of anomaly detection

6) Benchmark are compared with other algorithm (method/model) and compared with the other datasets

7) The reasons for improve the method for IDS consist of Traditional security mechanisms are not appropriate for IoT networks, because the IoT platforms cover regular internet, non-IP network, mobile network, cloud computing, fog computing, and sensor network. IoT devices also have limited processing and memory capability [24], existing anomalous intrusion detection models often misclassified normal network traffics as attacks while minority attacks go undetected due to extreme an imbalance in network traffic data. The leads to high false positive and low detection rate [25], Traditional classifiers shown the poor performance, now there is no standard model and datasets are available for evaluating the IDS [27], Lightweight techniques with less complexity, low resource usage and low computation requirement are necessary. The development of such techniques remains a challenging research task [28], the network behavior intrusion or normal base on the collection data of network status which high dimension and linear inseparable. In order to improved accuracy of network intrusion detection [29].

TABLE I. THE EXISTING INTRUSION DETECTION MODEL BASE ON MACHINE LEARNING

Paper NO, Year	Technique Name	Type	Performance	Dataset	Attacks Categories	Benchmark
[33], 2018	Decision Tree	Single	guarantee accuracy	KDDCUP99	DOS, Prob, R2L, U2R	Compared with two method
[34], 2017	KNN	Single	high accuracy	NSL-KDD	DOS, Prob	Compared with tradition KNN
[35], 2018	K-Mean/Random forest	Combine	improve false positive	KDDCUP99	DOS, Prob, R2L, U2R	Compared with many cluster dataset
[36], 2020	Support Vector Machine	Single	Increases the accuracy and minimizes the false alarm rate.	NSL-KDD	DOS, Prob, R2L, U2R	Challenge Complex Environment such as cloud computing
[37], 2020	Naïve bayes	Single	improve accuracy	NSL_KDD	DOS, Prob, R2L, U2R	Compared to other models.
[38], 2019	Random Forest	Single	accuracy, precision, recall, f-measure	KDDCUP99	DOS, Prob, R2L, U2R	Compared with different features
[39], 2017	K-Mean	Single	detection rate, false detection rate	KDDCUP99	DOS, Prob, R2L, U2R	Improved k-mean algorithm
[10], 2020	Decision Tree, Random Forest	Combine	high accuracy, precision	NSL-KDD CICIDS2017	DOS, Prob, R2L, U2R	Compare with other dataset
[24], 2020	Decision Tree, Random Forest	Combine	lowest false positive accuracy, Precision, recall, f-score	IoT Botnet	DoS ,DoS, Reconnaissance, Theft	Compared with KDD, UNSW-NB15, CICIDS2017
[25], 2019	K-Mean, Random Forest	Combine	higher detection accuracy, sensitivity, and specificity	KDDCUP99	DOS, Prob, R2L, U2R	Compared with existing model
[26], 2019	PCA, Naïve Bayes, K-Nearest	Combine	higher detection rate, low false positive accuracy	NSL-KDD	R2L, U2R	Compared with existing model
[27], 2017	Ensemble SVM Rough set theory (RST)	Combine	increase the detection accuracy and reduces the computation time	KDDCUP'99 UNB-ISCX HTTP CSIC	-	Enhances the detection rate and decreases the detection time
[28], 2018	Principle Component Analysis Level 1-2	Combine	Reduce the complexity, and Increase the detection rate	Kyoto Honeypot	-	Compared with different dataset
[29], 2017	Random Forest, Support Vector Machine	Combine	higher detection rate	KDDCUP99	DOS, Prob, R2L, U2R	Compared with Other algorithm
[30], 2017	Principle Component Analysis, Soft max regression, K-Nearest Neighbors	Combine	low computing complexity, low memory size, high accuracy	KDDCUP99	DOS, Prob, R2L, U2R	Compared with different number of features
[31], 2016	K-Means, Naïve bayes	Combine	improve detection rate	KDDCUP99	DOS, Prob, R2L, U2R	Compared with other model
[32], 2019	Naïve bayes , Random Forest K-Nearest Neighbor, J-48	Combine	high accuracy low false positive	NSL-KDD	DOS, Prob, R2L, U2R	Compared with other model

V. CONCLUSION

In this paper , we present a literature review of intrusion detection system base on machine learning, including of three things: First, intrusion detection system concept. The second, one is machine learning technique for intrusion detection system. Finally, analyzed the existing intrusion detection model base on machine learning. The knowledge from the analysis will provided direction for the researcher to develop and improve the IDS base on machine learning for support the new paradigm Internet of things network.

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Machine Learning Based Attack Detection in Internet of Things Network

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Abstract- In recent years, the Internet of Things (IoT) has grown up rapidly and tremendously. This growth has brought big and special problems. Two of the urgent topics of problems are security and privacy for IoT devices. Those devices are creating and gathering all data in their connections. For the security of IoT, detection of anomaly attacks is the first and crucial point for avoiding any interruption in the connection. Machine Learning algorithms have been rising and improving substantially year by year. Many classic tests can detect many attacks in the current time. However, those techniques are not enough for security since the types of attacks are changing and getting stronger frequently. In this study, we propose that how to detect a maximum number of attacks in IoT networks by applying machine learning techniques, especially K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN), Logistic Regression (LR), and Random Forest (RF) models. Dataset is presumably one of the most important starting points for the use of those techniques. UNSW-NB15 dataset which is publicly available has been used for this study. K-Nearest Neighbors algorithm shows 98.03% accuracy which is the best performance within the selected algorithms.

Keywords- Internet of Things, Security, Attack detection, Machine Learning, Confusion matrix, Classification report

I. INTRODUCTION

The Internet has connected computers and is spreading in every corner of the world at present. It provides many protocols which are used for communicating networks. Semi-Automatic Ground Environment (SAGE) and Semi-Automatic Business Research Environment (SABRE) have connected at the beginning of the 1950s due to the Internet network. The Advanced Research Projects Agency (ARPA) acted as design financing for ARPANET in the 1960s. In the late 1960s, usage of the internet increased in that time. From ARPANET, the modern internet comes which are now using by people.

Devices are needed to be used to communicate with each other due to the increase in Internet usage in recent years. The term named Internet of Things (IoT) has been taken place everywhere for this reason. IoT is forming connections among one smart device with many devices and building a communication network. This definition is used for the first time by Kevin Ashton in 1991. Internet of Things includes wide areas such as wearable technology, kitchen robots, electrical cars, mobile phones, etc.

To create better performance for the users of these systems, many researchers have been studying IoT for a long time. There are a lot of problems in the IoT environment. Cyberattacks are one of the most important problems of IoT devices. This study focuses on how to detect attacks on IoT devices using machine learning techniques, especially K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN), Logistic Regression (LR), and Random Forest (RF) Models to increase security layers of the network.

Review of related literature, types of attacks, dataset, machine learning methods, data analysis, and results and conclusion are discussed in sections II, III, IV, V, VI, and VII, respectively.

II. REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Many research works related to the detection of malicious activities in IoT networks are going on. Monika et al. [1] proposed an advanced intrusion detection system for attacks detection in IoT networks using deep learning models named Convolutional Neural Network combined with LSTM applied on CICIDS2017 dataset, obtained an accuracy of almost 99.03%

Nilesh et al. [2] designed machine learning-based approaches for attacks detection in IoT networks using an Artificial Neural Network algorithm on the NSL-KDD99 dataset. Their model works well, and its accuracy is 99.4%. Machine learning approaches for anomaly detection in IoT networks have been proposed in [3] using K-Nearest Neighbors algorithm on the IoT network intrusion dataset. They showed 99% accuracy through their works. Author et al. [4] a packet-level machine learning attacks detection for IoT devices has been proposed where K-Nearest Neighbors, Support Vector Machine, Neural Network, Random Forest and Decision Tree models are applied on KDD99 dataset. They got a 99% accuracy maximum in their research.

Abhinaya et al. [5] proposed high-level deep learning library for the detection of malicious activities in IoT networks where four deep learning models such as Convolutional Neural Network (CNN), Autoencoder, Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP), and Deep Neural Network are used on UNSW-NB15 and NSL-KDD99 datasets. They showed 98% accuracy in their work with the model.

Canedo et al. [6] explained about security is one of the weakest areas in IoT. That is why they implemented the Artificial Neural Network (ANN) technique which is one of the Machine Learning techniques. They observed that can this technique detect anomaly attacks on the gateway. The authors also describing that IoT devices can divide into 2 primary groups. Edge devices and Gateway devices. Edge devices mean low-power and low-resource devices include sensors. Edge devices use for a single aim, kind of collecting humidity data and send to the gateway devices. Gateway devices mean they collect data from edge devices, and they connect with devices and gateways. The authors used Arduino Uno and Raspberry Pi 3. They used Arduino Uno to create an edge device. Raspberry Pi 3 was used to create a gateway device. Raspberry pi 3 works like a computer and it has 1 GB RAM for implement machine learning techniques to smaller data sets. They collected 4000 data samples from the edge device, and they stocked their data in the MySQL database. They implemented ANN to their real data and all data were not harmful. Then, they manipulated their sensors on edge devices and sent invalid data to the gateway device. They got 99% accuracy in their study.

Author et al. [7] used different ways for improving the IoT security level. He used cloud microservices for anomaly detection. The author used 3 different data sets and all of them include different information. For example, one of them includes credit card scores and credit risks. Another one includes temperature and humidity data. The author collected all data and sent it to the Raspberry Pi microcontroller. From this microcontroller, he uploads his data to the Microsoft Azure Machine Learning Studio. Finally, they are trying to detect malicious data and anomaly attacks. The author also used one of the most popular datasets which are publicly available. This dataset is generated from the University of California San Diego (UCSD). This dataset has many images of pedestrian walkways. If any non-pedestrian enters walkways, it looks like an anomaly attack. The author used 34 videos for training and 36 videos for testing. Each clip includes 200 frames.

Lawal et al. [8] propose different network anomaly reduction schemes in IoT networks. In this paper, they used 200,700 data and they implemented 3 different supervised machine learning algorithms in this dataset. Their result comes with different values. For example, in the KNN algorithm, they have 94% accuracy, Naïve Bayes has 85% accuracy. These results show to use more data increases accuracy. These results are not bad for 200,000 data but increased data might get better scores. The author used ROC (Receiver Operating Characteristic) curve method in their study. This curve works with two parameters. These are true positive rates and false-positive rates. When the curve reaches a peak, which refers to one decision threshold. The authors implemented the ROC curve to the same algorithms. Their new results increased well, such as KNN has 98% accuracy and Naïve Bayes has 96% accuracy. In the ROC curve, when the true positive rate and false positive rate reach the same value, it gives the best accuracy.

Zhang et al. [9] propose a unified model which is a combination of multiscale convolutional neural network (MSCNN) and long short-term memory (LSTM). This model is used for analyzing spatial-temporal features performance in the article. The author used 175,341 data for the training set and 82,332 data for the test set in model 1. The author also selected a dataset, which is classified by attack types, in this style, the author used 1601 normal and attack data in model 2. When it comes to the result section, the MSCNN-LSTM model has 95.6% accuracy for model 1, which is good but also the false-negative rate is 1.6% that means algorithm divided attack or normal mostly correct. When model 2 result comes on the article, MSCNN-LSTM model 89.8% accuracy which means algorithm did not detect attacks correctly in the study. Also, the false-negative rate goes up to 8.6% that is normal, because classification and correlation matrix has grown up, and it makes complicated mathematical problems. The

interesting point of this study is algorithm got 99.1% accuracy for worm attacks. Even worm attack is the lowest number of attack type in the dataset, that sound is good.

The existing proposals for attacks detection in IoT networks result in low accuracy. Also, these schemes used datasets which are available in public for a decade. So, the chances for anomaly detection of newly released IoT devices are low. For this reason, this study focuses on multiple number machine learning approaches on a newly available dataset for obtaining more than 95% accuracy.

III. TYPES OF ATTACKS

The usage of IoT is increasing day by day. IoT devices do not have effective antivirus systems. Although the malware things, Scientists are producing useful firewalls for IoT. Even though this huge security market, many attacks are happening, and they are giving more damage to devices. This section offers to explain some of the attack types which is used in this study, all attack types have different details.

A. *Backdoor*

Backdoor is a secure illegal remote Access to a device which is attacker circumvents a normal furtiveness authentication method. It is very tough for detection in the system because it runs background and is covered. That is why users can not recognize this attack type. If attackers reach to device from the back door, it is possible to steal information, install malware applications, and easily take it under the control of computer systems.

B. *Denial of Service*

Assume that a data center has 500 Mbps upload that it is giving service. The malicious bots who organized from attackers, if they create a 500 Mb traffic in a second, the application cannot give service. This attack calls DoS. DoS attack sends packets such as unnecessary messages, and they have an invalid return address. Computer systems are not available for finding certain return addresses while attackers sending packets, and computer systems start to wait before the connection is interrupted. After the connection is interrupted, attackers are sending more and more packets to the system, these invalid return addresses cut all connections and users cannot reach such as browsers, emails, and applications.

C. *Shellcode*

This attack uses a payload of software susceptibility. The attack is a limited piece of code that is inside an exploit attack. It Works on command Shell in software. This malignant code is implemented in computer memory (RAM) thoroughly exploiting the susceptibilities of stack buffer overflow.

D. *Reconnaissance*

This attack could also be described as a probe. This attack collects data from the network to avoid its security controls. This attack type works from ping. Attack follows ping to detect real IP address.

E. *Exploit*

This attack causes malicious behavior on the network with the array instructions such as bugs or vulnerable things. These behaviors include take the control of computer system or giving access to the system easily for DoS attacks.

IV. DATASET

As we explained in the related literature reviews section, all machine learning algorithms need the dataset for implementation. Science has been creating many dataset types such as DARPA98, KDD, NSL-KDD, CAIDA, UNSW-NB15, etc. All these datasets have different implementation areas, for example, information technologies, autonomous cars, education, Fintech, human resources, etc. All implementation areas have similar issues in their fields. The most significant point in these issues is security. UNSW-NB15 dataset has been used in this study. This dataset has created in the Cyber Range Lab of the Australian Centre for Cyber Security (ACCS) through the IXIA

Perfect Storm tool [10]. This dataset includes a hybrid of normal traffic and attack traffic. Twelve algorithms and tools such as Bro-IDS, Argus have been used to produce UNSW-NB15. This dataset includes 39 features with a class label. This dataset has over 2.5 million data which is good for prediction. Table I shows the categorization of features of the dataset.

TABLE I
FEATURES CATEGORIZATION OF UNSW-NB15 DATASET

Number	Name of category	Description
1	Flow features	It contains the identifier attributes between hosts such as client to server or server to client
2	Basic features	It includes the attributes that characterize the connections of protocols
3	Content features	It contains the attributes of TCP/IP and also includes some attributes of http services
4	Time features	It includes the attributes of time such as round-trip time of TCP protocol start/end packet time arrival time between packets etc.
5	Additional generated features General purpose features	Own purpose features which to care for the protocols service
	Connection features	Built based on the chronological order of the last time feature
6	Labelled features	It shows the label of recorded data

Table II shows how much data UNSW-NB15 has in the dataset. In this study, all attack data have been used for getting the best result. This dataset has five different attack types and all of them are created in the dataset.

TABLE II
NUMBER OF DATA IN UNSW-NB15 DATASET

Name	Count
Total Number of Data	2,540,044
Normal	2,218,761
Attacks	321,283

Table III shows the number of attack data and attack category in the dataset.

TABLE III
ATTACKS CATEGORIZATION IN UNSW-NB15 DATASET

Attack Category	Number of Data
Backdoor	63294
Denial of Service	56353
Shellcode	75118
Reconnaissance	71993
Exploits	54525

V. MACHINE LEARNING METHODS

Machine Learning is the subfield of Artificial Intelligence. It is one of the best methods that can provide a result without being explicitly programmed. Machine learning has four big different techniques. Supervised Learning, Unsupervised Learning, Reinforcement Learning, and Semi-Supervised Learning.

A. *K-Nearest Neighbor Model*

K-Nearest Neighbor (KNN) is the subfield of the supervised learning method. This algorithm works for regression and classification problems. The rule of this algorithm is similar things should have similar characteristics. When the algorithm classifies all characteristic things, it should be close to proximity. This algorithm estimates the distances between input value and classified value. K refers to when we classify the new data, algorithm looks to classified data for examine the closeness between these data. KNN is extremely easy to implement in its most basic form, and yet performs quite complex classification tasks. It is a lazy learning algorithm since it does not have a specialized training phase. Rather, it uses all data for training while classifying a new data point or instance. KNN is a non-parametric learning algorithm, which means that it does not assume anything about the underlying data. This is an extremely useful feature since most of the real-world data does not really follow any theoretical assumption e.g., linear separability, uniform distribution, etc. The intuition behind the KNN algorithm is one of the simplest of all the supervised machine learning algorithms. It simply calculates the distance of a new data point to all other training data points. The distance can be of any type e.g., Euclidean or Manhattan, etc. It then selects the K-nearest data points, where K can be any integer. Finally, it assigns the data point to the class to which most of the K data points belong. Figure 1 shows KNN algorithm.

Figure 1. K-Nearest Neighbor Algorithm

B. *Logistic Regression Model*

Logistic Regression is a supervised machine learning algorithm from the field of Statistics. It is the method for binary classification problems. Logistic Regression is named for the function used at the core of the method known as logistic function. This function is also called sigmoid function. Logistic Regression is known as logit regression, maximum-entropy classification, or the log-linear classifier. In this model the probabilities describing the possible outcomes of a single trial are modeled using logistic function or sigmoid function. A logistic function $f(x)$ or logistic curve is a common “S” shape (sigmoid curve) in Figure 2. Where $f(x)$ is the prediction probability and x is the input data, $f(x)=1/1+e^{-(x)}$

Figure 2. Sigmoid Curve

C. Random Forest Model

Random Forest is a supervised machine learning method that operates by constructing multiple decision trees. A decision tree is a tree-shaped diagram used to determine the output. Figure 3 shows that each branch gives the output of individual possible outcomes. The base estimator of this model is the decision tree. Each estimator is trained on a different bootstrap sample having the same size as the training set. The Random Forest model introduces further randomization on features in the training of individual trees. Random Forest algorithm is used for both classification and regression problems. Classification aggregates predictions by the majority votes. And regression aggregates predictions by averaging.

Figure 3. Random Forest Model

VI. DATA ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The evaluation of the results of the implementation of the algorithms has been calculated according to the confusion matrix. Size of the matrix is depending on the number of the class in the testing dataset. There are a couple of criteria terms produced by the confusion matrix. Those criteria's names are respectively precision (Pr), recall (Rc), f-measure (F1), and accuracy.

- TP = Number of True Positive predicted values. (Correct classified)
- TN = Number of the True Negative predicted values. (Incorrect classified)
- FP = Number of the False Positive predicted values. (Correct classified)
- FN = Number of the False Negative predictive values. (Incorrect classifier)

Table IV, Table V, and Table VI show all type confusion matrix which is used in this study.

TABLE IV
RESULT TYPES OF IMPLEMENTED ALGORITHMS

<u>Precision</u>	$TP/(TP+FP)$
<u>Recall</u>	$TP/(TP+FN)$
<u>F-measure</u>	$(TP+TN)/(TP+TN+FP+FN)$
<u>Accuracy</u>	$2 * \frac{Precision * Recall}{Precision + Recall}$

TABLE V
2X2 CONFUSION MATRIX

Actual Value	Predicted Value	
	True Positive	False Negative
	False Positive	True Negative

TABLE VI
NXN CONFUSION MATRIX

		Predicted Value			
		Class 1	Class 2	...	Class n
Actual Value	Class 1	X_{11}	X_{12}	...	X_{1n}
	Class 2	X_{21}	X_{22}	...	X_{2n}

	Class n	X_{n1}	X_{n2}	...	X_{nn}

Due to imbalanced data, we have used 210,000 datasets. It includes 61,987 attack data and 148,013 normal data. When we implement our first machine learning algorithm, which is the KNN algorithm, we got 98.03% accuracy in this algorithm. 896 benign data have been predicted as attack traffic, and 3245 attack data have been predicted as benign data. Table VII shows the confusion matrix of the KNN algorithm. Figure 4 and Figure 5 show the classification report and ROC curve of the model, respectively.

TABLE VII
CONFUSION MATRIX OF KNN MODEL

KNN	Benign	Attack
Benign	193168	896
Attack	3245	12691

	precision	recall	f1-score	support
0	0.98	1.00	0.99	194064
1	0.93	0.80	0.86	15936
accuracy			0.98	210000
macro avg	0.96	0.90	0.92	210000
weighted avg	0.98	0.98	0.98	210000

Figure 4. Classification Report of KNN Model

ROC_AUC_Score of KNN Model : 0.9732975151155989
Accuracy of KNN Model : 0.9802809523809524

Figure 5. ROC Curve of KNN Model

When we implement the Logistic Regression method, we got 92.4% accuracy in attack detection. Table VIII shows the confusion matrix of this algorithm where 15936 attack data is predicted as benign data. Figure 6 and Figure 7 show the classification report and ROC curve of the model, respectively.

TABLE VIII
CONFUSION MATRIX OF LOGISTIC REGRESSION MODEL

Logistic Regression	Benign	Attack
Benign	194064	0
Attack	15936	0

	precision	recall	f1-score	support
0	0.92	1.00	0.96	194064
1	0.00	0.00	0.00	15936
accuracy			0.92	210000
macro avg	0.46	0.50	0.48	210000
weighted avg	0.85	0.92	0.89	210000

Figure 6. Classification Report of Logistic Regression Model

Figure 7. ROC Curve of Logistic Regression Model

When we implement the Random Forest model, we got 92.41% accuracy in attack detection. Table IX shows the confusion matrix of this algorithm where 15936 attack data is predicted as benign data. Figure 8 and Figure 9 show the classification report and ROC curve of the model, respectively.

TABLE IX
CONFUSION MATRIX OF RANDOM FOREST MODEL

Random Forest	Benign	Attack
Benign	194064	0
Attack	15936	0

	precision	recall	f1-score	support
0	0.92	1.00	0.96	194064
1	0.00	0.00	0.00	15936
accuracy			0.92	210000
macro avg	0.46	0.50	0.48	210000
weighted avg	0.85	0.92	0.89	210000

Figure 8. Classification Report of Random Forest Model

Figure 9. ROC Curve of Random Forest Model

VII. CONCLUSION

In this technology age, it shows us the electronic devices which relate to the internet, it covers human life. The data science world is developing new techniques for the security of those devices. When we look for the collection of data in networks, IoT devices are closing to the computer systems. This study aims for improving the security level of IoT networks. With the machine learning algorithms, we reached at least 92% accuracy with all our algorithms that are implemented to the dataset. We got the highest 98.03% accuracy from the K-Nearest Neighbors algorithm which is a good contribution in respect to the state-of-the-art of research. This study reached our goals, we detected most of the attacks in our dataset. Data science will grow up with our next research and articles. Data is very important, so we always try to secure all types of data. In the future, we will research to apply Deep learning and Reinforcement learning models for bigger datasets to get better accuracy result in detecting attacks.

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Comparative Analysis of Selected Filtered Feature Rankers Evaluation of Cyber Attacks Detection

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Abstract— An increase in global connectivity and rapid expansion of computer usage and computer networks has made the security of the computer system an important issue; with the industries and cyber communities being faced with new kinds of attacks daily. The high complexity of cyberattacks poses a great challenge to the protection of cyberinfrastructures, Confidentiality, Integrity, and availability of sensitive information stored on it. Intrusion detection systems monitors' network traffic for suspicious (Intrusive) activity and issues alert when such activity is detected. Building Intrusion detection system that is computationally efficient and effective requires the use of relevant features of the network traffics (packets) identified by feature selection algorithms. This paper implemented K-Nearest Neighbor and Naïve Bayes Intrusion detection models using relevant features of the UNSW-NB15 Intrusion detection dataset selected by Gain Ratio, Information Gain, Relief F and Correlation rankers feature selection techniques. The results of the comparative analysis of the model's predictive performances shows that, among all the feature selection techniques used, the models of Relief F reduced features recorded the best cyber-attacks predictive performance. Models built with all the features of the dataset gives the least predictive performance. All the KNN models recorded better predictive performance than all Naïve Bayes models. The models' performance were measured in terms of classification /detection accuracy, precision and false alarm rate.

Keyword:- Features Rankers, Cyber-attacks, Computer Security, Intrusion, Classification, Network Packets

I. INTRODUCTION

The increase in global connectivity and rapid expansion of computer usage and computer networks has made the security of the computer system an important issue; with the industries and cyber communities being faced with new kinds of attacks daily. The high complexity of intrusion poses a great challenge to the protection of cyberinfrastructure and the Confidentiality, integrity, and availability of sensitive information stored on them. The state of computer security is complicated, it is difficult to have a system that is completely free from attacks. The nature and the means of executing cyberattacks make it prevalent. Cyber-attacks are easy and cheap to execute, all that is require to stage a cyber-attacks are computer system and internet access, the nature of internet makes launching a cyber-attack is less risky than physical attacks, and not constrained by geographical distance. [1]. Network traffics contain different types of protocols and services which accounted for the multiple features in the network packet.

Some of these features are redundant or irrelevant and does not contribute the classification of the network packets as either attack or normal network packets. The redundant features are the primary causes of increasing the false alarm rate (FAR) and decrease in detection accuracy. Feature Selection (FS) Techniques are the methods used to determine the relevant features of a dataset. It is an efficient way to reduce the dimensionality of a problem [2]. Different FS techniques existed in classification and clustering problems. They are i) Filter method ii) Wrapper Method and iii) Embedded method. The filter methods are used to select the features based on the scores in various statistical correlations. Wrapper method uses a greedy approach in feature selection. It evaluates all possible combination and produces the result for Machine learning. The embedded method combines the advantage of two models. Filtered Feature selection algorithms can be grouped into two categories from the point of view of a method's output: feature-ranking and feature-subset selection. Feature-subset selection focuses on selecting best subset of features that satisfies an evaluation criterion, feature-ranking on the other hand ranks features according to certain evaluation criterial, which measures the relevance of individual feature to the target class, and select the set of ranked features that gives the best evaluation performance, the drawback of this methods is that, a features that is not relevant to the target class on its own, can be very relevant when combined with others features.

The objectives of feature-ranking are three-folds: improving the prediction performance of the predictors, providing faster and more cost-effective predictors, and providing a better understanding of the underlying process that generated the dataset [3]. The FS also reduces the computational time to implement an online Network Intrusion Detection System (NIDS) [4]. The efficiency of the FS methods is measured by its accuracy at removing noisy and redundant features [5]. The quality of the network traffics /dataset does not only help to build effective NIDS but also shows its potential efficiency during deployment in a real-life operating environment. NIDS analyze and monitor network traffic to detect suspicious activities and vulnerability in the system [6]. The effectiveness of NIDS is evaluated based on its ability to correctly identify network traffics as attacks traffic or benign traffics (normal) in a comprehensive dataset that contains normal and abnormal behaviors [7].

Feature-ranking techniques ranked features independently without involving any learning algorithm based on statistics, information theory, or some functions of classifier's outputs [8]. It consists of scoring each feature according to a particular evaluation criterion [9]. Several authors have proposed various features selection methods. In the work of Wang and Gombault [9], IG and Chi-squared were applied to extract nine most important features from the forty one features to build Bayesian Network and C 4.5 decision tree classifiers to detect DDoS attack in the network. Results obtained shows that the detection accuracy remains the same while the overall efficiency improved. Authors in [10] proposed a multi-filter feature selection techniques that combines the results four filter selections methods on NSL-KDD intrusion network dataset to achieve an optimum selection. C4.5 decision tree evaluation of the thirteen optimal selected features out of forty one features shows a high detection rate and classification accuracy when compared to the forty-one features and other classification techniques. [11] Proposed a feature selection method based on Decision Dependent Correlation (DDC). Mutual information of each feature and decision is calculated and top twenty important features {feature no.: 3, 5, 40, 24, 2, 10, 41, 36, 8, 13, 27, 28, 22, 11, 14, 17, 18, 7, 9 and 15} are selected and evaluated by SVM classifier. The classified result is 93.46% detection accuracy. [12] Applied Information Gain (IG), Correlation-based (CFS), Gain Ratio (GR) feature selection to reduce the dimensionality of NSL-KDD dataset, and built a decision tree classifiers of the three feature selection methods. The three classifier recorded an improved performance than the classifier built with the whole NSL-KDD dataset. [13] Proposed a feature selection method that combined three filter methods; Gain ratio, Chi-squared and Relief F (triple-filter) in a cluster-based heterogeneous Wireless sensor network (WSN) for attacks classification. Fourteen important features of the NSL-KDD intrusion detection benchmark dataset out of the forty one original features were extracted for intrusion detection classifier. Results obtained show that the proposed method can effectively reduce the number of features with a high classification accuracy and detection rate in comparison with other filter methods.

II. METHODOLOGY

The proposed architecture of the Comparative Analysis of Selected Filtered Feature Rankers Evaluators for Cyber Attacks Detection is depicted in Fig. 1. The discretization of the UNSW-NB15 dataset was first carried out to make it suitable for machine learning. Four Filtered Feature Rankers Evaluators algorithms; (Information Gain, Relief F, Gain Ration, and Correlation) rankers were used to rank and select the optimal relevant features of training and testing UNSW-NB15 intrusion datasets. The training dataset with the all it feature and the reduced features of the training datasets were used to train the K Nearest Neighbors (KNN, and Naive Bayes' algorithms. The testing dataset with the all it features and the reduced features of the testing dataset were used to

evaluate the two classifiers. The model's training is depicted in black arrow lines while the model's evaluation is depicted in red arrow lines in the figure. The results of the evaluation for each reduced dataset were analyzed.

A. Data Munging and Analytic

This section outlines the Feature Rankers Evaluators and the machine learning techniques used for this study.

i. Description of Attributes Selection Evaluators

Attributes Selection Evaluator ranks features based on their relevant to the target class, ranking is a way of evaluating relevant features and selecting a minimal set of features based on given criteria in order to build simple models, that take less time to compute and become more understandable Feature ranking evaluation criterion compute the score $S(fi)$ of feature (fi) of the training dataset. By convention a high score implies important (relevant) of the feature to the target class and select the k highest ranked features according to S . This is usually not optimal, but computationally efficient and often preferable to other, more complicated feature selection methods that involve searching through the entire search space. In this study, we use four feature-ranking techniques; Correlation Attribute Evaluator (CAE), Gain Ratio Attribute Evaluator (GAE), Information Gain attribute Evaluator (IGAE) and Relief F Attribute Evaluator (RFAE).

Correlation Attribute Evaluator (CAE)

Correlation Attribute Evaluator (CAE), evaluate Attribute using correlation analysis. The correlation between each attributes x and the target class Y , can be measured by finding correlation coefficient. A good feature is expected to have a higher correlation coefficient between it and target class. In correlation attribute evaluator method the attributes are considered based on their values where each value is treated as an indicator. CAE handles only nominal attributes input for evaluation and it uses Pearson's formula for computing correlation coefficient. for a candidate feature $x_i \in X$ and regression target Y the Pearson correlation coefficient is given by

$$\mathcal{R}(i) = \frac{\text{cov}(X_i, Y)}{\sqrt{\text{var}(X_i)\text{var}(Y)}} \quad (1)$$

where cov designates the covariance and var the variance.

Figure 1; Architecture of the Selected Filtered Feature Rankers Evaluators for Cyber Attacks Detection

Information Gain attribute Evaluator (IGAE)

Information gain (IG) measures the amount of information in bits about the class prediction, if the only information available is the presence of a feature and the corresponding class distribution. Concretely, it measures the expected reduction in entropy (uncertainty associated with a random feature) [15], it is given by equation 2 Info Gain (Class, feature) = H (target class (Y)) – H (target class(Y) | feature (X))

$$IG = H(Y) - H(Y|X) = H(X) - H(X|Y) \tag{2}$$

Where $H(Y)$; the entropy of the target class $H(Y)$ and $H(X|Y)$ is the entropy of target class given a certain attribute X

The entropy of the target class Y is given by equation (3).

$$H(Y) = - \sum_{y \in Y} P(y) \log_2(P(y)) \tag{3}$$

Equation (4) gives the entropy of target class Y after observing feature X .

$$H(Y|X) = - \sum_{x \in X} P(x) \sum_{y \in Y} P(y|x) \log_2(P(y|x)) \tag{4}$$

Gain Ratio Attribute Evaluator (GRAE)

Gain ratio (GR) is a modification of the information gain that reduces its bias. It considered the number and size of branches in choosing an attribute. It assess the value of an attribute by measuring its gain ratio with respect to the target class [16], the root attribute is the attribute of the UNSW-NB15 with the highest gain ratio, the gain ratio is the ratio of the information gain and the split information for the attribute as presented in equation (5)

$$\text{Gain Ratio} = \frac{\text{Information Gain}(X)}{\text{Split Information}(X)}$$

The information gain of attribute X is given by equation 2. The Split information value of an attribute is chosen by taking the average of all the values in the domain of current attribute. It is given by equation (6)

$$\text{Split}(X) = - \sum_{x \in X} \frac{|x|}{|N|} \cdot \log_2 \frac{|x|}{|N|}$$

Where n is the number of instances in the UNSW-NB15 training dataset

Relief Attribute Evaluator (RFAE)

Relief Attribute Evaluator (RFAE) sample an instance recurrently using distance function taking into consideration the value of the given attribute for the nearest instance of the same and different class [13]. The original Relief algorithm, proposed by Kira and Rendell [8], is a two-class filtering algorithm for features normalized to [0, 1]. Each feature is initially assigned a zero weight. A-dimensional training example R is chosen randomly and the Euclidean distance to all other instances calculated. Denote the nearest hit in the same class H, and the nearest miss in a different-class M. Since a good feature R[A] should be able to separate class values, it should have a small distance to H and a large distance to M. Hence W[A] is adjusted to reward good features and penalize poor ones. The final selection of features is made by selecting those large W[A], (that is, those that exceeded a given threshold.)

ii. Description of Machine learning techniques

Two machine learning algorithms, namely; KNN and Naïve Bayes were used in this study to build the intrusion detection system,

K-Nearest Neighbor,

Let p_i and q_t represent the instance to be classified and the other instances in the dataset having the same number of features as P respectively, K- nearest neighbor

Euclidean distance between p_i and q_t is defined in equation 7.

$$d(p_i, q_t) = \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n (p_i - q_i)^2} \tag{7}$$

From equation (3), a given instance will be classified as the attack categories having majority attacks among top k closest instance to the given instance.

Naïve Bayes)

Given the UNSW-NB15 intrusion detection dataset that have X number of attributes called the predictors ($X = x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n$) and another attribute y called the class label, with ten members y_1, \dots, y_{10} , the Naive Bayes probability that a class y_j will be assigned to a given unlabelled instance X is given in equation (8).

$$P(y_j | x_1, \dots, x_{42}) = \frac{P(y_j) \prod_{i=1}^{42} P(x_i | y_j)}{P(x_i)} \quad (\forall_j = 0, 1, \dots, 9) \tag{8}$$

Maximum posterior probability for classifying a new instance attack categories is given in

equation (9)

$$y = \underset{y}{\text{arg max}} P(y) \prod_{i=0}^9 P(y_i) P(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_{42} | y) \tag{9}$$

III. RESULT

The features of the UNSW-NB15 intrusion detection dataset selected by the four features rankers deployed in this research is presented in Table 1, these reduced selected features with the complete features were used to build Intrusion detection systems of Naïve Bayes and KNN. The UNSW-NB15 testing dataset was used to evaluate all the classifiers. The confusion matrix and the performance of the KNN and Naïve Bayes classifiers with each of the selected features of the ranking feature technique is presented in Tables 2 and 3 respectively, from tables, it shows that KNN and Naive Bayes intrusion detection models of Relief F selected features that identified thirteen (13) features recorded the best performance in terms of detection accuracy, classification precision and false alarm rate. The Intrusion detection models of KNN and Naïve Bayes of the fourteen (14) features identified by the Gain Ratio recorded the second best performance in terms of the selected performance metrics. Correlation and information Gain recorded the third and the fourth performances among the Rankers Features Selection Techniques respectively. Intrusion detection models of the two classifier with all of features of the UNSW-NB15 intrusion detection network dataset recorded the least and poorest performance, this result shows the importance and

ability of the Rankers Features Selection Techniques to improve the performance of intrusion detection models.

The comparison analysis of the two classifiers shows that, KNN intrusion detection models recorded better detection accuracy, precision and false alarm rate than the Naïve Bayes model in the classification of UNSW-NB15 intrusion

detection network dataset, it can be further deduced that the Relief F features selection method with KNN is the best-performing algorithm for the detection of network packets of UNSW-NB15 intrusion detection dataset. The comparison analysis of the selected Rankers Features Selection Techniques with each machine learning algorithms, based on the selected performance metrics is illustrated in Fig. 2.

Table 1; Features Selected by the Filtered Features Rankers

Relief F (13)	Gain Ratio (14)	Information Gain(15)	Correlation Ranker (11)
proto, service, state, smean, ct_dst_src_ltm Sttl, ct_state_ttl, ct_srv_src, ct_dst_sport_ltm, ct_dst_sport_ltm, ct_srv_dst, dttl, ct_dst_ltm, ct_src_ltm	Proto, service, smean, ct_state_ttl, ct_dst_sport_ltm, ct_dst_dport_ltm, ct_srv_dst, Sbytes, dbytes, rate, dmean ,dpkts , dur, sload	proto, service, state, smean, swin, sttl, ct_state_ttl, dwin, ct_dst_sport_ltm, ct_src_dport_ltm, Sbytes, dttl, tcprrt, stcpb, dtcpb	proto, service, state, ct_srv_src, ct_dst_src_ltm, swin, sttl, Dwin, ct_dst_sport_ltm, ct_src_dport_ltm, ct_srv_dst

Table 2: Confusion Matrix and Performance of KNN Models with Each of the Rankers Features Selection Techniques

Rankers Features Selection Techniques	Number of selected Features	Confusion Matrix				Performance Metrics		
		TP	TN	FP	TP	Accuracy	Precision	FAR
Gain Ratio	14	106023	50900	13318	5100	89.50%	88.84%	20.74%
Information Gain	15	104572	49908	14769	6092	88.10%	87.62%	22.84%
Relief F	13	108503	51420	10838	4580	91.21%	90.92%	17.41%
Correlation	11	104572	50826	14769	5174	88.63%	87.62%	22.52%
All Attribute	49	90572	28026	28769	27974	67.64%	75.89%	50.65%

Table 4: Confusion Matrix and Performance of Naïve Bayes Models with Each of the Rankers Features Selection Techniques

Rankers Features Selection Techniques	Number of selected Features	Confusion Matrix				Performance Metrics		
		TP	TN	FP	TP	Accuracy	Precision	FAR
Gain Ratio	14	100629	47007	18712	8993	84.20%	84.32%	28.47%
Information Gain	15	89042	44576	30299	11424	76.20%	74.61%	40.47%
Relief F	13	102983	48937	16358	7063	86.64%	86.29%	25.05%
Correlation	11	93072	47186	26269	8814	79.99%	77.99%	35.76%
All Attribute	49	81272	29026	38069	26974	62.90%	68.10%	56.74%

Figure 2: Comparison Analysis of the Selected Rankers Features Selection Methods with For Each Model

IV CONCLUSION

In this research, Comparative Analysis of Selected Filtered Feature Rankers Evaluators for Cyber Attacks Detection was proposed using UNSW-NB15 intrusion detection network dataset. The dataset contained nine attacks and one normal traffic types with 49 features some of which were not suitable for the effective detection of existing and new attacks. Four selected Filtered Feature Rankers Evaluators ((Information Gain, Relief F, Gain Ratio, and Correlation) were applied to the dataset to select it suitable and relevant features to model intrusion detection systems of KNN and Naïve Bayes machine learning algorithms. The Results of the features ranking shows that Relief F features ranker selected thirteen (13) features, Information Gain features ranker selected fourteen (15) features, Gain ratiom selected fifteen (14) features, while correlation ranker selected eleven (11) features. Features selected by Relief F recorded the best performance, Gain Ratio recorded the second best performance. Correlation and information Gain recorded the third and the fourth performances respectively, while the use of all the features recorded the least and poorest performance, this result shows the importance and ability of the Rankers Features Selection Techniques to improve the performance of intrusion detection models. All the KNN models recorded better performance than all Naïve Bayes models. The models' performance were measured in terms of Classification /detection accuracy, precision and false alarm rate. The results further shows models of KNN with the reduced features of Relief F features selection method recorded the best overall performance for the detection of network packets of UNSW-NB15 intrusion detection dataset.

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Conflict of Interest

The corresponding author states that there is no conflict of interest.

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Applications of IoT in Smart Grids Using Demand Respond for Minimizing On-peak Load

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Abstract

Increased on-peak loads requests have gotten quite possibly the most difficult issues addressed by numerous electric utilities and governments. Electricity power outages in developing nations are an everyday reality because of expanded economic activities. Consequently, traditional electric grids are being changed into smart grids (SGs) to address such issue of on-peak loads events. SGs enable "bi-directional" electricity and data flow between electric utilities and end-uses, and utilize different gadgets deployed at power plants, distribution centers and in customers' buildings for checking and control the grid functions. Consequently, a SG requires automation, tracking and connectivity of such gadgets. This is accomplished via the applications of Internet of Things (IoT). IoT supports different functions of SG frameworks through the generation, transmission and utilization of energy by deploying IoT gadgets (like sensors), just as by giving the

connectivity, computerization and tracking for such gadgets. In this paper, we present a comprehensive overview on IoT helped SG frameworks, which incorporates the current models, applications and models of SG - based IoT frameworks. This overview likewise features the roles of demand response (DR) programs and fog computing paradigm needed for SG-based IoT systems.

keywords: Internet of Things (IoT)- information & communication technology (ICT)- on-peak loads - peak loads reduction- smart grid (SG)- IoT in SG - demand response (DR)- fog computing (FC).

1- Introduction

The loads profiles in power systems are characterized with the on-peak load occurrences of the system (brief timeframes when a lot of electricity is demanded by consumers). The on-peak load events can happen at various occasions throughout the day, contingent upon the period of the year and the load usage whether by "residential", "business", or "industrial". Fulfilling electricity required particularly in on-peak events has an extensive issue to electric utility. as, this peak request is influenced on the planning of power systems as the structures of power transmission and dissemination should be intended to deliver the maximal requests on the electricity. For this reason, the electrical energy grid infrastructure possibly underutilized more often than not, arriving at its capacity limit at a little events of the year. Thusly, "commercial" and "industrial" consumers are charged with their complete energy utilization as well as their highest demand on electricity which dominates the power system development costs. The power charge can be separated in sub-segments like the generation cost, assessments, and expenses which address a little bit of the electricity consumptions bill of the clients. Likewise, industrial and commercial clients are keen on diminishing their consumptions costs, which are the main piece of the complete charges, without bringing down their electricity utilization. Besides, the electric grids address some different difficulties too, such as growing requests on electricity, unwavering quality, availability, arising sustainable power sources and maturing foundation issues and another some problems. To settle these difficulties, the SG worldview today is considered a favorable architecture that based on advanced technologies in areas of information and networking. These technologies would enhance the availability, effectiveness, quality, securing trends, support, soundness as well as versatility in the whole power grid system [1].

SG contrasts from conventional power grids in numerous perspectives. For example, SGs offer a "bi-directional communication" stream between electric utilities and end-users, but conventional power grids just offer "uni-directional communication" from the electric utilities to the end-users. SGs support Advanced Metering Infrastructure (AMI), adaptation to internal failure, smart meters, unapproved utilization

recognition, and load adjusting, just as self-recuperating, i.e., discovery and recuperation from faults [2]. SG takes care of the issue of electricity wastage by producing electrical energy that intently meets the request on electricity. SG assists with settling on significant choices as per the request of energy, like constant valuing, self-mending, scheduling electricity utilization and streamlined electrical energy use. These facilities can fundamentally improve the electricity quality just as the effectiveness of the power system by keeping a harmony between electricity production and its use [3]. SG conveys different kinds of gadgets for checking, investigating and controlling the grids. these observing gadgets are conveyed at "power plants", "transmission lines", "transmission towers", "distribution centers" and end-users buildings, and their numbers add up to the many millions or even billions [4]. The existence of smart meters available at end-users' premises and the facilities of two-way correspondences are the fundamental specialized making way for "demand response" (DR) (Figure 1) technique that applied into "smart grid". DR is a promising innovation in "smart grid" to provide the always expanding on-peak loads through peak load shaving methods that is performed by service providers and clients to diminish the pressing factor on electrical power grid and reduce the consumptions bill costs of clients. As per the US Power Branch, DR alludes as "the services developed to enhance movements on electricity prices and offering different payments programs to encourage end-users to improve their consumptions" [5]. Basically, current studies typically talk about two DR classifications: "Cost perspective "and "incentive perspective "; every class has its advantages and exploit benefits of various directions of the potential for adaptable demand. Nonetheless, between different DR solutions and services, "real-time pricing" (RTP) has been viewed as the most productive and financial value procedure to decrease peak-to-average proportion of demand.

Figure 1: presentation of demand Response via two-directions flows of "power" and "information".

SG projects primary worry are the communications and monitoring for about greater than millions of devices that need conveyed monitoring via two-way digital interchanges. Thus, they would based significantly on appropriated mechanization offered by "Internet of Things" (IoT) innovation. IoT is characterized as

"millions of linked things acting with each other based on internet" [6]. Recently, IoT innovation is acquired extremely consideration within different solutions; in addition it took into account the "Internet" role in connecting different gadgets utilized in our everyday life. IoT is actual objects network associated with the Internet. These things would be furnished with implanted technologies to enable them to work probably within its network. The things in that network could process and work independently in a circulated, autonomous and pervasive way via advanced connectivity facilities. So, it is the actual requirement to establish the successful Smart Grids projects. Consequently, IoT innovation able to helping smart grids projects by offering different capacities for power system operations including the generation, transmission, distribution, saving and utilization by fusing IoT gadgets (like sensors and smart meters), in addition to allowing communications, computerization and controlling for these gadgets [7]. SGs are considered as perhaps the biggest IoT applications. Basically, all that utilizes power could be made more valuable by associating it to the Internet, (for example, microwaves and clothes washers which are associated with the Internet can be worked distantly and during off-peak events, along these lines saving expense, just as give individuals comfortable via automation). Subsequently later on, it would be imagine that the architecture based on the coordination between IoT and the intelligent grids will be huge than today, and this advanced and smart framework (like SG) won't be conceivable without the IoT innovation. Ordinarily, Secure, adaptable and consistently accessible bidirectional stream of continuous data is the substance of things to develop SG. Rather than depending on chronicled information, usage of ongoing data empowers electric utilities to more satisfactorily react to expanding and fluctuating of power utilization, change power streams to fulfill need, and consequently reduce on-peak loads occasions. Sending huge amounts of data from an immense number of heterogeneous smart gadgets to a distant and Cloud servers for additional investigation and analysis is a genuine problem and it requires time. Distributed applications, better depicting of SG, and requirement for quicker reaction infer that the Cloud-based SG situation is maybe not the most fitting. The likely solution for Cloud-related "bandwidth" and "latency" issues is found in "*Fog computing*" approach that is set up on nearby and distributed data processing facilities, subsequently altogether decreasing time and amounts of the transmitted data. Fog paradigm doesn't supplant the Cloud, it diminishes the time and amounts of the transmitted data by the Cloud by executing data processing near to where information are being delivered. So, just preprocessed data and results are being post to the Cloud for additional examination and lasting stockpiling that diminishes latency and resolve transmission capacity issues. *In this study*, we introduced a good survey about the application of smart grids-based IoT technology and the application of the demand response programs and fog computing needed for successful implementation of the smart grids-based IoT projects. From the applications perspective, few numbers of studies that talked about the SG-based IoT solutions were published. We interestingly summarized the state-of-art on the applications of IoT

supported both Smart Grids (section 8) and demand response programs (section 9). Also in section 10, we summarized the state-of-art of the fog computing needed for SG-based IoT.

2- On-Peak load problem

Within energy community the term “peak load” is used to describe one of the major challenges that have to be addressed by electrical utilities. The “Peak load” has been defined by many professions, experts, academics, and technicians in various studies, reports, and formal websites. According to [8], peak load is “an event where electricity is relied upon to be accommodated during consumption is fundamentally higher than normal production points.” Moreover, one of interesting definitions has been supported by “Low-Income Home Energy Assistance Program Clearinghouse” that described it as “the highest level of request on energy through specific time” [9]. Another effort introduced by The Energy Vortex that defined the “peak load” and its interchangeable term “peak consumption” as “the greatest amount of electricity to be generated during period where consumption at the greatest point.” [9]. In fact, on-peak load event would happen every day, every month, or every year. For electrical utilities, peak load may last for half-hour or hour that indicates the maximum demand of electricity consumption by end-users. In German or chine industry sector, the peak event happens in “day time”, while in Australia, it often causes in the “late afternoon” to “early evening time” (example: 4 pm to 8 pm) [8]. The occurrence of on- peak load depends on the “economy”, “weather”, “climate”, “demography”, the “day of the week” and other factors. During on-peak periods, the prices of electricity consumption is expensive than the prices of consumption at off-peak load periods. This differentiation in the consumption prices returns to, the electrical utilities need to exchange their generators with biggest ones or to involve other alternative generation resources to be able for supplying the requested electricity of on-peak events. The key reasons behind the occurrence of electricity shortage during on- peak time are: 1) the total amount of requested electricity is more than the maximum capacity of generated electricity, 2) Lacks of fuels needed for power generation that negatively impacts on the reliability of power supply. So, the utility have to balance between the power generation and the electricity consumption within the power system by applying advanced technologies and developing alternative systems like “renewable energy generation systems”.

3- The Smart grid (SG)

The Smart grid (SG), the comprehensive revolution in power grid also known as “intelligent grid”, “grid wise”, “EPRI’s Intelligrid”. SG is basically using information and communications technology for improving the conventional power grids in terms of availability, reliability, quality, efficiency and security. In other words, the SG is a term that integrates “information and communications technology” with the “traditional

power grids” for creating two-directions of communications inside each node of the power grid system using “advanced metering infrastructure (AMI)”. SGs allow electricity end-users to involve in power system to schedule their electricity consumption, this facility extensively improve overall power reliability and availability of the grids and typically reduce electricity consumptions especially during on-peak events. The smart grids development and implementation are typically response to the continuously advancements in various emerging technologies such as distributed electricity storages systems, computing power, renewable energy systems, and sophisticated communications. Today, high number of SGs projects is developed which applies advanced information and communication technologies in the grid applications, involving smart machines, devices and appliances of end-users level to build responsive and flexible power system. Moreover, these SGs projects applies advanced solutions, programs and services integrated with smart controlling, monitoring, connectivity, and self-healing technologies to: 1) enable end-users to take part in enhancing the whole power system processes, 2) provide end-users with interesting information that help them in schedule their electricity consumptions. Last but not least, SGs promise much great potential in various aspects such as improving power reliability, efficiency and quality, ability to establish and utilize renewable energy systems, ability to address many malicious attacks and enhance the security dimensions, decreasing in requested electricity during on-peak events, ease of repair adverse natural events and also decreasing transmission overcrowding expenses. In addition, SGs optimize the utilization of “Renewable Energy systems RESs” and “Demand-Side Management” methods through sending real-time data to control center unit, for balancing the production and usage at the consumers’ level.

4- Demand Response (DR)

Demand response has considered a critical part for advanced grids in which it enables electricity consumers to changing their patterns of consumptions to decrease their bills. On other words, DR is a set of services and programs that offer grid end-users the opportunity to involve in processes of grid system by decreasing or moving their needed loads during the occurrence of on-peak event. Ref [10] indicated that DR is the “services and methods for allowing consumers to change their usage patterns of electricity to avoid the consumptions during events of high electricity prices” [10]. Actually, the DR main objective is concentrated on making reductions in consumptions during on-peak occurrence. DR address on-peak load challenges through giving consumers chance to decrease their needed loads in which it resulted in mutual positive affects and financial benefits for the utility and consumers. There are various intelligent methods that enable consumers to be involved in smart grid demand response (or power system) like “Direct Load Control (DLC)” techniques that give the electrical utility the facilities to turn off smart machines and appliances

during on-peak load event. From functionality point of view, DR methods could be classified into three comprehensive groups as presented in **figure 2**:

- a) “Peak clipping” which aims to decrease on-peak demanded electricity to avoid the consumption to exceed the generation capacity. This method would reduce the end-users satisfaction and comfort as it limits portion of their requested loads.
- b) “Valley filling” aims to encourage the off-peak electricity consumption using electricity storage systems, like “storage facilities”.
- c) “Load shifting” aims to move the demanded electricity across the “time horizon”, like convert the consumption from “high-demand” to “low-demand” times, without any decreasing in total electricity consumption of the consumer over a day.

The electrical utility considers the DR programs as a significant and precious facility according to its great influence on power system in which they provide grid renovation efforts. In addition, they help in reducing the occurrences of peak load events, achieve more power grid availability; improve power translucence and efficiency, reduce CO₂ emissions.

Figure 2: The DR functionality

5- Communication systems

From power system point of view, the Communications systems architecture is the base needed to support the smart grids and its DR programs success, since the SG is based on the two-way communications system for improving power availability, reliability and avoiding electricity outage. This two-way communication facility enables the electrical utility and their consumers to involve effectively in the process of load management as; it provides smart monitoring for the available capacity of generated electricity during Demand Response event and allocating the required electricity. In general, the communication networks of smart grid system can categorized into three types as the following: a) Home Area Network (HAN) which links the smart appliances and machines in smart homes with the “communication gateway”. b) Neighborhood Area Network (NAN) that links a number of consumers inside a particular zone with the

center of electrical data. C) Wide Area Network (WAN) that links multiple NANs to the “Central Control Unit” as presented through **Figure 3**.

Figure 3: the smart grid communication infrastructure

The complication of these networks would lead to some difficulties during picking out a suitable networking connection cause various factors and capabilities have to consider based on the developed applications. As illustrated in **table 1**, different communication technologies which support the developed solutions of intelligent grids. One of recent pioneer ecosystem for ICT following revolution in mobile communications is the “IoT”. IoT is a paradigm which allows smart entities to be linked with each other via the internet for collecting and sharing data. Through the next sections, the IoT and its technologies as well as the possible and available IoT solutions supported smart grid and DR, would be discussed.

Table 1: networking Technologies for IoT_Smart Grid Applications

Technology	Protocol	Coverage Range	Application
Z-wave	Z-wave	Up to 30 m	HAN
Bluetooth	802.15.1	Up to 100 m	
Zigbee	802.15.4		
Wi-Fi	802.11x	Up to 50 km	HAN, NAN
WiMAX	802.16		HAN
Cellular	2G-4G		
Satellite	Satellite internet	Up to 100-6000 km	WAN

6-Internet of Things (IoT)

The information and communication technologies (ICT) world become more progression thanks to the recent revolution in sensing and networking technologies that link entities located everywhere. This connection and networking is called the “internet of things (IoT)”. Meantime the last few years, IoT has realized as Omniscient technology term. It visualizes a future as all digital objects able to be easily communicated together via adequate ICT to support the entire denomination of applications and services. According to [11], IoT can be defined as “a connectivity which able to link every smart things around us via internet to share and exchange data between each other for monitoring and managing these smart things”. Ref. [12], defined IoT as “a set of technologies subject to support efficient interaction and connection among huge various linked devices”. Moreover, [11] gives more detailed definition they defined it as “the organization of communicated advanced devices in which they supported with identifier in addition to abilities for sharing data with each other without any help of human”. Thus, via IoT paradigm may be almost objects surround us like “homes”, “intelligent grids”, as well as any entity (able to connect to internet) can integrate within IoT network. It is expected that this paradigm will connect 100 trillions of digital entities, and will extensively growth the Internet in terms of the size and scope. Typically, IoT concentrates on 3 elements namely “objects”, “Internet” and “semantic”. The “objects” that focus on intelligent and digital entities, things or devices can be engaged in IoT network like “RFID tags”, “sensors”, “cameras”, “GPS”...e.g. The “Internet” which defines the connectivity between huge numbers of smart entities using sophisticated communication technologies (like “ZigBee”...e.g.) that connect them to Internet. The semantic element that refers to a set of developed solutions supported within various smart entities.

As reported by certified many world statistics we suffer from nearly “seventy percentage of gas emissions” also our energy consumption is about “seventy five percentage of the total primary energy” every year. IoT undertakes to convert civil zones into “smart cities” using advanced information technologies for addressing these problems, improving living quality, and accomplish sustain targets. IoT systems enable real-time data collection, smart management for energy resources, streamline data collection for “traffic and parking” aspects, reducing gas usage and CO2 emissions. IOT projects provide comprehensive solutions for many applications that improve

resources efficiency, the quality of life and serve various areas and sectors in our daily life (as presented in **figure 4**) include: “smart building”, “Smart Grid”, “emergency services”, “security”, “industrial management”, and “E-health” [12].

Figure 4: IoT Infrastructure

These recent applications require to be supported with advanced, wide utilized and common internet protocols. For response to these requirements, many consultation and experts took a significant part in this mission and conduct a list of standard Internet protocols that have to be so suitable at each specific layer of the IoT network stack for enable the interpretation into various Internet solutions. **Figure 5** presents the main “IoT” and the “Internet” protocols.

Internet		IoT
Application		Application
HTTP	Application	CoAP Request/Response
TCP	Transport	CoAP Message
IPv4/IPv6	Network	UDP
Ethernet/WLAN	Data Link/Physical	IPv6 + 6LoWPAN
		ZigBee, etc.

Figure 5: Protocols of “Internet” & “IoT”

7- Integration of the IoT into a SG

Typically, the smart grids based on the communications networks that enable intelligent and real-time monitoring and control. These modern grids have the same IoT characteristics; include smart data analyzing and lightweight techniques. Via IoT paradigm, the electric utilities in addition to their consumers can usage an advanced communications networks (Advanced sensors and intelligent gateways). Recently, various IoT capabilities offered on SGs projects were enticed a great attentiveness within information technologies and energy areas that resulted in “Internet of Energy (IoE)”. Thus, the IoT paradigm has a grand part in the smart grid system architecture. The considerable motivation behind increasing number of developing smart grid projects is to employ automation in the power system as well as to improve designing, conservation, quality and functionality with ensuring that all elements within the grid system are able to “listen” and “talk” to each other. For example, in traditional grids, the utilities could be notified about any service disturbance when consumer tells them. But, in smart grids the electric utilities would be automatically notified about any service disturbance according to a specific element of the smart grid will send the collected data to the “control unit”. Thus, the IoT owns a great part in the previous scenario as each SG’s component has its “IP address” and able to support two-way communication. Actually, IoT provides real-time network communications to the end-users and smart entities/things via sophisticated connection technologies. As well as, it provides the facilities and functions needed for recognizing fast and continuous delivery of data through different facilities which enable the SG to enhance its efficiency. The IoT applications supported smart grid functionality can be categorized into three classes according to the three basic layers of IoT build: Firstly, IoT application for realizing various smart objects linked within IoT network, for monitoring and controlling their status i.e., at “the perception layer of IoT”. Secondly, IoT application for collecting data from smart objects using advanced networking technologies i.e., at “the network layer of IoT”. Thirdly, IoT applications propose for smart monitoring and controlling of the SG operations using various applications i.e., at “the application layer of IoT”.

8- The IOT Applications in Smart Grid

There is a wide list of expected IoT applications that can aid SG operations some of these expected application have been exactly implemented, as shown in **Figure 6. Table 2** summarized the state-of-art on the applications of IoT supported Smart Grid. In the following, we present and explain the proposed IoT applications in SG introduced in the studies [13]–[39].

Figure 6: IoT applications in smart grid

Table 2: survey of the proposed IoT applications in smart grid

References	Smart Grid Area	Applications
[13]–[14]- [15]- [16]- [17]- [18]	Power Consumption	“Smart Home”
[19]	Power Consumption	“Information Management Systems for EVs”
[20]	Power Transmission	“Transmission Tower Protection”
[21] – [22] -[23]- [24] - [25]	Power Transmission	“Monitoring of Power Transmission Lines”
[26], [27], [28]- [29] - [30] - [31]	Power Consumption	“Renewable Energy Resources”
[32]–[33]- [34]- [35]- [36]	Power Consumption	“Power Demand Management”
[37]- [38]- [39]	Power Consumption	“Advanced Metering Infrastructure”

IoT application in Smart home: IoT technology has a key role in the smart grid by grasping smart machines, and appliances of smart homes and buildings. The smart home enable smart environmental monitoring through sensor and actuator nodes in which they send the oversight data for the “control unit” inside home [26]. The “control unit” allows individuals for controlling as well as monitoring their smart devices and appliances from anyplace at anytime. This unit also usages the data collected from various smart machines and appliances in order to reveal any critical event then convey individuals or consumers to take suitable actions. These facilities would only be recognized as a result of employing IoT technology. So, the smart home is considered one of a main portion of the SG for recognizing ongoing interconnection between consumers and the electric utility which improve the grid serving quality, enhance the power reliability, and to supply customers’ electricity demands in the most appropriate possible ways.

Information Management System-aided Electric Vehicle: EV is an eco-accommodating transportation facility aims to decreasing “carbon dioxide emissions” [19]. The EV charging framework is made out of a power supply system, charging gear and monitoring system. The power supply part where liable for the yield and the executives of power. The chargeable part “charges/discharges” the vehicles. The checking system is liable for ongoing observing of the charging system as well as security aspects. IoT takes a critical role within that monitoring system, as it offering data management capabilities that incorporate various elements within the chargeable part [19]. The GPS based IoT supported in **E-Vehicle** would assist driver in many purposes like finding the closest gas station in addition to sending the traffic data.

Advanced Metering Framework (AMI): Customarily, power utilization data was gathered physically on location at explicit time stretches. This event definitely prompted deficiencies regarding precision and idealness. “AMI meter” or “Smart Meter” is a progressed and computerized variant of the customary electric meters that is implemented external the home. An AMI framework is quite possibly the main elements of the Smart Grids, gathering the constant power utilization information with high dependability, preparing this data and henceforth giving continuous checking, measurements and power utilization investigation. Other than estimating the power utilization, AMI meters likewise send electricity and pricing data from service organizations to the end-users, along these lines permitting two way interchanges, on account of the IoT. By utilizing

this framework, IoT innovation could assist the end-users with setting aside cash by changing their power utilization patterns depended on the investigation of their electricity utilization.

Integration of Renewable Energy Resources (RERs): Renewable energy systems are dynamically incorporated into the present electric grid. Over last few years, many experts and academics give in impressive consideration in smart grid concentrates because of environment changes and natural pressing factors. Sustainable energy emphatically affects the worldwide climate by producing power without fossil fuel byproducts [27]. The main features of renewable energy sources in terms of generation patterns, they are irregular and depend on climate, area and environment, so they present critical difficulties for the predictability and availability of the demanded energy. Such issues are tended to utilizing the consistent interoperability and availability given by the IoT innovation. Besides, the IoT innovation utilizes advanced sensors to gather ongoing climate data that helps in estimating energy availability soon.

Management of Power demand: otherwise called “demand-side energy management”, is characterized as the adjustment in the power utilization patterns of end-users according to the moving in energy consumption costs by electric utility [40]. This activity is utilized to limit the customer's electricity bill, diminish the operational expense of the grid and energy misfortunes, in addition to minimize the requested load during on-peak events [41]. IoT gadgets gather the electricity consumption data of different home apparatuses and send them to the “home control units”. Hence, the SG control unit plans the electricity utilization of home apparatuses dependent on the customers' characterized inclinations so that every customer's electricity bill is reduced.

Online Power Transmission Monitoring: is perhaps the main employment of the IoT in the SG, explicitly for debacle anticipation and relief. Sensors would now be able to be utilized to accomplish continuous “electronic control for electricity transmission”. This recent electronic control framework involved the following parts: 1) the sensors that composited on the electricity transmission paths between transmission pinnacles for monitoring the status of transmission paths. 2) the subsequent part has sensors composited on the transmission pinnacles for monitoring their status and their ecological boundaries. IoT empowers the connection across the electricity transmission paths sensors and the transmission pinnacles sensors.

Transmission Pinnacle Assurance: it is a basic element of power transmission, created to upgrade the wellbeing of transmission towers from actual harm by ravaging of parts, catastrophic events, perilous development and developing trees under the establishments. With the assistance of WSNs, IoT innovation can enable distant observing for tending these security dangers. The IoT-aided transmission tower assurance framework includes different sensors that produce early alerts of dangers to high voltage transmission towers, empowering speedy reactions. The sensors incorporate vibration sensors, anti-theft bolts, an inclining sensor and a camcorder. These sensors and the sink hub structure a WSN. The sensors identify any danger, and impart the pertinent signs to the sink hub. The sink hub gets these signs from the sensors, processing them to get information and sends the information to the control unit.

9- The Applications of IoT-aided DR the integration of IoT and DR enables the consumers and electric utility to oversee electricity utilization by checking electricity use and changing utilization patterns for limiting cost and energy consumptions [42]. The critical features of DR are the improvement of ICT, in addition to the necessary connections and checking that help the DR procedures, for example, climbing to utilize the advanced metering foundation and IoT. Moreover, the IoT applications in DR got more consideration than the conventional applications of energy observing and control. In any case, the IoT application in DR of the existing studies primarily centered on in-home power management, as shown in **table 3**. But, less interest was considered to DR systems, which was produced depended on IoT for the utilization of electric consumers.

Table 3: Survey of the proposed IoT applications in DR

References	Network	Protocols	Main objective
[43]	HAN, WAN	IoT stack protocols	Propose WBFA algorithm to reduce “on-peak-to-average ratio”.
[44]			Develop a system to manage the linked smart devices within SG.
[45]			Propose a real time DR platform in intelligent grids.
[46]			Develop a framework for balancing load using IoT.
[47]			Establish extensive framework for managing load.
[48]	HAN		Integrate web service solutions with the smart meter for minimize load consumption.
[49]	HAN, NAN	Internet stack protocols	Multiple web services enabled devices offer metering data on an event based mode.
[50]	HAN, WAN	IoT stack protocols	Load management system to address peak events through adjusting pricing rate and managing load demand.
[51]		Internet stack protocols	Managing Load system to monitor home appliances and collect their consumption data and send notifications for the electric end-users on Twitter.
[52]	HAM		DR solution for controlling air conditioners based on online control feature.

Ghulam H. et al. [43], they proposed WBFA algorithm to methodically deal with the electricity management via utilization of IoT-empowered individuals to schedule their smart machines to reduce “on-peak events”, limit power consumption price, and augment consumers comfort (CC). The WBFA-based system consequently reacts to cost based DR services to address the serious issue of the DR programs, which is the limit of consumer's information to react after getting DR prices signals. They reported that their developed system beats the existing techniques in market regarding execution measurements.

Ashish K. et al. [44], they propose a monitor system for managing the linked smart apparatuses within a smart grid. This system is likewise equipped for arranging the network progressively. They evaluate the latency execution for their platform utilizing the suitably Orange communication network. It is seen that NB-IoT empowered smart gadgets could be controlled and checked with a

most extreme latency less than “8 seconds” in the “deep-indoor environment” and 2 seconds for the “outdoor environment”.

Luca B. et al. [45], they introduced a novel disseminated structure for on-going administration of DR in intelligent grid. Their structure allows a “close” real time co- simulation module to approve new DR-strategies using IoT technology to perform programming-in-the-loop. Thus, the conduct of true real-world power frameworks can be imitated in a sensible manner and diverse DR-approaches can be effectively implemented and potentially supplanted in a “plug and-play design”, without influencing the remainder of the structure. Also, this solution incorporates IoT associated smart gadgets at consumer level and along the Smart Grid to recover power data and send activation orders. In this way, the system is likewise prepared to oversee DR in a genuine Smart Grid. This is shown on a reasonable Smart Grid with an experiment DR-strategy.

Jacobsen and Mikkelsen [46], designed the framework project 7 (FP7), the European-subsidized scheme for smart power system, named “SmarHG”. The point of this venture is to assist end-users and the electric service provider to organize power utilization through IoT modules. The framework utilized open source conventions, for example, “smart energy profile 2 (SEP2)”, and “ZigBee IP”. This framework initially began in 2012 and ran through a 3 year time frame and spending about 4.5 million EUR.

Kelly et al. [47] represented a successful minimal cost and adaptable solution for home power management. The vital elements of the proposed model are the inconspicuous checking of homegrown uses, which give encompassing intelligence to diminishing the electricity utilization based on IoT innovation. The aftereffect of the developed solution displayed roughly 97% accuracy in detecting data transmission.

Altmann et al. [48] they structured a varied meter network to find a solution for the multi-seller problems. An Online smart metering platform was implemented utilizing a “device profile for web services (DPWS)” and brilliant message language. This platform is registered to any IP-based actual technology. To lessen the correspondence overhead, they utilized a CoAP convention rather than HTTP, and EXI was utilized rather than XML paired encoding. Consequently, the traffic overhead was decreased by more than ninety percentages. The recommended method could be applied in the DR module for checking the electricity utilization.

Karnouskos et al. [49] created practical intelligent metering in an event based framework. A multi-specialist framework and online services of the DPWS convention were utilized to gauge and assess a few gadget attributes. This methodology performs exact metering estimation for DR applications. As indicated by this arrangement, a solitary gadget can send its metering data to wide numbers of intelligent meters which were bought in. This framework enables detection for the new metering gadget automatically. A synchronization technique was applied for processing millions of smart meters for the genuine smart meter unit.

Ali et al. [50] developed a pricing strategy model using the Demand Response services supported by IoT. As indicated by the costs declared from the supplier, their model would control the consumers' apparatuses distantly when the peak events occurred. Consumers adjust their electricity utilization as indicated by the prices signs to boost their own advantages.

Lloret et al. [51] built up a minimal cost in-home power management framework. As indicated by this framework, the consumer incorporates the timetable of apparatuses and the ordinary activity (healthy statue) of every machine. At whatever time, an up- normal event is revealed on the “gateway”, the framework will notify the consumer through its account on Twitter. Besides, every consumer would be able to plan his/her timetable of the machines distantly.

Wu et al. [52] created the Demand Response framework that diminish the on-peak periods and limit electricity bills. The outcomes demonstrated that their framework would enable remote control for electricity consumption which will help in reduce the request on electricity and the outflow of carbon dioxide every year.

10- Cloud and Fog Computing for IoT-Aided SG Systems

Smart grid utilizes smart meters that able to gather and convey power utilization data as well as private individuals' data, for example, electricity consumptions data at gadget level and so on. The continuously advancement of power frameworks requires the intelligent grids to encourage constant management and checking of all power system operations thanks to two-paths of data and power offered by these intelligent grids. Smart meters generate high data quantities which need to extensive capabilities for processing and storing it. Thus, the “Cloud computing (CC)” is the best

choices in this case as it provides sophisticated facilities to perform these tasks. “Cloud computing” gives flexible assets and administrations partook in “communication network”, “parallel processing”, as well as “omnipresent access”. In CC distant shared resources and information are given to end-users who demand them. It offers three models to allow access to the shared “computing resources”. The cloud computing frameworks own outstanding abilities that enable exchanging information in or out these frameworks. Because of these abilities, cloud computing takes great interest in the power field. Firstly, power industry endeavors to create environmentally friendly power energy to forestall an Earth-wide temperature boost. Cloud computing is the ideal possibility to accomplish effective and efficient green energy delivering. Venture and operational expense is another explanation, as CC runs on inexpensive data centers. **Figure 7** portrays CC technology within the intelligent grid where the end-users’ as well as the electric utility are connected to the cloud.

Figure 7: Cloud computing in smart grid

Despite the fact that the CC model is considered a proficient for intelligent grids, it neglects to ensure the “Quality-of-Experience (QoE)” necessities for the grids administrations, inactivity, transmission capacity, energy utilization, and communication cost. These challenges can undoubtedly be tended by “fog computing”. It is an exceptionally virtualized paradigm that stretches out the cloud computing to the edge of the network so that “computation”, “storage” and “networking services” can be locally conducted. In this manner, “fog Computing” is an environment that offers a spot for gathering, analyzing, putting away data received from smart meter prior to sending them to cloud, as demonstrated in **Figure 8**. This platform performs as an extension between smart grid and cloud. It is topographically allocated and redesigns cloud

computing through extra abilities including diminished latency, expanded security and locality for smart grids.

Figure 8: Proposed fog computing model in smart grid

Hussain M. et al. [53] they develop a mathematical framework for a regular fog based SG model that clarifies the Planning and Arrangement of fog computing in SG (PPFG). Essentially, the proposed PPFG system is an “Integer Linear Programming (ILP)” problem that decides the ideal area, the limit and the quantity of Fog Computing Hubs (FCH) for limiting the whole network deferral and energy utilization of network components. our proposed model has been running on a little network of “30 Electric Vehicles (EV)”, “10 FCHs “and “one cloud server”, they clarified the processing of PPFG. Truth be told, the authors executed a total investigation that resulted in more readily comprehend the working of every constraint in the PPFG model. The “NSGA-II algorithm” performance was additionally compared with the outcomes got by the conventional ILP solver.

Saman Z. et al. [54] developed the cloud/fog framework to asset the whole operation of smart grids. Their vital thought about this framework is to decide a leveled design of cloud and fog facilities to give various services for SG asset processes. As to execution improvement of cloud computing, distinctive load adjusting procedures are utilized. For load adjusting between a SG “client's solicitations” and “service providers”, five techniques were actualized. Additionally, they developed a mixture method called “hybrid artificial bee ant colony optimization (HABACO)”. The findings of their Simulation reported that the HABACO method outperformed other algorithms.

Forcan M. et al. [55] this paper centers on the development of communication framework models to be utilized for voltage profile observing and power misfortunes assessment in SG. A notable “IEEE

13 feeder power framework network model” is utilized for simulation investigation of proposed communication platforms and later acquired outcomes uncovered their preferences and disadvantages. The “Cloud- Fog based methodology” has shown a generous decrease of absolute simulation time and data amounts being shipped off the Cloud. Along these lines, the favorable circumstance that fog processing layer integrated with SG monitoring is approved. The proposed communication structures can be effortlessly altered and adjusted to provide smart monitoring in SG with different geographies and directions.

Rabindra K. et al. [56] in this investigation, the use of fog computing for a “microgrid” framework is proposed, mentioned and assessed. The design of the fog and cloud computing are thought about. It has been discovered that the fog level goes about as an auxiliary layer to cloud computing where the data can be put away and recovered momentarily and allow the smart meters operate autonomously. The outcomes acquired illustrate the adequacy of Fog computing for smart grid architecture regarding reduced power consumption, decreased storage necessity and overlay examination abilities. The principle task is to instruct the energy research staff to overhaul such progressive constructions for execution.

Huang Y. et al. [57] designed an edge computing system for ongoing observing, that moves the computation away from the incorporated cloud to be close to gadget edge servers. To amplify the advantages, they form an extensive schedule for additionally improve the system as well as develop a productive technique depended on the strengthening methodology. According to the presented outputs, their suggested system would decrease latency eighty five percentage contrasting with the cloud arrangement.

Hussain M. et al. [58] they at that point implement an expense advancement model for FC that mutually explores data of customer affiliation, burden allocation, virtual machine position requirements. After testing their implemented model they found out the general delay in service in case of fog computing was extremely less than the delay in case of cloud worldview. They additionally realized that the Fog Computing brings down the energy utilization of the cloud computing paradigm by over forty four percentage.

Javed A. et al. [59] they researched the reconciliation of organizing local electricity that needs cloud facilitates for obtaining and processing data to build up an on-peak and off-peak timetable to charge electricity storages during off-peak periods. The framework utilized these electricity storages for reduce on-peak electricity occurrences. Their methodology exhibits that the prediction method could join with a transformation technique for assessing delay contemplations.

Conclusion

SGs are developed for solving a number of main issues in the traditional grid such as on-peak load and energy wastage. The IoT paradigm enables connectivity that can help SGs by allowing the grid for monitor and control every operations and devices in the grid. Real-time, reliable, secure, and efficient supplying of electric power in high-quality considers as the key role of the SG in which it represented as the power network combined with various advanced ICTs. Our survey focuses on address the issues of on-peak loads events and Electricity power outages through discussion the development of communication systems especially the Internet of Things applications as well as the integration of Cloud and Fog computing approaches to support SGs and its DR programs. Thus, a number of significant existing research focuses on the IoT applications in SG is briefly overviewed as well as the existing research focus on Cloud and Fog computing approaches that needed for the implementation of IoT-aided SGs projects.

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Track A: Security

Access control, Anonymity, Audit and audit reduction & Authentication and authorization, Applied cryptography, Cryptanalysis, Digital Signatures, Biometric security, Boundary control devices, Certification and accreditation, Cross-layer design for security, Security & Network Management, Data and system integrity, Database security, Defensive information warfare, Denial of service protection, Intrusion Detection, Anti-malware, Distributed systems security, Electronic commerce, E-mail security, Spam, Phishing, E-mail fraud, Virus, worms, Trojan Protection, Grid security, Information hiding and watermarking & Information survivability, Insider threat protection, Integrity
Intellectual property protection, Internet/Intranet Security, Key management and key recovery, Language-based security, Mobile and wireless security, Mobile, Ad Hoc and Sensor Network Security, Monitoring and surveillance, Multimedia security ,Operating system security, Peer-to-peer security, Performance Evaluations of Protocols & Security Application, Privacy and data protection, Product evaluation criteria and compliance, Risk evaluation and security certification, Risk/vulnerability assessment, Security & Network Management, Security Models & protocols, Security threats & countermeasures (DDoS, MiM, Session Hijacking, Replay attack etc.), Trusted computing, Ubiquitous Computing Security, Virtualization security, VoIP security, Web 2.0 security, Submission Procedures, Active Defense Systems, Adaptive Defense Systems, Benchmark, Analysis and Evaluation of Security Systems, Distributed Access Control and Trust Management, Distributed Attack Systems and Mechanisms, Distributed Intrusion Detection/Prevention Systems, Denial-of-Service Attacks and Countermeasures, High Performance Security Systems, Identity Management and Authentication, Implementation, Deployment and Management of Security Systems, Intelligent Defense Systems, Internet and Network Forensics, Large-scale Attacks and Defense, RFID Security and Privacy, Security Architectures in Distributed Network Systems, Security for Critical Infrastructures, Security for P2P systems and Grid Systems, Security in E-Commerce, Security and Privacy in Wireless Networks, Secure Mobile Agents and Mobile Code, Security Protocols, Security Simulation and Tools, Security Theory and Tools, Standards and Assurance Methods, Trusted Computing, Viruses, Worms, and Other Malicious Code, World Wide Web Security, Novel and emerging secure architecture, Study of attack strategies, attack modeling, Case studies and analysis of actual attacks, Continuity of Operations during an attack, Key management, Trust management, Intrusion detection techniques, Intrusion response, alarm management, and correlation analysis, Study of tradeoffs between security and system performance, Intrusion tolerance systems, Secure protocols, Security in wireless networks (e.g. mesh networks, sensor networks, etc.), Cryptography and Secure Communications, Computer Forensics, Recovery and Healing, Security Visualization, Formal Methods in Security, Principles for Designing a Secure Computing System, Autonomic Security, Internet Security, Security in Health Care Systems, Security Solutions Using Reconfigurable Computing, Adaptive and Intelligent Defense Systems, Authentication and Access control, Denial of service attacks and countermeasures, Identity, Route and

Location Anonymity schemes, Intrusion detection and prevention techniques, Cryptography, encryption algorithms and Key management schemes, Secure routing schemes, Secure neighbor discovery and localization, Trust establishment and maintenance, Confidentiality and data integrity, Security architectures, deployments and solutions, Emerging threats to cloud-based services, Security model for new services, Cloud-aware web service security, Information hiding in Cloud Computing, Securing distributed data storage in cloud, Security, privacy and trust in mobile computing systems and applications, **Middleware security & Security features:** middleware software is an asset on its own and has to be protected, interaction between security-specific and other middleware features, e.g., context-awareness, **Middleware-level security monitoring and measurement:** metrics and mechanisms for quantification and evaluation of security enforced by the middleware, **Security co-design:** trade-off and co-design between application-based and middleware-based security, **Policy-based management:** innovative support for policy-based definition and enforcement of security concerns, **Identification and authentication mechanisms:** Means to capture application specific constraints in defining and enforcing access control rules, **Middleware-oriented security patterns:** identification of patterns for sound, reusable security, **Security in aspect-based middleware:** mechanisms for isolating and enforcing security aspects, **Security in agent-based platforms:** protection for mobile code and platforms, Smart Devices: Biometrics, National ID cards, Embedded Systems Security and TPMs, RFID Systems Security, Smart Card Security, Pervasive Systems: Digital Rights Management (DRM) in pervasive environments, Intrusion Detection and Information Filtering, Localization Systems Security (Tracking of People and Goods), Mobile Commerce Security, Privacy Enhancing Technologies, Security Protocols (for Identification and Authentication, Confidentiality and Privacy, and Integrity), Ubiquitous Networks: Ad Hoc Networks Security, Delay-Tolerant Network Security, Domestic Network Security, Peer-to-Peer Networks Security, Security Issues in Mobile and Ubiquitous Networks, Security of GSM/GPRS/UMTS Systems, Sensor Networks Security, Vehicular Network Security, Wireless Communication Security: Bluetooth, NFC, WiFi, WiMAX, WiMedia, others

This Track will emphasize the design, implementation, management and applications of computer communications, networks and services. Topics of mostly theoretical nature are also welcome, provided there is clear practical potential in applying the results of such work.

Track B: Computer Science

Broadband wireless technologies: LTE, WiMAX, WiRAN, HSDPA, HSUPA, Resource allocation and interference management, Quality of service and scheduling methods, Capacity planning and dimensioning, Cross-layer design and Physical layer based issue, Interworking architecture and interoperability, Relay assisted and cooperative communications, Location and provisioning and mobility management, Call admission and flow/congestion control, Performance optimization, Channel capacity modeling and analysis, Middleware Issues: Event-based, publish/subscribe, and message-oriented middleware, Reconfigurable, adaptable, and reflective middleware approaches, Middleware solutions for reliability, fault tolerance, and quality-of-service, Scalability of middleware, Context-aware middleware, Autonomic and self-managing middleware, Evaluation techniques for middleware solutions, Formal methods and tools for designing, verifying, and evaluating, middleware, Software engineering techniques for middleware, Service oriented middleware, Agent-based middleware, Security middleware, Network Applications: Network-based automation, Cloud applications, Ubiquitous and pervasive applications, Collaborative applications, RFID and sensor network applications, Mobile applications, Smart home applications, Infrastructure monitoring and control applications, Remote health monitoring, GPS and location-based applications, Networked vehicles applications, Alert applications, Embedded Computer System, Advanced Control Systems, and Intelligent Control : Advanced control and measurement, computer and microprocessor-based control, signal processing, estimation and identification techniques, application specific IC's, nonlinear and adaptive control, optimal and robot control, intelligent control, evolutionary computing, and intelligent systems, instrumentation subject to critical conditions, automotive, marine and aero-space control and all other control applications, Intelligent Control System, Wiring/Wireless Sensor, Signal Control System. Sensors, Actuators and Systems Integration : Intelligent sensors and actuators, multisensor fusion, sensor array and multi-channel processing, micro/nano technology, microsensors and microactuators, instrumentation electronics, MEMS and system integration, wireless sensor, Network Sensor, Hybrid

Sensor, Distributed Sensor Networks. Signal and Image Processing : Digital signal processing theory, methods, DSP implementation, speech processing, image and multidimensional signal processing, Image analysis and processing, Image and Multimedia applications, Real-time multimedia signal processing, Computer vision, Emerging signal processing areas, Remote Sensing, Signal processing in education. Industrial Informatics: Industrial applications of neural networks, fuzzy algorithms, Neuro-Fuzzy application, bioInformatics, real-time computer control, real-time information systems, human-machine interfaces, CAD/CAM/CAT/CIM, virtual reality, industrial communications, flexible manufacturing systems, industrial automated process, Data Storage Management, Harddisk control, Supply Chain Management, Logistics applications, Power plant automation, Drives automation. Information Technology, Management of Information System : Management information systems, Information Management, Nursing information management, Information System, Information Technology and their application, Data retrieval, Data Base Management, Decision analysis methods, Information processing, Operations research, E-Business, E-Commerce, E-Government, Computer Business, Security and risk management, Medical imaging, Biotechnology, Bio-Medicine, Computer-based information systems in health care, Changing Access to Patient Information, Healthcare Management Information Technology. Communication/Computer Network, Transportation Application : On-board diagnostics, Active safety systems, Communication systems, Wireless technology, Communication application, Navigation and Guidance, Vision-based applications, Speech interface, Sensor fusion, Networking theory and technologies, Transportation information, Autonomous vehicle, Vehicle application of affective computing, Advance Computing technology and their application : Broadband and intelligent networks, Data Mining, Data fusion, Computational intelligence, Information and data security, Information indexing and retrieval, Information processing, Information systems and applications, Internet applications and performances, Knowledge based systems, Knowledge management, Software Engineering, Decision making, Mobile networks and services, Network management and services, Neural Network, Fuzzy logics, Neuro-Fuzzy, Expert approaches, Innovation Technology and Management : Innovation and product development, Emerging advances in business and its applications, Creativity in Internet management and retailing, B2B and B2C management, Electronic transceiver device for Retail Marketing Industries, Facilities planning and management, Innovative pervasive computing applications, Programming paradigms for pervasive systems, Software evolution and maintenance in pervasive systems, Middleware services and agent technologies, Adaptive, autonomic and context-aware computing, Mobile/Wireless computing systems and services in pervasive computing, Energy-efficient and green pervasive computing, Communication architectures for pervasive computing, Ad hoc networks for pervasive communications, Pervasive opportunistic communications and applications, Enabling technologies for pervasive systems (e.g., wireless BAN, PAN), Positioning and tracking technologies, Sensors and RFID in pervasive systems, Multimodal sensing and context for pervasive applications, Pervasive sensing, perception and semantic interpretation, Smart devices and intelligent environments, Trust, security and privacy issues in pervasive systems, User interfaces and interaction models, Virtual immersive communications, Wearable computers, Standards and interfaces for pervasive computing environments, Social and economic models for pervasive systems, Active and Programmable Networks, Ad Hoc & Sensor Network, Congestion and/or Flow Control, Content Distribution, Grid Networking, High-speed Network Architectures, Internet Services and Applications, Optical Networks, Mobile and Wireless Networks, Network Modeling and Simulation, Multicast, Multimedia Communications, Network Control and Management, Network Protocols, Network Performance, Network Measurement, Peer to Peer and Overlay Networks, Quality of Service and Quality of Experience, Ubiquitous Networks, Crosscutting Themes – Internet Technologies, Infrastructure, Services and Applications; Open Source Tools, Open Models and Architectures; Security, Privacy and Trust; Navigation Systems, Location Based Services; Social Networks and Online Communities; ICT Convergence, Digital Economy and Digital Divide, Neural Networks, Pattern Recognition, Computer Vision, Advanced Computing Architectures and New Programming Models, Visualization and Virtual Reality as Applied to Computational Science, Computer Architecture and Embedded Systems, Technology in Education, Theoretical Computer Science, Computing Ethics, Computing Practices & Applications

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